

Social Forecasting: Evolving a Model for Indian Business Process Outsourcing Industry

THESIS
SUBMITTED FOR THE AWARD OF THE DEGREE OF
Ph.D. (BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION)

BY

K.PRABHAKAR

Under the supervision of

Dr. Mrs. SALMA AHMAD,

Reader,

Faculty of Management studies & Research,
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh -202002

DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION
FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT STUDIES AND RESEARCH
ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY
ALIGARH -202002, INDIA

2009

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

It is my privilege to begin this acknowledgement by expressing my profound sense of gratitude to revered supervisor Dr.Salma Ahmad for her guidance and intellectual stimulation throughout the present study. Her suggestions, research acumen, immense interest, and empathetic behavior have been an inspiration for me. I convey my profound gratefulness to Prof. Javaid Akhtar, Dean, Faculty of Management Studies and Research, Aligarh Muslim University, for his help and unstinted support throughout the course of research. I am grateful and indebted to Prof. Mohammed Khalid Azam, Chairperson, Faculty of Management Studies and Research, Aligarh Muslim University for providing me guidance and encouragement to complete the thesis. I thank Dr. Mohammed Naved Khan, Reader, for providing me guidance regarding research methodology. Special thanks to Prof. Athar Ali Khan, Department of Statistics, Aligarh Muslim University for providing me guidance on statistical analysis. I thank my co research scholars Mr. Shahid Mustaq and Mr. Saif for helping me to review my work to complete my research. I thank specially Dr. Katia Caldri, Professor, University of Padova, Italy for providing me a scholarship to attend STOREP-2007 summer school research training at Italy. The interaction with Professors from Europe provided me with immense clarity with respect to sociological perspectives

for my present research. I am thankful to teaching and non-teaching staff of Department of Business Administration, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh for always being kind and helpful to me. I specially thank Mr. Thirumalai for consistently helping me have access to different BPO organizations in Chennai. I thank specially ten human resources managers of BPO organizations who formed a panel to provide research inputs for present study. A special thanks to Dr.S.Rajarajeswari and Prof.Vijay Kumar for providing me moral support and help.

I am thankful to K.S.Rangasamy, Chairperson, KSR College of Technology and Mr.R.Srinivasan and Ms. Kavitha Srinivasan who provided me with necessary financial help.

I dedicate the work of mine to my grand mother M.Rajeevakshamma and my uncle M. Ramanujam Naidu who always encouraged me to reach higher levels of thought. I thank my mother Swarajyalakshmi and mother in law Kamala, my dearest sister Sujatha, my brother- in- law Ravikumar and my nephew Dr.Leelu Mohan. I thank my uncle Mr. Govindarajulu for his moral support. I take this opportunity to thank Ms.Elena Barba Acquisition Editor, LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing AG & Co. for providing me encouragement, support by way of suggestions and documentation for publication this thesis work.

She has taken special care to see that this work is to the satisfaction of international standards. Two persons who are most important and lovable

in my life and present success of completion of research go to my wife
Alamelu and to my dearest son Rajiv Ramanujam.

31/12/2009

Krishnamurthy Prabhakar

profkprabhakar@gmail.com

Preface

The present research is an application of social forecasting. On a broader plank, Can future be forecasted? The answer is not affirmative. If there is something known or defined as '*the future*' then it can be attempted. The word future is a relational term (Bell, 1973) it can be discussed as the *future of something*. Is it possible to forecast results? The answer is more not affirmative. Forecasts can specify the constraints or limits within which decisions can be effective. Forecasting has different modes. Social forecasting differs from other modes in its scope and techniques. The most important distinction is study of sociological variables that are independent or exogenous and least precise, which affect the behavior of other variables. In the present study, an attempt is made to study sociological variables such as individualization of work and value priorities and project them within the social framework of business process outsourcing industry.

Business process outsourcing industry is the fastest growing industry creating highest number of jobs across the world (Holman, Batt, and Holtgrewe, 2007) and India is a major player in the this sector. The industry's variability, novelty, technological intensity, work intensity with new sociological, anthropological, and economic networks at the intersection of globalization provide challenging opportunities for research.

Ferni and Metcalf (1998) undertook pioneering research with respect to human resources issues and called the industry as modern age sweatshops- far from the depiction of knowledge worker of twenty first century. In India, the employees are paid higher salaries compared to other industries for same qualifications. The industry is growing at highest rates compared to other industry sectors, indicating a win-win situation for all stakeholders. However, the industry is facing highest attrition rates in the world to the tune of 40%, with employees complaining disillusionment with jobs. Press publishes violation of cultural codes and changing lifestyles of employees. This context, present study is undertaken to address the issue of job attrition by using methodology given by social forecasting.

The study is organized into five chapters. The first chapter introduces the genesis of Business Process Outsourcing Industry, its definition, growth, human resources issues, and discusses research for the past decade. This is to understand the nuances of industry that are different from that of Information technology industry as well as from other industries. It tries to portray human resources challenges of the Indian Business Process Outsourcing Industry and in the process establishes need, objectives, and significance of the study. Social forecasting which permits use of eclectic approach is introduced with definition, its relation with other types of

forecasting, model procedure and validation process with required elaboration. Economic forecasting, demographic forecasting technological forecasting and political forecasting is provided for BPO industry for the period 2009-2014.

The second chapter deals with literature survey and has four objectives. The first is to provide contextual clarity and examine the research with respect to BPO organizations in the areas relating to job attrition and job satisfaction, and in the process, establishing gaps in the literature. The second objective is to answer the need for social forecasting and initiation of social forecasting process. The third objective is to consider conceptual model for research and the fourth objective is to present typology of BPO organization. As suggested by researchers, social forecasting commence with the study of values. A detailed study of values is undertaken to clarify definitional issues. Values and its relation to attitude and behavior are reviewed. Role scope and need for its study is examined. The concept of individualization and its importance for study in the era of changes in life course and network economies is deliberated. A model for present research is discussed.

The third chapter deals with addressing issue relating to research methodology adopted for the present study. Theory borrowing of organizational studies especially from sociology is studied. Subsequently, research methodology, hypotheses, research model, instrument design, sampling method, validity, and reliability are considered. The conceptual underpinnings and assumptions regarding job satisfaction are discussed. Hypothesized model is proposed and the limitations of the study are provided.

Analysis and findings are presented in the fourth chapter. The first section concerns analysis and testing of hypotheses regarding sociodemographic characteristics of sample. The study variables are analyzed using factor analysis, cluster analysis, and multi dimensional scaling and given in the section two to five. In the process, abstractions are developed from details of observed phenomena with identification of latent constructs with appropriate nomenclature. The constructs are formalized in the form of typologies. The sixth section related to establishing preliminary relationship within study variables with the help of statistical tools and testing hypotheses, to construct a prototypical model for further testing. The final section is devoted to rigorous testing of the model using logistic regression tool to identify vital predictors for job satisfaction model.

The fifth chapter presents major findings in the context of economic, technological, political issues. The managerial implication of suggestions is delineated. Finally, topics for future research are suggested.

Date: 31/12/2009

K.Prabhakar

Dedication

This Thesis is dedicated to Daniel Bell, Distinguished Professor of Sociology, Harvard University, USA. His work has inspired sociologists and social thinkers for the past five decades. This is a small tribute to the great thinker and social philosopher of 20th Century.

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

Title of Paper	Journal/ Proceedings	Organizations	Date
Social Forecasting: Relevance in strategic Planning for Corporate Sector	10th International Strategic Management Forum Conference	Indian Institute of Technology, Mumbai	June 2007
Methodological Premises of Social Forecasting in the Context of Business Organizations	Second National Conference on Management Science and Practice	Indian Institute of Technology, Chennai and Indian Institute of Management, Ahmedabad	March 9-11 2007
Social Forecasting: Relevance in Strategic Planning	7th STOREP Conference	University of Padova, Italy	September 5-16 2007

Contents

Chapter Overview.....	1
1.1 Background of the Study.....	1
1.2 Performance of Indian BPO Industry.....	3
1.3 Genesis of Business Process Outsourcing Industry.....	5
1.4 Business Process Outsourcing Introduction and Definition.....	9
1.5 Research in Business Process Outsourcing Industry First Stage.....	13
Second Stage.....	14
Gendered Workplace.....	22
Commonalities and Differences in BPO Operations.....	23
Age of Operating Firms.....	24
National and Global Markets.....	24
Business Strategy.....	25
Customer Segmentation.....	25
Common organizational features.....	26
Selection, Staffing and Training Strategies.....	26
Nonstandard Work Arrangements and Flexibility.....	27
Work Organization.....	27
Performance and Monitoring.....	28
Teamwork.....	28
Collective Representation and Compensation.....	29
Outcomes of work and Job Design.....	31
Summary of Different Approaches to Research.....	36
1.6 Need for the Study.....	38
1.7 The Problem.....	39
1.8 Social Forecasting Introduction.....	41
Social Forecasting in the Context of Business.....	44
Social Forecasting relationship with economic forecasting and technological forecasting.....	45
Elements of Social Forecasting.....	47
Forecasting Social Trends.....	51
Effectiveness of social forecasting in different contexts.....	54
Model Procedure for Social Forecasting.....	55
Validation Process of Social Forecasting Model and Applications.....	57
Social forecasting Applications in business organizations.....	58
1.9 Social Forecasting for BPO Industry.....	59
Basic Assumptions.....	60
Method Used for Social Forecasting.....	60
Time Frame.....	60
Identification of important phenomena.....	61
Selection of phenomena for deeper study.....	61

1.9.1	Economic Forecasting Global economic downturn	62
	Growth Prospects for India (2008-2010)	64
	Economic Forecast and BPO Industry	68
1.9.2	Demographic forecasting	69
	Decline in fertility rate.....	69
	Increase in life expectancy.....	69
	Rise in the median age.....	70
	Ageing population	70
	Share of labour force to the total population.....	70
	Demographic Forecast for BPO industry.....	71
1.9.3	Technological Forecasting	72
	Kondratieff Curves – Introduction.....	73
	Social Phenomenon of Kondratieff Curves.....	75
	Validity of K-wave phenomenon.....	75
	Technological Forecasting for BPO Industry	81
1.9.4	Political Forecasting.....	82
1.10	Justification of the Study	83
1.11	Objectives of the Study	84
1.12	Significance of the Study.....	85
Chapter 2	Review of Literature Chapter Overview	86
2.1	Research Context.....	86
2.2	Research and Issues of BPO industry	89
2.2.1	Emotional Exhaustion, Conscientiousness, and Role Clarity.....	90
2.2.2	Skill levels of Employees and Job Satisfaction.....	91
2.2.3	Performance Monitoring Controls in BPO.....	93
2.2.4	Psychological Contract and BPO Employment.....	97
2.2.5	Teams and Team work in BPO Operations.....	98
2.2.6	BPO Employee Attitude towards Union Membership	102
2.2.7	BPO Employee Satisfaction Survey-India	102
2.2.8	Study by Occupational Physicians	104
2.3	Technology- Axial Principle to Scrutinize the Different Dimensions of Society.....	106
2.3.1	Social Forecasting and Dimensions of Society	109
	Western Societal Structure.....	109
	Indian Societal Structure.....	110
2.3.2	Essential features of Social Forecasting.....	110
2.3.3	Initiation of Study of Social Forecasting.....	112
2.4	Values.....	112
	Values Definition.....	113
	Dimensions of Value System.....	115
	Value Types- A Paradigmatic Explanation.....	116
	Figure 2.1 Locations of Ten Value Types in a Two-dimensional Space.	119

Nature of value priorities	120
Value priorities as guides for best living	121
Value Priorities to Value Typologies.....	122
Typology of Value Carriers	123
2.5 Value Priorities – Work Related Behaviour - Job Satisfaction.....	124
2.6 Job satisfaction Introduction.....	126
Job Satisfaction-Definition	127
2.6.1 Absenteeism and Attrition Relationship with Job satisfaction	129
2.7 Role Scope	130
Role negotiation.....	132
2.8 Occupational Changes Due to Technology	133
2.9 Individualization.....	136
2.9.1 Individualization and Life Course Research	137
Measurement of Individualization	144
2.10 Typology of BPO Organizations	144
Expressive Cycle and Instrumental Cycle.....	147
Partial Inclusion, Potency of Involvement, and Priority of Commitment	149
Table 2.4 Present typology of a typical BPO organization	152
2.11 Research methodology adopted for study.....	154
Chapter 3: Research Methodology Chapter Overview	158
3.1 Research Methodology.....	158
3.2 Theory Borrowing in Organization Studies.....	159
3.2.1 Cross-level and Cross-Context Borrowing.....	159
3.3 Research gap	162
3.4 Research Problem.....	163
3.5 Research Statement	164
3.6 Research Objectives	164
3.7 Hypotheses	165
3.8 Research Design.....	167
3.9 Sources of Data	168
3.10 Instrument Development	168
Demographic data.....	168
Job Satisfaction.....	169
Assumptions regarding BPO employees’ satisfaction	170
Value Priorities	172
Analysis of Value Priorities.....	173
Three Dimensional Scaling of Value Types	175
Role Scope.....	180
Individualization of work.....	181
3.11 Suggested Research Model.....	182
Pilot Testing.....	183

3.12	Validity and reliability of the instrument Introduction	184
	Discriminant validity	185
	Reliability	186
3.13	Sampling Procedure and Questionnaire Administration.....	187
	Sample Unit	188
	Sample Frame	189
	Time and Space.....	189
	Sample Size Determination.....	189
	Sampling Methodology.....	190
	Data Coding.....	191
3.14	Tools and techniques used for data analysis.....	191
	Multidimensional Scaling.....	192
	Exploratory Factor Analysis	193
	Factor- Cluster Approach.....	194
	Logistic Regression.....	195
	Model Estimation fit	196
	Predicative Accuracy	197
3.15	Limitations of Study	198
	Chapter 4: Analysis and Findings Chapter Overview.....	201
4.1	Sociodemographic Analysis	201
	Two Dimensional Scale Job Satisfaction	214
	H ₀ 4: Job satisfaction groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.	215
	Inference	216
	Inference	217
4.3	Analysis of Role Scope.....	218
4.3.1	Nomenclature for Role Scope Dimensions	221
4.3.2	Definitions of Dimensions of Role Scope	223
4.3.3	Cluster analysis - Role Scope.....	224
	Two Dimensional Scale Role Scope.....	227
	H ₀ 5: Role scope groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.	229
	Inference	230
4.4	Analysis of Value priorities	231
4.4.1	Nomenclature for Value Priorities Dimensions.....	233
4.4.2	Definitions of Dimensions of Value Types.....	236
	Inference	239
	First Quadrant Third Quadrant Social Context of Outcome versus Individual Context of Outcome Paradigm	239
	The fourth quadrant-Focus on Opportunity –Focus on organization Paradigm	240
	Inference	241
4.4.3	Analysis of Value Typology	242
	Analysis of Inter correlation Coefficients of Value Priorities.....	246
	Inference	248

4.5	Analysis of Individualization of work	249
4.5.1	Nomenclature for Individualization of Work	251
4.5.2	Definitions of Dimensions of Individualization of work.....	252
	Inference.....	255
	Inference	258
	Analysis of Inter Correlation Coefficients of Individualization of Work	258
	Analysis of Bivariate Correlation Coefficients of Individualization of Work and Value Priorities.....	260
	Inference	262
	Inference	262
4.6	Analysis - Relationships within Study Variables.....	263
	Job Satisfaction with Role Scope.....	263
	H ₀ 8: Job satisfaction group and role scope group are independent.	263
	Inference	264
	Job satisfaction with Value Priorities.....	264
	Inference	265
	Job satisfaction with Individualization of work	265
	H ₀ 10: Job satisfaction group and individualization of work group are independent.	265
	Inference	266
	Value priorities with Role Scope	266
	H ₀ 11: value priorities group and role scope group are independent. H ₁ 11: value priorities group and role scope group are dependent.	267
	Inference	267
	Individualization of Work and Role Scope.....	268
	H ₀ 12: Individualization of work group and role scope group are independent.....	268
	Inference	269
	Value Priorities and Individualization of Work	269
	H ₀ 13: Value priorities group and individualization of work group are independent.....	269
	Inference	270
4.6.1	Summary -Relationships within Study Variable	271
	Inference	271
4.7	Goodness-of-fit Test for Job Satisfaction Model using Logistic Regression.....	273
4.7.1	Justification for Use of Logistic Regression	273
4.7.2	Coding of Data for Analysis	274
4.7.3	Conditions for Logistic Regression.....	275
	Inference	275
	Independent Variables	277
	Inference	279
	Inference	281
4.7.5	Predictive Accuracy	283
4.7.6	Validation Analysis.....	283
	Inference	284

4.7.7	Outliers and Influential Cases	285
4.8	Summary of findings and human resources model for BPO organizations.....	286
	Figure 4.18 Human Resources Model for BPO organizations	288
	References	309

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1	Turnover and Growth of BPO Sector in India (2004-2009)	4
Table 1.2	Employment in BPO sector in India (2004-2009)	4
Table 1.3	Annual Earnings of Call Centre Agents and Managers (Dollar Value as in the year 2007)	13
Table 1.4	GDP Forecast 2008-2009 and 2009-2010	66
Table 1.5	Number of United States of America Jobs Moving Offshore	67
Table 1.6	Cyclical Patterns of Innovation	79
Table 1.7	India's political and economic vulnerability ranking	83
Table 2.1	Types of Skill-Matching and Satisfaction Levels	91
Table 2.2	A selection of values definitions	114
Table 2.3	Value Types, definitions, and representative values	118
Table 2.4	Present typology of a typical BPO organization	152
Table 3.1	Questionnaire structure	182
Table 3.2	Validation of Instruments used for research	184
Table 3.3	Reliability Scores for different testing instruments	186

Table 4.1 Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Respondents	202
Table 4.2 Major Functional Areas of Respondents	203
Table 4.3 Segments of Work Area of Respondents	204
Table 4.4 Gender and Work Area Classification	205
Table 4.5 Social status and work area classification	206
Table 4.6 Religion and Work area Classification	207
Table 4.7 Descriptive Statistics of Job Satisfaction Dimensions	209
Table 4.8 Descriptive Statistics of Job Satisfaction Groups	211
Table 4.9 Z-Values for Dimensions of Job Satisfaction	212
Table 4.10 Cross Tabulation of Job satisfaction Groups with Sociodemographic Variables	215
Table 4.11 Chi-Square Tests for Job Satisfaction Dimensions with Social Variables	216
Table 4.12 Total Variance Explained for different components of role scope	219
Table 4.13 Role Scope Dimensions Identified through Factor Analysis	220
Table 4.14 Descriptive Statistics of Role Scope Dimensions	222
Table 4.15 Descriptive Statistics of Role Scope Groups	224

Table 4.16 Inter Correlation Coefficients ^a of Role Scope Dimensions	225
Table 4.17 Cross Tabulation of Role Scope Groups with Sociodemographic Variables	229
Table 4.18 Total variance explained for different components of Value priorities	231
Table 4.19 Value Priorities Dimensions Identified through Factor Analysis	232
Table 4.20 Change in the Mean Values to Reflect the Value Dimensions	234
Table 4.21 Identification of Value Types Relating to Factor Analysis Output	235
Table 4.22 Descriptive Statistics of Value Priorities Dimensions	237
Table 4.23 Descriptive statistics of value priorities groups	240
Table 4.24 Analysis of Value Typology of Respondents	240
Table 4.25 Intercorrelation Coefficients of Value Priorities Dimensions	245
Table 4.26 Cross Tabulation of Value Priorities Groups with Sociodemographic Variables	247

Table: 4.27 Total Variance explained for different components of individualization of work 249

Table 4.28 Individualization of Work Dimensions Identified through Factor Analysis 250

Table 4.29 Descriptive Statistics of individualization of work dimensions 253

Table 4.30 Descriptive statistics of individualization of work groups 254

Table 4.31 Analysis of Three Dimensional Representation of Individualization of work Dimensions 256

Table 4.32 Intercorrelation coefficients of Individualization of Work Dimensions 257

Table 4.33 Bivariate Correlation Coefficients between Individualization of work and Value Priorities 258

Table 4.34 Cross Tabulation of Individualization of work Groups with Sociodemographic Variables 260

Table 4.35 Summary of Sociodemographic Variables relation with Study Variables 261

Table 4.36 Cross tabulation of job satisfaction group with role scope group
262

Table 4.37 Chi-Square Test for cross tabulation of job satisfaction group
with role scope group 262

Table 4.38 Directional measures of job satisfaction group with role scope
group 263

Table 4.39 Cross tabulation of job satisfaction group with value priorities
group 263

Table 4.40 Chi-Square Test for Cross Tabulation of job satisfaction group
with value priorities group 264

Table 4.41 Directional Measures for job satisfaction group with value
priorities group 264

Table 4.42 Cross tabulation of job satisfaction group with individualization
of work group 265

Table 4.43 Chi-Square Tests for job satisfaction group with individualization
of work group 265

Table 4.44 Directional Measures for Job satisfaction group with
Individualization of Work Group 265

Table 4.45 Cross tabulation of Value Priorities Group with Role Scope Group 266

Table 4.46 Chi-Square Tests for cross tabulation of value priorities group with role scope group 266

Table 4.47 Directional Measures of Value Priorities Group with Role Scope Group 266

Table 4.48 Cross Tabulation of Individualization of Work Group with Role Scope 267

Table 4.49 Chi-Square Test for Cross Tabulation of Individualization of Work Group with Role Scope 267

Table 4.50 Directional Measures for Individualization of Work Group with Role Scope Group 267

Table 4.51 cross tabulation of value priorities group with individualization of work group 268

Table 4.52 Chi-Square Test for Cross Tabulation of Value Priorities Group with Individualization of Work Group 269

Table 4.53 Directional Measures for value priorities group with individualization of work group 269

Table 4.54 Initial Classification by Logistic Regression Analysis	274
Table 4.55 Variables in the equation at step zero	275
Table 4.56 Variables not in the Equation	276
Table 4.57 Overall Model Fit Goodness of Fit Measures	277
Table 4.58 Sociodemographic Variables in the Solution after Step 1	278
Table 4.59 Classification table for sociodemographic variables effect on Job Satisfaction ^a	279
Table 4.60 Overall Model Fit Goodness of Fit Measures	279
Table 4.61 Study Variables and interaction variables in the Equation in Step 2	280
Table 4.62 Classification table with study variables and interaction variables in the final solution	282
Table 4.63 Classification matrix of randomly selected cases and holdout sample cases for validation	283
Table 4.64 Case-wise List of Outliers	285

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1.1 Representation of Social forecasting definition 45
- Figure 1.2 World GDP Growth rates 63
- Figure 1.3 Global Trade, 1981-2008 63
- Figure 1.4 Projection of GDP Growth rate 66
- Figure 1.5 The Generational- Learning Model of Long Waves 78
- Figure 2.1 Locations of Ten Value Types in a Two-dimensional Space
119
- Figure 2.2 Research process undertaken for study 155
- Figure 3.1 Research process adopted for the study 161
- Figure 3.2 Representation of modified Value Types in two-dimensional
space based on Schwartz Model 172
- Figure 3.3 Representation of value types in three-dimensional space
(Zeterberg and Zeterberg, 1997) 177
- Figure 3.4 Representation of value trajectory from Gemeinschaft to
Gesellschaft 178
- Figure 3.5 Depiction of different value carriers according to relative
position in the value dimensions 178

Figure 3.6	Hypothesized Models for Job Satisfaction of BPO Employees	181
Figure 4.1	Scores of Job Satisfaction Dimensions	209
Figure 4.2	Scores of Job Satisfaction Groups	211
Figure 4.3	Two Dimensional Model of Job Satisfaction	213
Figure 4.4	Scree Plot for Factor Analysis of Role Scope	218
Figure 4.5	Scores of Role scope dimensions	222
Figure 4.6	Scores of Role Scope Groups	224
Figure 4.7	Two Dimensional representation of Role Scope	226
Figure 4.8	Scree Plot for factor analysis of value priorities	231
Figure 4.9	Scores of Value Priorities Dimensions	237
Figure 4.10	Models of Value Priorities of BPO Employees	238
Figure 4.11	Scores of Value Priorities Groups	240
Figure 4.12	Three-dimensional Model of Value Priorities	242
Figure 4.13	Scree Plot for Factor Analysis of Individualization of work	249
Figure 4.14	Scores of Individualization of work Dimensions	253

Figure 4.15	Scores of Individualization of work groups	254
Figure 4.16	Three-dimensional Model of individualization of work	255
Figure 4.17	Prototypical human resources Model for BPO Organizations	270
Figure 4.18	Human Resources Model for BPO organizations	287
Appendix 1		298
Appendix 2		306
References		308

Chapter 1: Introduction

Chapter Overview

This chapter presents the genesis of Business Process Outsourcing Industry, its definition, growth, human resources issues, and discusses research for the past decade. It endeavors to delineate present human resources challenges of the Indian Business Process Outsourcing Industry and in the process establishes need, objectives, and significance of the study. Social forecasting which permits use of eclectic approach is introduced with definition, its relationship with other types of forecasting, model procedure and validation process with required elaboration. Economic forecasting, demographic forecasting technological forecasting and political forecasting is provided for BPO industry for the period 2009-2014.

1.1 Background of Study

Business process outsourcing industry is one of the fastest growing industries, creating highest number of jobs in economies across the world (Holman, Batt, and Holtgrewe, 2007). The industry is human resource and technology intensive, and capacities of firms vary from fifty employees to more than fourteen thousand with different types of

ownership. It offers employment both for graduates who are repeating given scripts and to engineers, doctors, and qualified accountants who are offering advice on technical, medical, and financial issues (Dormann & Zijlstra, 2003). The industry's variability, novelty, technological intensity, work intensity, with new sociological and economic networks at the intersection of globalization and liberalization, provide challenging opportunities for researchers across various disciplines. Russel (2008) opined that they have garnered attention both as a new means of organizing work and as an important venue from which to understand the study of other elements of management practice. The present interest is like textile mills or automobile factories, which were treated as both objects of curiosity and as metaphors for their age. India is one of the major players in this sector. According to data of National Association of Software and Service Companies, India, BPO industry offers direct employment to 11.5 lakh persons with annual turnover of 12.5 billion dollars for the budget year 2008 and estimated to grow at the rate of twenty-five percent yearly.

The industry growth in India is phenomenal albeit with human resources challenges such as attrition rate of employees to the tune of 40%, which is highest compared to same industries across the world. The employees are also experiencing low job satisfaction, and health issues

ranging from high stress to severe physical illness (Holman, Batt, and Holtgrewe, 2007; DQ-IDC Employee Satisfaction Survey, 2007). Fernie and Metcalf (1998) undertook pioneering research with respect to human resources issues that provided a basic framework followed by other researchers for the past decade. However, there is paucity of research in India to address human resources issues, which, if not addressed are likely to threaten the long-term viability of the industry. The present research is an attempt to address the issue of job attrition, job satisfaction using social forecasting methodology. Social forecasting is based on axial principle of technology for examining different facets of society, is believed to provide better insights not addressed by traditional approach. A brief mention of financial performance is provided here to understand the economic and financial aspects of BPO industry.

1.2 Performance of Indian BPO Industry

Indian share of global market for BPO is worth 12.5 billion of US dollars. Work force and its effective utilization is the key to success in the global market. The industry is also experiencing growth in terms of both employment and revenue. The following data provides a glimpse of growth of the business process outsourcing industry.

Table 1.1 Turnover and Growth of BPO Sector in India (2004-2009)

	FY*2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
BPO Exports & Domestic	3.4	5.2	7.2	9.5	12.5	14.8
Growth year to year basis		50%	38%	31%	24%	15.54%

*FY indicates financial year. (Figures in Billion USD).

SOURCE: National Association of Software and Service Companies- Facts Sheet updated on February 2009.

Table: 1.2 Employment in BPO sector in India (2004-2009)

	FY*2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
BPO Exports	5,34,000	6,68,000	7,80,000	9,31,000	11,50,000	12,89,806
Percentage		25%	16.7%	19.35%	23.5%	12%

*FY indicates financial year

SOURCE: National Association of Software and Service Companies- Facts Sheet updated on February 2009.

Though the number of persons employed in the BPO sector is comparatively lower to the persons employed in total service sector in India, this sector provides high visibility in the international arena for Indian expertise. India commands highest share in the BPO sector to the tune of 21% of global market, and global business organization have recognized its capability to deliver solutions (Gartner, 2006).

The salary and perquisites offered by BPO organizations to its employees are comparatively higher for comparable qualifications in other sectors in India. All these trends indicate highly favorable conditions of successful industry for all stakeholders. An understanding of the genesis of BPO industry and growth for the past decade provides better comprehension of human resources issues.

1.3 Genesis of Business Process Outsourcing Industry

Business process is any *'workflow'* that is required for producing an output. More commonly, the term is applied to the *production, distribution, or use of information*, either on behalf of other businesses or for the clients of such concerns. Business Process Outsourcing in simple terms stated as *"the delegation of a business process or workflow to an outside service provider who owns, administers and manages it according to a defined set of matrices as set forth in a contract (Greaver, 1999)."* During 1990's, at the nascent stages of industry, with this definition, it has been argued that organizations should divide activities into core and non-core and outsource non-core activities, for instance back office operations. Global organizations Nike and Dell and in India Bharti Telecommunications have outsourced activities that are considered traditionally core activities such as manufacturing and network

management as a strategy and have established phenomenal success. The success of strategy led organizations to reclassify activities as core and non-core based on outsourcing decisions as one of the strategic alternative. The activities that are not outsourced have become core activities of the organizations. For Nike and Dell, supply chain management has become core activity and for Bharti, marketing has become its core activity. It is observed that organizations choose to outsource not only because of cost minimization but also for resource access, resource leverage and risk diversification provided by BPO organizations, though cost minimization remains the major focus (Ramachandran and Mukherji, 2007). Based on its enlarged role, BPO is defined as *“an investment strategy for sourcing best practice process capabilities end-to-end along business value chains consisting of: the customer relationship chain, supply chain, organizational productivity chain, and product and innovation chain. It is intensively collaborative because it rests on lattice of the BPO client’s skills, technology base and processes with the BPO provider’s distinctive offerings. The outsourcing has multiplicative-strengthening capabilities along the value chain and not subtractive-process of off loading non core businesses.”* This definition captures the strategic role of outsourcing in organization’s decision-making.

It involves different value chains and helps to unlock value. However, for the purpose of present research focusing on human and technological dimensions, it is insufficient. There is also a need to answer the question as to why the industry had different nomenclature at different periods as call centre industry, information technology enabled services industry and presently, BPO industry. Examination of early stages of research from multiple disciplines and evolution of the industry will provide needed insight.

During initial stages, outsourcing was adopted relating to repetitive operations such as back office work; later customer service is brought within the realm of outsourcing. The first sector to use the concept is the telecommunication organizations for long distance operators and telephone directory assistance. System engineers developed technical innovations for effective handling of large volume of customer enquiries with the help of operations research models. With deregulation by governments in different parts of the world, the telecommunications organizations experimented with the call centre model expanding from simple transactions to complex services. (Mandelbaum, Sakov, and Zeltyn, 2001). The early studies and literature in operations management used to describe the process as call centre model and the word call centre is used in this context (Mandelbaum, 2004).

The call centre is defined *as any communications platform from which firms deliver services to customers via remote, real-time contact* (Norling, 2001). The contacts are either initiated by customers (i.e., inbound) or transactions initiated by employees (i.e., outbound). The employees are provided with explicit, specific operational guidelines in the form of ‘talk time’ (i.e., the phrase used in BPO to refer to targeted average call length) and customer interaction scripts. A study by Witt, Andrews and Carlson, (2004) found that the scripts generally specify not only the phrases to be used at different points of conversation (e.g., Thank you for calling XYZ company or How may I help you?) but also “display rules,” that are emotions to be manifested during interaction with customers. It is coalescence of digital technologies -fiber optics, switches, integrated voice recognition systems, predictive dialing capacity, web articulation, drop down call, screen capture systems, and development of automated call distribution systems¹ that lie at the heart of call centre technology and human interface processes. As the processes have matured, diffusion has taken place into other work areas such as administrative support, customer relationship management, sales and telemarketing, document processing, accounting, finance, payroll maintenance, human resources, training, intellectual property research,

¹ An important telecommunication technological innovation, where calls are allotted to different operators by their availability and optimize utilization of operators’ time.

legal services, medical transcription, product development, publishing, research & analysis, security, and supply chain management. The technology progressed from telephony to multi-channel communication such as voice, email, fax, and voice over internet protocol, web enablement, media blending, and electronic customer relationship management. At present, researchers refer the industry as call centre industry despite its change in characteristics. Nonetheless, for the purpose of present research, the term BPO is used to describe the industry. While ITES or information technology enabled services is a very different kind of industry from software, however, this is categorized together in India under 'IT'- because both come under the ambit of NASSCOM, the industry body that is active in promoting all these industries.

1.4 Business Process Outsourcing

Introduction and Definition

Business Process Outsourcing with human resource perspective is defined as *“the socio technical system of conducting business and described as specialized entity where agents or customer service executives remotely provide information, deliver services, and conduct sales including telemarketing and general commercialization of products and services, collection of information including surveys and market*

research , offer advise including financial ,insurance and medical using combination of integrated telephone and information technologies, with an aim to enhancing customer service while reducing organizational costs.” The use of the word socio-technical system indicates the importance attached to social outcomes of this technological innovation. The definition encompasses different models adopted by organizations. They are classified into three broad categories (Valverde, Ryan, and Gorjup, 2007).

1. External organizations or outsourced BPOs- outside operator performs the activity. Internal departments or internal call centres operated by the organizations themselves.
2. Inbound and outbound, according to the types of calls managed; customers (actual or potential) initiate the inbound calls; outbound are initiated by organizations.
3. There are three models operated by organizations. The lower end of the model is mass production model providing voice services addressing large volume markets with focus on minimizing costs. The other end is occupied by professional services such as medical, accounting,

human resources, intellectual property research and so on. Within this spectrum, there are hybrid models, which have both the characteristics. The major difference between these models is the compensation provided to employees (Batt, 2002) and control they exert on performance of tasks. While the professional services employees have higher control over their jobs, the lower mass production model employees have least control.

The industry growth and diffusion is driven by rapidly expanding information and communication technologies, re-engineered business processes, a changing profile of customer needs and expectations and a prevailing culture of occupational restructuring (Houlihan, 2000; Holman, 2002) and by operations management objective of converting high-contact service to low contact service while adhering to quality - quantity norms . The transformation of telephony by the development of digital exchanges, intelligent telephone networks and their integration with computer data bases; falling telephony costs and the introduction of toll-free numbers; the high degree of penetration and familiarity of telephone technology and the ability to communicate complex information by phone in real time (Richardson and Marshall, 1999), have spearheaded the industry growth.

As the business expanded to other areas especially customer service²², the name transformed to information technology enabled services as the activity is conducted as part of information technology initiatives. Realizing its importance due to expansion of outsourcing activity into different domains of business horizontally and vertically, the information technology services industry transformed into business process outsourcing industry and the same is used for the purpose of present study. Another reason for growth is drive towards reducing costs and cutting staff to face global competition —both of which can be accomplished by centralizing services, reducing branch offices close to the customer and taking advantage of lower cost real estate and labour costs in locations out-side main business centers (Richardson and Marshall, 1999). The centralization of service provision has enabled firms to rationalize the work process through the extensive use of information and communication technologies, thereby maximizing the use of service employees' time. The standardization of service encounters with customers and the use of “*functionally equivalent and interchangeable service providers from different geographies*” have also helped call centers to achieve great speed and efficiency in the delivery of their

² Two thirds of customer service of Fortune 500 companies is conducted through call centres enabled by information technology (Bakker, Demerouti, and Schaufeli, 2003).

services (Gutek, 1995). This is enhanced by technological developments, which allow for the disentanglement of time and place for both individuals and organizations.

As an outcome, organizations can concentrate on their “*customer information desk*” in a particular country and automatically route calls from a number of countries to this centre, without customers coming to know that they are calling local or international call. As a result, organizations have begun to move some of their labour intensive operations to low wage and low cost countries (Dormann and Zijlstra, 2003), sparking off the outsourcing trend. India has emerged as an important stakeholder in the outsourcing arena. Companies around the world find India a suitable destination due to the availability of skilled, English speaking labour whose wages are a fraction of the wages paid in the home country (Chithelen, 2004).

1.5 Research in Business Process Outsourcing Industry

First Stage

The research from 1948-1990 may be termed as the first stage of research with more technological orientation. The research in call centre models started with early telephony with Erlang (1948) and for the next three decades operational research models, forecasting (customer traffic),

Industrial engineering and simulation are the mainstream of research. From 1980s, business applications and human-computer interactions were given importance, followed by studies into the ergonomics of call centre work. Mandelbaum (2004) compiled research in these domains starting from early studies of Erlang. From 1990, the industry started growing exponentially and research started on the managerial aspects of the call centre.

Second Stage

In the second stage ushered in research for the past decade in various parts of the world addressed issues from different perspectives (Russell, 2008). Initially researchers were preoccupied with what constitutes call centre and how they are different from other service delivery organizations. Additionally, researchers considered the call centre as an object or unit of analysis *sui generis* that is, as a new socio-technical system for the production and delivery of information that is worth studying for its own sake (Russell,2008), suggesting that working with outdated assumptions about organization of capital and labour may not be helpful (Rainnie *et al.*, 2008).

The studies spanned around remuneration, cultural management, monitoring of employee performance, emotional labour³, high performance work systems, strategic management, and other related social, psychological, and human resources phenomena. Discussion papers by Fernie and Metcalf (1998), provided framework for understanding of call centres work and organizational analysis (Sewell and Wilkinson, 1992, Sewell, 1998; Russel, 2006). The focus of study was on management control and remuneration. The employee's performance is observed for the entire days' work including lunch breaks and management control was exercised based on the real time feedback. Therefore, the call centres are characterized as electronic sweatshops⁴ with panoptic⁵ controls. In this study for the first time, call centre employees are portrayed as new occupational category, distinct from

³ Hochschild (1983) defined **emotional labor** as the management of feeling to create a publicly facial and bodily display. It involves managing emotions so that they are consistent organizational or occupational display rules; regard less of whether they are in resonance with internal feelings.

⁴ **Sweatshop** is a working environment with conditions that are considered difficult or dangerous. Usually the employees, woman, and children, have few opportunities to address their situation and unsure of their employment and do not know their ultimate employer and know only their contractor referred as sweater. This can include exposure to hazardous situations, extreme temperatures, or abuse from employers. They often work long hours for little pay or laws may be violated. Sweatshops usually employ low levels of technology, but may produce many different goods such as toys, electronics, clothing, and furniture.

⁵ **Panopticon** is a type of building designed by English philosopher and social theorist Jerome Bentham in 1785. The concept of the design is to allow an observer to observe (*-opticon*) all (*pan-*) prisoners without the prisoners being able to tell whether they are being watched, thereby conveying Panopticon as "a new mode of obtaining power of mind over mind which is termed by Foucault (1977) as panoptic control.

clerical positions of the past. However, characterization of call centres as sweatshops is not vindicated by their research. Taylor and Bain (1999) study on BPO paved way for better insights.

The arrival of the BPO sector is due to deregulation, rise of global competition and globalization (Ellis and Taylor, 2006). The strategy of BPO was a response to the need for reducing costs and efficient delivery of information to customers. This led to re-examination of labor costs and *cost reduction* became the prime aim of organizations. As an outcome of this emphasis, BPO operations stand for Taylorization of white-collar work, subjecting work to templates of scientific management makes for an intense labor process. The research paper was titled *Assembly Line in the Head* (Taylor and Bain, 1999). Based on the work of making recording and actioning, conversation is subdivided into discrete elements, precise targets are set, and employees are made accountable and remunerated for the same (Bain *et al.*, 2002). Due to less control over their jobs and work intensification, it led to job stress (Taylor *et al.*, 2003). There is no possibility of constituting teamwork, as nature of tasks does not have possibility of creating teams (Van den Broek, 2002; Van den Broek *et al.*, 2004) and formation of teams only lead to team taylorism (Bain and Taylor, 2000, 2002a, 2002b; Baldry, Bain and Taylor, 1998). However, Korczynski (2003) is based on study of four call

centres, points to the fact that customer interaction is not always painful and sometime the employees enjoy interaction with customers and get disillusioned when faced with *customer abuse*. To overcome some of the pains of customer relations, the employees form communities of coping⁶, in the process overcome the problem of stress. The other point is balancing call timings and ensuring customer service. The higher the time taken to satisfy all the customer needs, the higher will be the customer satisfaction albeit with increase in costs and very few BPO organizations choose to ignore costs.

This limits the potential amount of variation in management control that is possible (Houlihan, 2000). Thus, BPO operations call for familiar forms of managerial challenge- eliciting employee co-operation, emotional labor, and discretionary work effort, while minimizing worker resistance. Frenkel *et al.*, (1998, 1999) suggested in place of Taylorism bureaucratic control, '*info-normative system of control*' due to involvement of customer in the service delivery process. This is articulated by Whyte (1946) who suggested that when customers and employees meet that relationship adds a new dimension to the pattern of human relations in industry.

⁶ Coping here refer to '*the way employees get through their working day*,' particularly how they deal with, and survive, the pain which abuse from customers can bring. Communities of coping can be seen as an important collective "*survival strategy*," for service employees. (Noon and Blyton, 1997, p.140)

The employees are requested to empathize with customers and this leads to looking at the interaction in a different direction. These are hybrid systems of management, while retaining the essential features of bureaucratic control such as compliance with rules and procedures; also introduce elements of professional or knowledge work such as empowerment and autonomy. Information technologies supply data on performance, while work place norms foster identification with the customer and his needs (Korczynski *et al.*, 2000). The info-normative control is characterized by '*facilitative styles of management,*' where information on performance is used for coaching and developmental purpose rather than for disciplinary purpose. In terms of employment, the employees assume the role of semi professional employees. The unit task in BPO operation is interaction with a customer for a very short period giving rise to *shorter work cycle*. Discretion building for an employee is difficult while considering work design and extracting cost economies. It is the limitation of info-normative system, and its use is limited. Fleming and Spicer (2004) addressed the issue of *social geography*. They studied the change in the separation of workplace and private domains of life and focus on the study of work and non-work boundary in contemporary organizations especially in call centres. They argue that there is a *two-way* cultural process, whereby practices considered as domain of

organizational life is transferred into the homes of employees, and private activities are carried out in organization. This is also supported by study of Kunda (1992) regarding high tech corporations that tried to appropriate as much time as possible of employees into organizational work, making them think that they are tech employees all the time. Because of this approach, the employees experienced burnout and role contradictions and other kind of pathologies.

BPO industry in a similar vein, through their cultural management, expect their employees to have fun, partying, joy, fulfillment, friendship and even sexuality are appropriate in workspace. Similarly, employees are requested to bring homemade food to be shared by others and things that are dear to them are required to be brought to office. In the process, the social geography of work and non-work is blurred and resulted in higher stress of working at the cost of family and other social relations.

Kinnie *et al.*, (2000a, 2000b) characterized the call centre as a paradoxical relationship between surveillance and fun. In this context, BPO organization created managerially constructed games and other planned social activities as an attempt to ameliorate the oppressive aspects of the labor process; this was characterized as *manufactured sociability*.

Initiatives such as fun factor, team hypes, symbolic awards, selective recruitment of young persons, focused training, performance related pay on the part of human resources management are also tried. These interventions are termed by researchers as '*fragility of fun*' (Houlihan, 2002), if they are followed by strict job designs and low trust managerial practices (Alferoff and Knights, 2001).

Two important questions can be discerned from the research- are different workflows possible and if so under what conditions? Second, can they make a difference to the way in which employees experience their work? Typologies are proposed for tasks to be performed by different authors (Batt and Moynihan, 2002; Fernie, 2004; Kinnie *et al*, 2000b; Wallace *et al.*, 2000) - such as differentiating between transactional, relational and hybrid forms of interaction with customers, under different regulatory regimes such as authoritarian, unionized and employee involvement. One of the important suggestions is the adoption of High Performance Work Practices, which is designed for manufacturing organizations. However, the practices designed need to be tailored to the needs of the BPO operations and there is cost associated with the strategy in the form of higher bonuses. Therefore, High Performance Work Practices in BPO industry experienced limited success.

Study by Wallace, Eagleson and Waldersee (2000) focused on the work performed when customer is involved in the service production process. They argued based on study of employees in Australia, that employees were selected based on their customer relating traits and they like the job.

However, they showed resentment for customers showing their anger towards them (called as customer abuse). They also felt demoralized as they cannot relate to co-employees with their problems as work design has no provision for the same. The researchers proposed '*Sacrificial Human Resources Strategy*.' They suggested using two types of managers, line, and relations-oriented managers. While line managers control the targets and performance, the relationship managers try to reduce the stress related to work. They argued that absence of relations-oriented managers leads to problems. The strategy did not propose any measures; its focus is to absorb stress as a natural outcome.

Cohen and El-Sawad (2007) studied call centre of financial organization of United Kingdom, which had an Indian base. The employees are from the same organization and geographically separated. The finding of the research was that Indians did not lose their identity and

They could maneuver the cultural labyrinth and perform to the expectations of their organization.

Gendered Workplace

One of the important phenomena pointed out by researchers is gendered workplace in BPO industry in different parts of the world. Women are constructed as ideal workers in many call centres. Call centre work is the epitome of what is commonly seen as women's work; providing good service on the telephone require skills associated with hegemonic femininity, such as being nice, making customers feel comfortable, and dealing with tough customers (Steinberg and Figart, 1999; Leidner, 1999). Salzinger (2003) traces the ways in which women are considered as ideal workers and femininity has been closely linked to productivity, and masculinity to sloth and disruption (Ong, 1991; Carty, 1997; Bergeron, 2001). While this is the condition in other parts of the world but in India, the situation is different. There is no gender discrimination in employment in BPO, people are treated equally for payment of wages and other benefits as per NASSCOM Report 2006. This dimension is addressed further in literature survey.

Commonalities and Differences in BPO Operations

Holman, Batt, and Holtgrewe (2007) conducted one of the most important studies on BPO organizations across- 2500 centres at 17 countries from 4,75,000 employees indicating commonalities and differences in call centre operations that provide insights into their working. The countries studied are clustered into three groups suggesting that national labor markets influence management strategies.

Coordinated or social market economies-they are with strong labor market regulations and influential labor market institutions such as unions or work councils. The implications for employers are, the wages are to be negotiated with unions or work councils and employees are to be provided with work place that takes care of occupational health of employees and also enforced by state – the countries are Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Israel, Netherlands, Spain, and Sweden.

Liberal market economies are those with more relaxed labor market regulation with less influential labor market institutions such as unions. The implications for employers are less of labor unions involvement in wage negotiations; however, they need to take care of occupational health of employees and other legislations- the countries are Canada, Ireland, United Kingdom, and United States of America.

Recently developed economies are Brazil, India, Poland, South Africa, and South Korea that are having few labor market regulations with no major unions or statutory requirements to take care of employee's occupational health except for South Korea.

Age of Operating Firms

The average age of firms surveyed is eight years (in 2007), ranging from a high of fourteen years in US to a low of six in India, indicating relative novelty of industry to the business world.

National and Global Markets

The important characteristics of this industry are relative mobility, flexibility, and ease of workflows routing to different organizational locations leading to scale economies. These have led to locational changes in different organizations from high-cost locations to low cost locations. Nonetheless, the survey indicated that 86% serve local, regional, and national markets with exception of India serving 73% of international markets. The spread of industry is based on historical language ties and culture- France to Morocco, Spain to Latin America, between US and UK to India, Canada to South Africa.

Business Strategy

The organizations have a choice to develop BPO operations (in-house operations), offer the same service through third parties, or sub contractors. Globally 67% are in-house operations, with exception of India 80%, working with sub contracting mode.

A typical sub-contractor may handle more than one organization to maximize use of labor force. Firms in India manage twenty-five clients across different verticals. (Thite and Russell, 2007).

Customer Segmentation

Technology helps to reach different segments of the market. Seventy five percent of BPOs serve general or mass market, where the volume of service and sales transactions are highest, with 25% serving business-to-business markets. The employees of mass market serving BPOs are having high standardization of work in the form of pre prepared scripts with least leverage for operators to deviate from scripts and subjected to higher levels of supervision giving rise to human resources issues. The business-to-business BPO employees are found to have less standardization with less supervision.

Common organizational features

The BPO organizations have flat structure with on an average 12% of employees consisting of managers, indicating less chance for career progression. The front line workforce consists of females 69% with exception of India 40%. Only 20% of organizations globally adopted twenty four hours operations compared to majority of Indian BPOs adopting twenty four hours and seven days a week operations(24×7). The performance matrices followed by BPO organizations across the world are remarkably same. For a standard call, the time allowed for an operator is one hundred and ninety seconds or three minutes and ten seconds with least variation in different countries.

Selection, Staffing and Training Strategies

Psychometric tests, aptitude tests, realistic job previews are used for selection of candidates in that order. Globally 50% use tests, BPO organizations in liberal and industrializing countries use selection tests more extensively than in coordinated countries. The average selection rates globally are 20% and in India, it is lowest with 7%. Globally only 22 % rely on university graduates. However, in India only college graduates and engineers are selected compared to any other country in the world. Indian BPO's use extensively selection tests for all candidates to

be selected. Globally 15 days training in classroom is given for employees and they take 11.5 weeks to be proficient in their job.

Nonstandard Work Arrangements and Flexibility

Full time, part time, or temporary contracts are used due to demand fluctuations. Globally 71% of jobs are of full time, 17% part time, and 12% temporary of nature. However, in India 97% employees are full time. Coordinated economies use non-standard arrangements due to pressure of unions work agreements. Globally thirty five percent provide flexible arrangements such as job sharing, telecommuting, and flexi time to balance family and work. Forty percent in coordinated economies and UK provide such flexible arrangements. In India, no flexible work timing is provided to increase work- life balance of employees.

Work Organization

Work organization is examined in the context of job discretion and work monitoring by managers. In-house cameras monitor the performance of employees for comparison with standards, and performance appraisal. Job discretion refers to the amount of choice that employees have while performing job tasks-such as pace of work, work methods and procedures, timing of breaks and lunch and response to

customers. If the call timing standards are violated, the data of performance is displayed on the same day with comparisons with other employees and standards. High level of standardization of work , scripting of text for call handling efficiencies, with high performance monitoring by managers lead to boredom, stress due to routinization and repetition. Therefore, high job discretion and low monitoring are considered as high quality jobs. Liberal markets have fifty-one percent with job discretion; coordinated economies have thirty percent with job discretion and in India with twenty-five percent have job discretion.

Performance and Monitoring

Calls handling times, task times, call-waiting times are monitored and supervisors can listen to employees' interaction recorded as well as online talk with customers at their discretion. In turn, they are provided with feedback on a weekly, monthly, and quarterly basis. Globally, feedback is given fortnightly. In India, several times in a week feedback is provided to employee.

Teamwork

As the technology ensures individual performance and ease of monitoring teamwork has not been used as a managerial control process- globally sixty percent and in India, ninety percent use no teamwork.

However, eighty percent of the organizations use problem-solving teams with three percent employees participating.

Collective Representation and Compensation

Globally seventy seven percent of the organizations have some kind of collective bargaining with unions and work councils in coordinated economies and liberal economies. However, in India there is no mechanism of collective bargaining. Pay relating to performance is adhered by the industry and globally 15.3 % is paid as performance pay. Most incentives are paid based on individual performance. The average annual income converted in to US dollar base as on 2007 provides the following results. The Indian employee equivalent is calculated for comparison purpose.

Table 1.3 Annual Earnings of Call Centre Agents and Managers (Dollar Value as in the year 2007)

Countries	Call Centre Agent		Call Centre Manager	
	Salary	Indian Employee Equivalent	Salary	Indian Employee Equivalent
Social Market Economies				
Austria	16,867	6.32	50,602	5.69
Denmark	44,516	16.69	66,129	7.43
France	22,755	8.53	41,820	4.70
Germany	33,264	12.47	75,600	8.50
Israel	9,333	3.49	16,267	1.83
Netherlands	16,770	6.28	61,920	6.96
Spain	17,690	6.63	62,220	6.99
Sweden	30,618	11.48	43,200	4.85
Liberal Market Economies				
Canada	34,165	12.81	60,000	6.74
Ireland	28,800	10.79	58,560	6.58
United Kingdom	27,300	10.23	50,116	5.63
USA	29,000	10.87	60,000	6.74
Recently Developed economies				
Brazil	4,484	1.68	26,906	3.02
India	2,667	1	8,889	1
Poland	6,954	2.60	18,300	2.05
South Africa	10,588	3.97	31,324	3.52
South Korea	13,816	5.18	34,736	3.90

SOURCE: Adopted from Holman, D., Batt, R. & Holtgrewe, U. (2007). The Global Call Centre Report, Global Call Centre Project. p. 28. (Researcher added the Indian Employee Equivalent)

An analysis indicates that Indian employees are paid lowest compared to other economies as well as within the industrialized economies. The overall employee wage cost globally is sixty-five percent with India having thirty-eight percent, which is lowest in the world. This indicates Indian industry is most competitive in pricing and with respect to quality of workforce higher than any other country in the world.

Outcomes of work and Job Design

The overall employee turnover globally is twenty percent, with Austria having four percent and India forty percent. The turnover cost of a call centre employee is sixteen percent of annual gross earning of an employee, which is equivalent to two months pay. In India, the cost is eight percent. Employee sick rate globally is six percent of workdays, with Israel having only one percent with India having eleven percent of workdays. Discretion to perform tasks and intensity of monitoring are factors found to affect the job satisfaction. High discretion to perform tasks and low intensity of monitoring are classified as high quality jobs and provide higher job satisfaction to the employees in turn contributing to fewer turnovers. The data indicate the trends globally forty-three percent jobs are high quality jobs, with fifty-two percent of low quality jobs, while in India three percent high quality jobs, with eighty-two

percent jobs with low quality. Regarding tasks in Indian BPO sector, employees- are given fictional names and addresses in customer country and they are asked to mimic mostly English accent of the client country, which is called scripted Taylorism (Mirchandani, 2004). This also leads to loss of identity and propensity to leave organization according to work by Das, Dharwadkar, and Brandes (2008). This is in addition to experiencing less control on work with higher monitoring than their western counterparts monitor. Research by D' Cruz and Noronha (2007) using case study methodology with technical call centres in India indicates that the tasks in the Indian technical outsourcing are having higher variety, with complexity, autonomy of work promoting employee well-being and satisfaction. D' Cruz and Noronha (2007) argued that the claim of characterizing BPO operations as contemporary Tayloristic sweatshops is an oversimplification. Considering labour force of India consisting of mixed gender profiles with higher educational qualifications compared to their western counter parts and employing western human resource strategies of strategic recruitment, performance management and incentivized remuneration have no effect on the employee attrition. (Batt *et al.*, 2006; Bhatnagar, 2007; Budhwar *et al.*, 2006a, b; Budhwar and Malhotra, 2008; Thite and Russell 2007).

The research with respect to India and rest of the world has provided a wide canvass of issues and challenges in BPO industry with very less agreement on solutions.

The other important dimension is the changing nature of work and organizations. Standing (1999) pointed out the crumbling of what he described as labour market security, which is a result of insecurity in employment, insecurity from income of employment and fragmentation and detachment of social protection regimes. Feltstead and Jewson (1999), point to a worldwide growth in flexible labour, new forms of work such as temping⁷. There is erosion of unions and governmental controls. Grugulis *et al.*, (2004) suggested emergence of the *hourglass* shaped occupational structure where skills are polarized implicitly suggesting disappearance of middle level jobs. In present economy, it has been argued that, there are few highly skill oriented jobs with very high salaries and large number of low skilled jobs with lowest salaries giving rise to *low skill ecosystem*. They argued that while jobs at low skilled areas increasingly became multifaceted the control of employees over their work did not rise, instead due to technology- task discretion and autonomy declined. The present organizational structures, unlike in the past, based on supply chain management, business process outsourcing,

⁷ Temping is short contract employment where employee is employed for shorter durations of work ranging from two to three hours a day with no significant employment benefits.

globalization and global delivery model lead to blurring of employee-employer relationship. In this scenario, in a debate between Glucksmann (2004), Taylor and Bain (2007) about research in call centre work suggested that it is to be shifted to robust “*economic sociology*.” A growing body of work argues that important changes are taking place in organizational structures leading to networked organization and network economy. DiMaggio (2001) concurs with this proposition, saying that the change is striking, but the long-term effects are yet to be perceived. Schienstock (2002) viewed the network concept as a new techno-organizational paradigm, or an organizational *Leitbild*⁸. The network forms may include clusters, public-private partnerships, multi-client service organizations, multi-employer-work-sites, agencies, and franchises. De Man, (2004) defines Networks as “*select sets of multiple autonomous organizations, which interact directly or indirectly, based on one or more alliance agreements between them. The aim of network is to gain a competitive advantage for the individual organizations involved and occasionally for the network.*”

Castells (1996) provided insights into sociological thought about work characteristics. Network society according to him, is defined as a

⁸ Leitbild: A set of general ideas of effective production and business structures.

“social structure, which is characterized, by networked communication technologies and information processing.” Communication networks are breaking down biological sense of time as well as logical sequence of time. The disappearance of distance in communication due to technology is another dimension. This also gave rise to phenomenon of individualization of work. Individualization is *“a process by which the individual increasingly become point of reference in the shaping of ones values and attitudes.”* Considering intuitively that higher levels of individualization have taken place in a person due to technological intensity work feature of BPO, there is a need to understand the role of values in shaping his or her perception towards industry. The other important factor to be considered is job satisfaction.

Locke (1976) defined job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from one’s job or job experiences. Job satisfaction also has been shown to have a significant relationship to employee turnover (Schlesinger and Zornitsky, 1991; Testa, 2001). Employees who are satisfied with their jobs are considered stable with their organizations (Hartman and Yrle, 1996). Growth in the interest of the quality of work has caused researchers to investigate various aspects of jobs and their contributions to improving productivity over a long period. Among these aspects, job satisfaction is considered the most often

researched organizational variable in the organizational behavior literature (Blau, 1999). Beck (1990) reported that all aspects of job satisfaction, including various theories, measures, and definitions, as well as the motivational, emotional, and informational components, have been discussed in the management literature. An important link in the chain from the firm to repeat business is the link between satisfied employees and satisfied customers (Heskett, Sasser, and Schlesinger 1997). Job satisfaction showed to influence customers' perceptions of the quality of service (Rafaeli, 1989; Schneider and Bowen 1985). As the relationship between job attrition and job satisfaction is well established, the focus of present study will be to address the issue of job satisfaction. Value priorities, individualization and role scope and their relationship with job satisfaction will be major focus of present research.

Summary of Different Approaches to Research

The contribution of labour process theorists Fernie and Metcalf (1998) focused on the management control, wage payment, and continuities with past practices in the new work place. Frenkel *et al.*, (1998) argued that bureaucratic system of management must be modified in workflow that are relating to information provided to service industry with info-normative control.

Taylor and Bain (1999) focused on the employees control over tasks and management control. Employees do not control the pace of work and work content but by automated computer systems and all the activities of employee is captured visually and monitored by managers leading to taylorism of work. Kinnie *et al.*, (2000a) emphasized the role of manufactured sociability by management. Wallace, Eagleson, and Waldersee (2000) focused on the customer-employee interaction for suggesting sacrificial human resources strategy. These studies indicate that there is agreement with respect to problems or issues of BPO industry but there is less agreement as far as solutions are concerned. Present studies assume stability and continuity of economy, society, its institutions, and values of people and their relation to social institutions. Information and communication technology influenced all dimensions of society by its intensity and pervasiveness changed the social institutions such as education (life long education), employment (entering employment and leaving due to voluntary and involuntary conditions such as economic depression), migration, and entering a relationship. These trends are further accelerated by globalization and giving rise to questioning of present assumptions with respect to people, economic, social institutions. Present occupational structure of BPO industry is an outcome of technological intensity. An approach that gives prime

importance to technology is likely to provide better insights into issues. The work of Castells (1996) on technology and its effect of social institutions influenced much of the present research. This includes economic interdependencies among nations as well as globalization and social movements and relations to individual identity. The network economy means “*availability of information and the way individuals work, produce, and consume information.*” The human processes are changed by these technologies. Social forecasting is based on role of technology and its effects on society.

1.6 Need for the Study

Based on research findings, the researcher concur that; the relationship of employer and employee has become blurred; the economy has taken shape of networks and the BPO industry with higher qualified employees with change in personal values . The quality of jobs is perceived to be low and high job attrition rates with health issues continue to afflict the industry despite human resources interventions. Experts mostly based on western economic conditions provided solutions, which may not be suitable to Indian conditions. Thus to facilitate dealing with diverse issues spanning different domains, it is felt that the present approach may not be suitable and there is a need for alternative approach.

Present approach to solve human resources issues is based on reductionist approach; on the assumption that the society, its composition, and forces that provide trajectory to the society remain constant. Assumption of constancy of societal relationships is not in tune with reality. The composition of society is unique to each country and as generally observed; technology changes the nature of relations, occupational structure, polity, and values. Social forecasting considers technology as an axial principle to examine society. An axial principle is an overriding principle that helps us to achieve a vantage point so that other dimensions of society can be examined and in the process find solutions. This is prime reason for considering social forecasting as a tool to analyze and provide solutions to BPO industry challenges. The approach should be robust and uncomplicated to be understood and implemented easily by managers and offer good explanation in addition to prediction of phenomena.

1.7 The Problem

Business process outsourcing industry is facing challenges in the domain of human resources issues with respect to high rates of attrition, disillusionment, health problems relating to stress, erratic life-style changes, and social problems.

Present human resource interventions have limited success while addressing these issues. The research conducted in other parts of the world may not be applicable totally as social conditions in which employee perform tasks are different in India. Work as a necessity to serve a higher purpose is replaced by the view that work is a means of being autonomous, creative, enabling the individual to express oneself giving rise to phenomenon of individualization of work. Empirical data is not available regarding value priorities of employees that are having an impact on the perception towards task environment of organization, and job satisfaction.

The human resources issues lead to following questions,

- (1) If employee tasks are highly structured then what is the role of an employee?
- (2) Is there a fundamental change in the perception of employees with respect to task environment and work due to information intensity and networking of economy at a global scale?
- (3) The problems are because; organizations cannot cope with the work place diversity or homogeneity of work place?

- (4) What are the value priorities of BPO employees, which are likely to influence performance of job?
- (5) In the prevailing environment of high stressful conditions and higher performance demands on employees by organizations, why there is no collective action in the form of trade unions by employees?
- (6) What is the role of Indian state with respect to working conditions in BPO sector?
- (7) Is it possible to answer these questions from traditional human resource perspective or there is a need for different approach?

The present research attempts to address these questions. To answer these questions and find appropriate solutions to BPO industry issues, Social Forecasting as a tool is examined with required elaboration.

1.8 Social Forecasting

Introduction

Bertrand de Jouvenel (1967), the French philosopher-economist defined social forecasting as the prediction of *big, slow changes in society*. This definition indicates that the entity in question is nothing less than whole society.

Social forecasting is thus concerned with the sweeping and ineluctable features of socio cultural change. It describes the larger context within which volition may be exerted and alternatives effected, if desired. For de Jouvenel, there is no single tomorrow—the future consists of fan like array of possibilities, alternative futures that man can shape. The term is not a recent addition to business vocabulary. The use of social forecasting stems from recognition that social pressures are becoming an increasing determinant for the success of any organization (James, 1978). The various indicators indicate that the society will be experiencing a total change in next few years (Morris, 1975). Some of these changes must be anticipated and incorporated in any long-range plans. The changes that are happening in the environment are fundamental. They are not evolutionary. The greatest challenge is the discontinuities that are happening in the environment (Jain and Singhvi, 1977). Examination of history indicates that there are a series of significant shifts in the conditions of human society- the renaissance, the agricultural revolution, and the industrial Revolution. Human society is entering a period of rapid change that is more dramatic in its consequences compared to earlier revolutions (Bell, 1973). Globalization, network economy, and democratization of polity lead modern societies to transform themselves at more accelerated cadences.

The inevitability of internet and convergence of technologies is not only due to revolution in microelectronics, but also due to exhaustion of material resources essential for maintaining industrial economy. Similarly, what kind of explanation is provided for investment in social networking websites such as ORKUT, FACEBOOK, and phenomenon of Wikipedia? Is it because of individualism promoted by Information Technology? The purpose of social forecasting is to provide an analytical framework for helping the corporate decision-maker to make his or her own judgment based on analysis.

Social forecasting provides better understanding of the forces shaping the environment and provides confidence to manager that his decisions reflect assessment of these issues. Social forecasting includes all those other factors that are not currently considered by economic or technological forecasting. Primarily it involves individual as customer, supplier, manager, or employee. It concerns people in-groups both inside as well as outside organizations. It further unfolds to government, society in general and to transnational organizations such as World Trade Organization. Therefore, Social Forecasting is a term, which includes political, legal, and ecological factors in addition to social.

Social Forecasting in the Context of Business

Social forecasting is to enlarge the scope of traditional business forecasting to include relevant domain of social-psychological-economic-political-ecological-technological environment. Through social forecasting, the inclusion of socio-political-ecological dimensions in strategic planning and policy formulation brings social issues into the mainstream of an organization's operations. By providing an open-system perspective of the organization, social forecasting helps relate social responsiveness to organizational efficiency by providing a longer time horizon of social issues relevant to the organization. Social forecasting thus, encourages the organization to perceive itself in mutual interaction with its external environment, enables management's application of appropriate period for the effective planning, analyzing, and implementing of its social involvement in a complex and dynamic environment. Social forecasting is defined as *“a systematic process for identifying social trends and their underlying attitudes, analyzing these social changes for their relevance to the organization, and integrating these findings with other forecasts.”*

Figure 1.1 Representation of Social forecasting definition

Social Forecasting relationship with economic forecasting and technological forecasting

Economic forecasting is concerned with modeling how people behave using utility criteria as a means for maximizing welfare. It is dependent on certain assumptions of people behavior. If the behavior changes the forecast is likely to change. Therefore, one role of social forecast is to find the underlying relationships used by economic forecasters and to modify them, as necessary.

In the case of technological forecasts, it has been assumed that past data can be extrapolated into future. However, observations indicate that past relationships are unable to predict future. In the case of pharmaceutical organizations, the new molecule development is more dependent on the R & D expenditure allocated. The advances cannot be attributable to serendipity. In fact, they result from managerial investment decisions (James, 1978). In case of pharmaceutical industry, these resources have been raising due to society's growing concern for health. The liberalization of health insurance in India combined with accepting patent regime, has totally changed the role of Indian pharmaceutical organizations.

The example of Pharma industry in India illustrates the complexity consisting of technological, economic potential, economic support based on legislation, governmental action, and globalization of business.

1. Economists and technologists developed the forecasting techniques. It is dissatisfaction with the methods and tools have led to development of social forecasting.
2. Active involvement of sociologists and business organizations are needed to further the objectives of social forecasting.

3. these are no clearly defined measures compared to technological and economic forecasting. Though objectivity is desired, subjectively is inevitable.
4. The forecasts cannot be 'ends,' they are only 'means' through which better view can be obtained about future.

Elements of Social Forecasting

Forecasting aids understanding of the factors shaping future, their interaction, and their consequences. For this, the elements of social forecasting are explained.

1. *Identification of important phenomenon* – This answers the question, what to forecast. It is not obvious to discern the possible future events that could be significant for organizations. In the case of social forecasting, it is likely to be more difficult. Views about society in which people are living, the way it has developed and its likely path in future is affected by personal experience and individual values. It is likely that forecaster may overlook changes in attitudes that are not familiar to him. Though objectivity is attempted, it may not be achievable. Individual personal judgment is involved in the selection of the data to be used in the forecast and his interpretation of results.

The importance of first stage in the forecasting process cannot be overstressed. It calls for sensitivity to evolving influences and judgment.

2. *Selection of phenomena for deeper study* – A comprehensive scanning of the environment consisting of demographic, economic, technical, social, legal, political, and psychological environment leads to large number of trends and possible future events, which might be considered within the forecasting exercise. The social forecaster would like to introduce, as much variables as possible to make forecast more accurate. However, in practice it is better to have appropriate factors that are likely to affect the final forecast.
3. *A system of measurement* – The phenomena in which the social forecaster is interested can be categorized as *events or trends*. The word *event* is used to describe something, which either does or does not happen. Even in the case of happening of the events, it occurs over a short interval of time. Demolition of Berlin wall and disintegration of socialistic countries is an event. The occurrence may be foreseen with some probability rather than forecast the dates at which that would happen.

Therefore, the probability of occurring at any point of time may be less but a cumulative probability is likely to increase. On the other hand, the *trend* evolves with time. Majority of the social forecaster's work falls into this category. For example, the size of high-income group varies in magnitude with time. To make a forecast there is a need of parameter to measure the phenomena. Such parameter is obtained from economic, technological, demographic, or ecological data. Many a time the phenomena of interest for social forecaster are not directly measurable. In the case of alienation of the work force, this phenomenon can be understood but the direct measurement is difficult. In this case, social forecaster seeks some surrogate measures as indicators of alienation of the work force. The number of days lost through strikes or number of days lost due to absenteeism may be considered as surrogate measure. Regarding measurement, social forecasting is more complex than economic and technological forecast. The social trend may have been changing in regular pattern for a number of years within a particular political and legal framework.

4. *A time-scale* – The association of an event or attainment of a quantified level for a trend, labeled as critical mass or tipping point, with a time scale, is an essential feature of forecast. A time scale is necessary for taking decisions based on informed

view of future. In recent years, much of the data has been published with respect to impact of microelectronics on society. This has little value to businesspersons who needs to know *when* and *at what rate* the changes will become significant. The establishment of need does not mean that it can be satisfied. Isolated events could happen at any time. Unless events and trends are related to time-scale, the decision-making is likely to make business sense. In this respect, social forecasting is different from science fiction.

5. *A probabilistic assessment* – Decision making under uncertainty is one of the major limitations of social forecaster. The probability will vary with the forecaster confidence in selection of indicators.

Meadows (1972a, 1972b, 1972c) in his seminal study has delineated the need for social forecasting and described its ideal features. Information on social phenomena is not precise as in the case of technological and economic data. In social forecasting both the phenomena has to be included for study. Social changes come through the interaction of demographic, economic, technical, cultural, ecological, and other factors. When elements are ignored in one or more of these areas, the fundamental cause of the problem may be lost. Instead, the social data is to be incorporated whatever be the form of precision.

Neutral vocabulary should be used so that professionals from many different fields cooperate directly in pooling their knowledge to study social systems.

Forecasting Social Trends

The use of the word *trend* implies social phenomena evolving over a period. If it is called as a trend then pattern can be evolved of this evolution and future is extrapolation of past. However, this pattern may take variety of forms. In the case of technological and some technoeconomic relationship, “S” shaped growth curve is exhibited. The main feature is slow initial growth followed by period of rapid growth and reaches a plateau as physical limit is approached. This process is irreversible. The ability of the computer chip to shrink in its size is limited by its atomic structure. On the other hand, economic forecasting is based upon cyclical pattern superimposed upon a trend line, which may slope upwards or may be downwards a long-term cycle. It is assumed that the pattern established in the past is likely to repeat in future and therefore economic movement is reversible. In forecasting both technology and economic attributes, the possibility of *discontinuities* is not considered.

Social forecasting takes the occurrence of *discontinuity* as one of the most important factors. Social forecasting must deal with two groups of factors:

1. *Exogenous factors* – These factors affect the business. However, no control can be exercised by the business on these factors. They are labeled as the *environment*.
2. *Endogenous factors*- They are defined as resources of the organization and managers have control over them. In business, there is a need to expect the changes in exogenous factors and respond with endogenous factors i.e., resources.

The above discussion gave rise to three forecast outputs that business requires from the environment:-

1. Changes that are likely to happen in the market potential;
2. Changes that are likely to happen in the various relative price, cost parameters;
3. Changes that is likely to happen in those factors that could influence or affect efficiency.

To estimate the factors there is a need to have “synoptic model,” in which all the assumptions are dynamic.

The synoptic model consists of six separate models all interconnected with each other such that output of one becomes input of others and cause these models to react within themselves. The six models are economic model, demographic model, technological model, psychological model, sociological model, and political model. The economic and demographic models are to a certain extent independent when compared to other models. All other models increase either rate of change or decrease rate of change in the economic model. They are also likely to affect the time lapse in economic model. They also provide barriers to economic forecast or determine the maximum above which the economic model cannot operate. They should be analyzed in terms of their inter relationship to obtain a better view of the environment.

This is an essential prerequisite for organizational effective planning. Organizations must first assess the changes in the environment, then decide its objectives and goals to, and control the endogenous factors (resources) to achieve mission and vision of the organization efficiently.

Effectiveness of social forecasting in different contexts

In this section, the methodology of social forecasting using survey research with success in different countries in different times will be examined.

Schwartz (1967) studied survey findings over a period of years from 1942 to 1965 and gave projections regarding social phenomenon. The attitudes studied are those held by American whites over Black people; eleven questions were identified and repeatedly asked over the period of studies, and trends in subgroups of population as well as population were studied. The attitudinal change is expressed as in terms of percentage of the population. She found that favorability towards Black people has been steadily increasing since the Second World War, rather than showing any major fluctuations in response to the social turmoil in the US. The same questions replicated in different studies and demonstrated the trend towards acceptance of Black people as equals. They suggest longitudinal studies may be retained with direction and pace, with some empirical evidence may lead to better social forecasts. Schwartz's (1967) work demonstrated that some of the trends might be explained by the displacement of ageing individuals and increasing levels of education. In each period studied by her, young and educated people tend to show less

racial prejudice. These findings suggested that the trends in racial attitudes would come down with increasing chances for contacts between races as equals, which result from liberalizing policy decisions and which serve to break down racial stereotypes. Inkeles (1960, 1969) study concerned with the psychological effects of socio-economic development.

Inkeles engaged research in six developing countries, reporting on wide spectrum of attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors as associated with modernity. The importance of these attitudes was interest in community involvement, greater occupational and educational aspirations for oneself and one's children and less passivity, fatalism, and prejudice against new ways of doing. There was consistency in results from different countries and he expected psychological convergence, between different nationalities as a condition of education, urbanism and industry become more wide spread. Feldman and Hurn (1966) confirmed the results.

Model Procedure for Social Forecasting

Paris Arnopoulos (1979) discussed model procedure for social forecasting. Generally forecasting ranges from predicting astronomical events (which are predicted with utmost precision) to human behavior (which is highly unpredictable). For this purpose if human behavior is defined to lie between a range along a hypothetical continuum between

randomness and determinism, in this way, some pattern of human activities and some reason to social events can be predicted by way of social forecasting. In this limited area of determinacy, there are various degrees of predictability. There are certain activities, which have high predictability; there is possibility of attaching probability of their occurrence. The relative degree of predictability of different types of events may now be summarized in the following continuum.

The schema suggested comprises of social events coupled with volitional behavior at the centre of the chaos-order continuum. This centralization focuses attention on social events and its relation to incidental and structural events. Since most of the human activities fall into three middle categories of activities, social forecasting will have, “incident-possibilistic, social-volitional, and structure-probabilistic” events. The first type of event ‘incidental’ is nearest to the random end of the range and is least predictable. These incidents are revolutions, innovation breakthroughs and other dramatic events. The structural and mechanical have high probability of projection. Technological forecasting

falls into this category. Between these two types of events, social forecasting finds its place. Collective behavior is not as predictable as structured patterns of technology; however, they are predictable with probability. Social forecasting uses social-science hypotheses, historical analogies, and purposive activities, thus forecasting can be done with caution, as these tools are not as precise as mathematical outcomes. The events depend much on human volition and on external constraints, thus prediction can only be conditional and provisional. Social forecasts of this kind combine both subjective and objective considerations.

Validation Process of Social Forecasting Model and Applications

The other most important dimension is validation process of forecasting model. This may be given in the form of a linear construct. This arrow line given here represents various points along the continuum. Traveling along the path is likely to reduce the subjectivity and increase objectivity. This validates the forecasts and not the out come of the forecast.

The first need is to assume explicitly the basic premises on which the forecast is build. They are like the mathematical postulates and elementary definitions. It must be supplemented with assumptions that are made with respect to the forecast.

The next part concerns the source of evidence that constitute forecasting. The empirical evidence concerns only past and present, the future predictions can be based on projections and inferences. There is a need to accumulate certain amount of data with respect to different variables that concern an organization or nation that is stored, analyzed, and recalled for appropriate forecasting. Thus, an appropriate criterion must be developed and methodology is to be developed to have forecasts that will help organizations (Prabhakar, 2007).

Social forecasting Applications in business organizations

Newgren (1976, 1977), Carroll, Newgren, and provided research on social forecasting practices of seventy-eight organizations belonging to different Industrial firms in United States of America.

The research results are 42.6 % of the organizations have institutionalized social forecasting procedures. Similarly, the organizations are making use of social forecasting to fulfill social responsibility function. Becker (2001) suggests one of the major sub-fields of impact assessment is social forecasting. According to Becker, Social Impact Assessment is the process of identifying the future consequences of current or proposed actions, which are related to individuals, organizations, and social macro-systems.

Social forecasting is one of the tools that can be used for the purpose of social impact assessment. Mitton and Willmott (2005) produced a 30-year forecast in 1971, of leisure in the United Kingdom. In 2001, they obtained survey data for comparison with the forecasts. The actual and observed behavior indicate that the forecasts are near to the estimates after thirty years of lapse. These studies indicate that with appropriate methodology social forecasting will provide effective solutions.

1.9 Social Forecasting for BPO Industry

For building social forecasting for business process outsourcing industry the following procedure is adopted.

Basic Assumptions

- 1) There will be no fundamental changes in the global economic sphere with respect to globalization and liberalization.
- 2) There will be no far-reaching changes in the eco-policies of the countries to produce short-term changes in the corporate structures.
- 3) The energy dependence on the fossil fuels remain same, as alternative energy systems or nuclear energy are not likely to take effect with in five years in global sphere as well as in India.
- 4) There will be continued social and political stability in India for the next five years.

Method Used for Social Forecasting

Value profiling is used as a method for social forecasting. Extrapolation has been used for studying economic and technological forecasting.

Time Frame

The period selected for the forecast is five years from 2009-2014. This period consists of two most important phase of global economic downturn and recovery after the downturn.

Identification of important phenomena

The important phenomenon to be studied is;

- 1) Economic outlook globally as well as India for the years 2008-09, 2009-10. This is primarily needed as the global economy is in a down turn for major developed economies and in recession. BPO industry is dependent, on these economies. The present Indian economic outlook also needs to be forecasted as it is globalized to a large extent.(source: Reserve Bank of India)
- 2) Demographic outlook for the next ten years is to be examined, as it is likely to affect the policy decisions of the state and considering the long lag period for demographic variables.
- 3) Political outlook for global as well as India is explored for next five years.
- 4) Technological model for a period of five years is considered.

Selection of phenomena for deeper study

The sociological and psychological aspects will be considered for deeper study. The sociological variables and their effect on conditions of employment will be assessed. Different variables such as value priorities, role scope, individualization of work, and job satisfaction are studied for

further recommendation. A typology for BPO organization will be designed based on the inputs from research.

1.9.1 Economic Forecasting

Global economic downturn

The BPO industry depends on clients in US, UK, and Europe. Therefore, a good understanding of global economic scenario is necessary.

For this purpose, research by Rajiv *et al.*, (2009) is adopted. The financial crisis in global economic scenario can be traced to US.

The financial crisis in the US has spread to Europe and Japan and it is likely to see most developed economies suffering prolonged period of recession that could extend beyond 2010. The First Global Financial Crisis of the 21st Century, PART II, 2008. ([http:// www.voxeu.org](http://www.voxeu.org)) indicate that the crisis is due to excessive leveraging by investment and commercial banks, under pricing risk and lack of proper regulatory system. This crisis is yet to reach the bottom of recessionary slide. According to IMF (2008a, 2008b, 2009) estimates, the sub-prime loans increased up to US \$ 2.2 trillion. The US Government and Federal Reserve have provided rescue programs to the tune of US \$ 7.5 trillion (Barth, 2008).

Source: IMF World Economic Outlook Update, January 2009.

Figure 1.2 World GDP Growth rates

SOURCE: IMF- World Economic Outlook Update, January 2009.

The world output is likely to grow only by .5% compared to 3.4% in 2008 and 5.2% in 2007. However, International Monetary Fund's latest estimates indicate that there will be contraction of 3% in world economic output. During January 2009, the exports fell in Japan by 46.3%, Germany by 20.7% and China by 17.5% and India by 15.9%.

Fig 1.3 Global Trade, 1981-2008.

The latest forecast by Nouriel Roubini, the New York University Professor who warned about the crisis before others indicated that Indian business should reckon with another two years of weak global economic activity or further contraction of world trade. (Nouriel Roubini's speech at India Today Conclave in New Delhi on 6 March 2009 can be accessed at www.rgemonitor.com).

Growth Prospects for India (2008-2010)

For forecasting Gross domestic product growth in India, different models are used. They include simple methods such as Bridge model, mathematically sophisticated model such as Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium Model and Leading Indicators Method. However, in the opinion of the researcher and other researchers in econometrics, leading indicators method was found to be easy to use and favored by policy makers. Leading economic indicators are variables that are considered to have significant influence on future level of economic activity in India and give advanced signals about the future growth rate of GDP. They are used to identify inflexion points in the business cycles, which can be done with some accuracy, as the change in the direction of the principle leading indicators, would result in a similar directional change in the overall economic activity. Given its ability to predict GDP growth with high precision in India, the researcher suggests

use of same method for forecasting. For constructing leading indicators index, the following nine indicators have been selected.

- 1) Production of machinery and equipment.
- 2) Non food credit.
- 3) Railway freight traffic.
- 4) Cement Sales.
- 5) Net sales of corporate sector.
- 6) Fuel and metal prices.
- 7) Real rate of interest.
- 8) BSE Sensex.
- 9) Exports growth.

A composite index for Leading Economic Indicators has been constructed for 1997-2008. The Leading Economic Indicator Index, with a five quarter lag and the shock represented by a dummy variable (equal to 1 with shock and zero with no shock) are used to forecast India's GDP growth.

Source: Central Statistical Organization.

Figure 1.4 Projection of GDP Growth rate

Table 1.4 GDP Forecast 2008-2009 and 2009-2010

Year	No Shock	With Shock*	Shock Moderated
2008-2009	7.9	6.3	6.3**
2009-2010	8.4	4.8	5.5

* Shock is represented by Global Financial Crisis.

**The effect of moderation of policy in the year 2009 will take effect only in 2010.

Adopted from Kumar, Rajiv et al. (2009). Indian Economic Outlook 2008-09 and

2009-10, Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations. p. 25.

Therefore, the pessimistic growth rate is 4.8% and optimistic growth rate is 5.5% scenario after the crisis (2011-2014). There is likely to be macro economic stability, with modest growth in the world economic trade.

Furthermore, by the year 2015, an estimated 3.3 million US jobs would have moved offshore, a 3000% increase from the year 2000. This is the indication of BPO industry potential in United States of America.

Table 1.5 Number of United States of America Jobs Moving Offshore

Sl.No	Job Category	2000	2005	2010	2015
1	Management	0	37,477	117,835	88,281
2	Business	10,787	61,252	161,722	48,028
3	Computer	27,171	108,991	276,954	72,632
4	Architecture	3,498	32,302	83,237	84,347
5	Life Sciences	0	3,677	14,478	36,770
6	Legal	1,793	14,220	34,673	74,642
7	Art, Design	818	5,576	13,846	29,639
8	Sales	4,619	29,064	97,321	26,564
9	Office	53,987	295,034	791,034	1,659,310
	Total	102,674	587,592	1,591,101	3,320,213

SOURCE: United States of America Department of Labour and Forrester Research, Inc. (2008)

Economic Forecast and BPO Industry

The forecasts for the next two years, when the global down turn is likely to stabilize may be ventured with caution. The global trade is not likely to reach the 2007 levels by 2010.

The global cost cutting may continue. However, the recession may not prompt the global organizations to stop contracts already given; the political environment globally may not allow further extraordinary growth. As the margins will be under pressure and deflationary pressure on the Indian economy, the high rates of salary growth (14.8% in the year 2008) may not be possible for the years 2009- 2010. Therefore, recruitment may not be to the levels of 2007 and 2008 as expected by many industry experts during 2009- 2010. (www.bpoindia.org).

However, as global consolidation is likely to take place with respect to different verticals in Knowledge Process Outsourcing, and geographical expansion of buyers from UK, Europe and Asia preferring India as a destination and growth is likely to come from expansion. Therefore need for knowledge intensity of work force during the forecasted period will be higher.

1.9.2 Demographic forecasting

Three most important demographic trends are evident globally. First, fertility rates are dropping in all geographies. Second, life expectancy is rising in many parts of the world. Third, developed countries are having these two trends compared to developing countries and reflected in their declining share in world population according to Asher and Nandy (2007). Global demographic estimates by the United Nations (<http://esa.un.org/unpp>) suggest the following forecasts.

Decline in fertility rate

Global fertility rate at the world level is at 2.65 children per women. This is half of five children per women during 1950-1955. The global fertility is projected to drop to 2.05 children per women by 2045-2050.

Increase in life expectancy

Global life expectancy was estimated to be 46 years in 1950-1955 periods. The present estimates are 65 years for 2000-2005. In developed countries current level is at 75 years and likely to increase to 82 years by mid century.

Rise in the median age

Median age is an indication of aging population. The median age in the developed countries has reached forty; Japan, Germany, and France are on the higher side of the median. Therefore, employee scalability in these countries will be difficult and provides an opportunity to India.

Ageing population

The combined effect of fertility decline and increase in life expectancy is ageing population; the share of the older persons increase compared to that of the younger persons. Globally the present levels of 672 million in 2005 are likely to increase to 1.9 billion in 2050. The size of elderly population in developed countries has already surpassed that of the 12-24 age groups. However, according to (Bloom and Canning, 2006) such kind of problem will happen only in 2045 for India and China.

Share of labour force to the total population

Share of working population to total population is likely to decline between 2005 to 2050 except for India and Philippines. The largest decline is likely to occur in Japan, Korea, Italy, and France. By 2020, 50% of the population in these countries will be more than 65 years. The study indicates that there will be one retired person for every working person.

India will be one of the countries that will have rising working age population. According to Khurana (2005) the median age of India's population is 24.3 years. At present 550 million or fifty% of the total population is below 25 years. The overview indicates that the percentage of non-working older persons increase, the working group within 14-24 will decrease. The only solution for such aging economies is to increase the number of immigrants or export work to remain competitive in the market. This inference makes outsourcing and offshoring a logical business strategy for all developed countries. The demographic dividend or gift demographic opportunity is available to India. At present more than 50% of the Fortune 500 companies offshore to India according to NASSCOM, Strategic Review, 2006. Consistently Gartner, AT Kearney, McKinsey Global Institute and Forrester in various surveys ranked India as the preferred destination.

Demographic Forecast for BPO industry

The demographic dividend will not confer automatic advantage to India. With appropriate educational policies, the 14-24 age group population can be effectively converted to economically prosperous group. A keen observation of census figures of India (www.censusindia.net) indicates that not the all India averages capture the variabilities within states.

There are wide interstate differences in the fertility rates. The northern India will stay young over next two decades, and south will face rapid individual and population ageing. The southern states of Tamilnadu, Kerala, and Andhra Pradesh have already reached the replacement fertility rate. The median age in different states, also exhibit a wide range of differences-from 20 years in states such as Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, and Rajasthan to high around twenty-eight in states such as Kerala and Tamilnadu. However, most of the BPO organizations are in Tamilnadu, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, and Gurgon. Though the internal mobility is moderate to high, it will be most important for state to diversify the industries to Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and Madhya Pradesh for equitable development for the country. This will have better impact on the overall development of the country. The per capita educational institutions in Northern India are comparatively lower to that of Southern India and this need to be corrected.

1.9.3 Technological Forecasting

For technological forecasting for BPO industry, the phenomenon of long waves theory is examined. The purpose is to find; will there be more innovations in the next five years? Alternatively, have a plateau is reached with respect to advances in innovations in computers? How the growth is likely to come; is it from new research in different areas or

from the consolidation of existing business? An attempt is made to find answers. Economists analyze the business cycles that happened during different times for the past three centuries. However, Kondratieff curves, known as long wave phenomenon, gives one of the most important theories. The Kondratieff phenomenon will be discussed with respect to technological forecasting rather than with economic forecasting as the evidence proved that it deals with more physical phenomenon than economic phenomenon (Marchetti, 1988). In the introduction, the basic dimensions of K-wave theory are examined followed by discussion on its validation.

Finally, K-wave theory is used to discern the changes in technological environment. To study extensive references is obtained from Devezas, Linstone and Santos (2005).

Kondratieff Curves – Introduction

The Russian economist Nikolai Kondratieff was the first to bring observations about long waves also called super cycles, surges, long waves, or K-waves-are described as regular cycles in a capitalist world economy. These cycles consist of alternating periods between high growth and periods of negative growth. The cycle is more relevant to world economy rather than individual national economies. It affects all the sectors of an economy, and concerns output rather than prices

(although Kondratieff had made observations focusing more on prices, inflation, and interest rates). According to Kondratieff, the ascendant phase is characterized by an increase in prices and low interest rates, while the other phase consists of a decrease in prices and high interest rates.

Kondratieff proposed to apply the theory to the 19th century:

- 1790 – 1849 with a turning point in 1815.
- 1850 – 1896 with a turning point in 1873.
- Kondratieff supposed that in 1896, a new cycle had started.

The phases of Kondratieff's waves also carry with them *social shifts and changes in the public mood*. The first stage of expansion and growth, the *spring* stage, encompasses a social shift in which the wealth, accumulation, and innovation that are present in this first period of the cycle create upheavals and displacements in society. The economic changes result in redefining work and the role of participants in society. In the next phase, the *summer* stagflation, there is a mood of affluence from the previous growth stage that changes the *attitude towards work* in society, creating inefficiencies. The next stage is season of deflationary growth, or the plateau period. The popular mood changes during this period. It shifts toward stability, normalcy, and isolationism after the

policies and economics during unpopular excesses of war. Finally, the *winter* stage, which of severe depression, includes the integration of previous social shifts, and changes into the social fabric of society, supported by the shifts in innovation and technology.

There are four schools of thought and one of the most important schools of thought is innovation school propounded by Joseph Schumpeter. He suggested that these waves arise from the bunching of basic innovations that launch technological revolutions that in turn create leading industrial or commercial sectors. The theory hypothesized the existence of very long-run macroeconomic and price cycles, originally estimated to last 50–54 years.

Social Phenomenon of Kondratieff Curves

The curves are described to be economic waves. However, the explanation offered by Kondratieff, includes social shifts and public mood. Similarly, it also changes the attitude towards work. Further study is undertaken to find valid explanations for K-wave phenomenon.

Validity of K-wave phenomenon

Economists and economic historians have divided opinion regarding long wave phenomenon. Two areas are for continued debate. First, on the facts, are long waves a real phenomenon? If it is true, what is

the nature of long wave movement? The reason for economists not accepting long wave phenomenon is that econometric research from 1980's onwards does not give total support to the long wave phenomenon (Metz, 2005).

Regarding empirical evidence Marchetti (<http://cesaremarchetti.org>) in several publications have proved that the real evidence of long waves is not in time series data of economic parameters, but in the observation of physical entities associated economic domain, such as innovations, energy consumption, infrastructure etc. Berry (1991, 2000) using chaos theory and spectral analysis has found sound and robust evidence of the existence of K-waves. Moreover, Berry has observed that K-waves are not growth cycles, but instead structural cycles. That explained the regularity for every 55 years found by Marchetti (1988) in his extensive analysis of physical parameters. This explanation will answer the first question that it is a real phenomenon. The second question is the essence of discussion on long waves: their nature in relation to structural cycles and clusters of innovations. Metz (2005) found evidence of clusters of innovation activity. He used database of (15,000 innovations from the period of 1750 to 1991 collected by researchers of the Institute of Employment Research in Nuremberg) and found evidence for clusters having a peak at 1840,

1890, 1935, and 1986. His research shows that innovation activity followed by an upswing in growth of economic activity with a lag of about 18 years. These studies provide support for Generational-Learning Model that will help understanding the phenomenon better. Among theories that explained K-waves, the plausible evidence is from cluster of radical innovations that peak during the ‘downswing,’ phases of each K-wave. This cluster of innovations originates a completely new technological new environment, which is called Technosphere according to Devezas and Corredine (2001). The 50-60 year K-waves are usually measured from trough to trough, for the purpose of study, the cycles are calculated from peak to peak. Thus, Technosphere commences with a downswing of the K-wave, the period of knowledge innovation or Schumpeter’s “creative destruction,” and proceeds through the trough to the knowledge consolidation in the K-wave upswing culminating at its peak.

Figure 1.5. The Generational Learning Model of Long Waves. The overall growth curve of a new technoeconomic system (technosphere) encompasses two successive logistic structural cycles: an innovation structural cycle with characteristic duration t_i triggered during the “disintensity down slope” of the previous technosphere, and a consolidating structural cycle, with characteristic duration t_c , which marks the definitive entrenching of the new technosphere and the vigorous “intensity up slope” of the long wave.

SOURCE: Adopted from Devezas T.C, Linstone H.A, and Santos H.J.S. (2005). *The Growth Dynamics of the Internet and Long Wave Theory, Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 72, p. 916.

Each such period from peak to peak has associated with it, an overarching technology that has a dominant impact. The mechanization of textile industry galvanized the first K-wave upswing before 1800. Steam powered transportation was the dominant technology of the period encompassing the subsequent first wave down swing and second K-wave

upswing (about 1800-1856). Steel and electricity are important in the second downswing and third upswing (about 1856-1916), while oil was important technology in the era of the third downswing and fourth upswing (about 1916-1969). The overreaching technology is now, in the cycle of fourth down swing and fifth upswing (about 1969-2024). The cyclical patterns are given in the following table for reference.

Table 1.6 Cyclical Patterns of Innovation

Domain of Innovation	1 st to 2 nd wave 1800-1856	2 nd to 3 rd wave 1856-1916	3 rd to 4 th wave 1916-1970	4 th to 5 th wave 1970-2025
Overarching technology	Steam power	Steel/Electricity	Oil	Information Technology
Transportation	Rail roads	Automobiles	Air craft	Space craft
Communication	Periodicals	Telegraph, Telephone	Radio, TV	Internet, WWW
Primary Global Energy	Wood	Coal	Oil	Natural Gas, Nuclear
Manufacturing Process	Factory	Scientific Management assembly line	Mass production, in-house R&D	Minimal inventory, CAD
Corporate organization	Hierarchy	Division	Matrix	Network, Virtual company

SOURCE: Adopted from Devezas T.C, Linstone H.A, and Santos H.J.S. (2005). *The Growth Dynamics of the Internet and Long Wave Theory, Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 72, page 917.

It has been widely observed that the K-wave rhythm is observed not only in economic sphere, where Kondratieff focused his attention, but also in global reliance on energy, in disruptive innovations in communication, transportation modes, infrastructure, manufacturing,

business organization. However, these domains are related. Marchetti (1988) stated, “With increasing mechanical transport and speed, the personal territory increases, and so rises the opportunity to set up communication poles farther away. Movement generates communication (not vice-versa).”

The nature of this pattern made him to think that it is not an economic phenomenon, but an expression of deeper *physical* one relating to the basic working of the society: especially society as a learning system (Marchetti, 1980). The prime mover of any evolutionary process is the information transfer, which can be named as learning process. The rate of information transfer is initially low, then overcoming the inertia of system, grows, reaches a maximum rate of growth, slows down, and reaches a ceiling, following then a typical logistic growth pattern. In the evolutionary process, a system self-organizes and learns configuring and reconfiguring itself towards greater efficiency and with each successive iteration improves performance. Each stage corresponds to a given structure that corresponds previous self-organization, learning, and current limitations. Thus, it may be said that, “*self-organization and learning are embodied in the system’s structure, and the learning rate is an overall system property.*”

Technological Forecasting for BPO Industry

As it can be observed from the generational learning model (figure 1.5), 1970 is the starting point of dis-intensity down slope. In the beginning period there are swarm of innovations between 1983-1995, indicating the period in which swarming of innovations has taken place. 1995-2005 exhibited diffusion phase with synergism and disingenuity phase. Thus, the BPO industry, which depends on the information technology and communication, is at the phase of consolidation from 2000-2010. Thus, from now onwards the growth must happen due to new technological innovations or due to further consolidation of the present technologies. The cautious approach will be not to expect technological breakthrough in the next five years. Thus, the new business must come from consolidation of present business at a rapid rate and expand.

1. Manage multiple internal and external considerations such as increase footprint from thirty destinations in India and 25 destinations outside India. Any expansion must come from 2-tier and 3-tier cities. This gives raise to the infrastructural issues and social capital issues.
2. Overcome supply-side constraints such as talent and infrastructure especially in tier two and three places.

3. Combat emerging competition from other offshore destinations especially from Eastern Europe, Philippines, and China, who are offering considerable cost advantages and near shoring capabilities.
4. Sustain cost advantage and economic value proposition.
5. Scale their value propositions in line with evolving buyer expectations.

If all the parameters are met, the forecast for the next five years is that an average growth rate of 20% is expected to be achieved by the industry.

1.9.4 Political Forecasting

The global political environment is not likely to undergo many changes with stability being ensured by leadership of President Barack Obama at United States of America for the next five years. His initiatives with Middle Eastern countries and economic measures are likely to take effect in next two years.

Similarly, in India, Dr. Manmohan Singh leadership with less dependence on left front and other allies is likely to complete its term with the economic policies in tune with globalization. The Political Instability Index prepared by Economic Intelligence Unit provides an analysis combining economic factors and social factors. It shows the level

of threat posed to governments by social protest. The index scores are derived by combining measures of economic distress and underlying vulnerability to unrest. The index covers the period 2009/10, and scores are compared with results for 2007. The data given is for 165 countries and India occupies 135th rank. A high ranking indicates low political vulnerability.

Table 1.7 India's political and economic vulnerability ranking

Rank	Country	Underlying vulnerability	Economic distress	Indexed Score	2007 score
135*	India	5.0	4.0	4.5	4.5

SOURCE: Economic Intelligence Unit (2009)

The index is a confirmation regarding stability and continued economic growth for India from a political point of view. The risks also remain unchanged from 2007.

1.10 Justification of the Study

Human capital and social factors are the key factors that will propel any business organization to failure or success, specifically business process outsourcing industry. The occupations are filled by a new kind of workforce: They are from different educational backgrounds, well paid, and closely linked to global economy. Work in the case of business

process outsourcing industry is performed virtually, which is high technology intensive with planetary scale, giving rise to different work culture, value priorities, individualization of work, which in turn influences outcomes such as job satisfaction, expectation regarding compensation and interpersonal work environment. It is believed that the effective performance of roles is likely to increase motivational levels of employees. The role scope of the employees of BPO needs to be documented, as the task expectations are different from that of other industries. Value research and its empirical relationship with job satisfaction help to devise human resources initiatives. Social forecasting is the methodology adopted for study, which encompasses forecasting relating to economic, technological, demographic, political, in addition to value profiling, and social equity that will help policymaking by state.

1.11 Objectives of the Study

Social forecasting is used as a methodology, provide forecast for BPO industry for five years from 2009-2014. For this purpose, there is a need for identifying demographic, educational, and social background of business process outsourcing employees as Indian sociological work environment is different compared to that of other countries. Job satisfaction is identified as most important reason for

attrition and disillusionment of employees with the industry. The different factors that affect job satisfaction such as value priorities, role scope, and individualization of work are to be delineated and appropriate model is to be devised. Based on the research, researcher would suggest suitable recommendations to Indian state and BPO industry.

1.12 Significance of the Study

The study has the potential to contribute in different dimensions. Conceptually in the present study, social forecasting is used as an approach to provide solutions to both Indian state and BPO industry. The output of economic, demographic, technological and political forecasting are used to improve quality of explanation and prediction. Individualization of work, value priorities, and role scope are examined and relationship with job satisfaction is delineated. The model provided will help BPO organizations to address the issue of job attrition.

Chapter 2 Review of Literature

Chapter Overview

There are four purposes for the present chapter. The first is to provide contextual clarity and examine the research with respect to BPO organizations in the areas relating to job attrition and job satisfaction, and in the process, establishing gaps in the literature. The second purpose is to answer the need for social forecasting and initiation of social forecasting process. The third purpose is to consider conceptual model for research and the fourth purpose is to present typology of BPO organization. As suggested by researchers, social forecasting commence with the study of values. A detailed study of values is undertaken to clarify definitional issues. Values and its relation to attitude and behavior are reviewed. Role scope and need for its study is examined. The concept of individualization and its importance for study in the era of changes in life course and network economies is deliberated. A model for present research is discussed.

2.1 Research Context

The BPO industry has attracted much negative comments in the media worldwide and in India. Newspaper, radio, and television features have referred to BPO's as 'electronic sweatshops,' with the term such as

'battery hens' used to illustrate the intensive and stressful nature of being an employee of BPO industry. Such terminology has partly emerged from research papers by Garson (1988), Fernie and Metcalf (1998), Taylor and Bain (1999). Call centre jobs are considered low quality and heavily routinized forms of work. Batt and Moynihan (2002) state that production line call centres proliferate, whilst many manufacturing enterprises have moved away from this 'mass production model' (maximize volume and minimize costs) and have adopted more high involvement work practices (Huselid, 1995). All this is removed from the 'knowledge workers' predicted for the new millennium.

Research in BPO organizations may be bifurcated into two broad areas; research relating to call centres (as it is referred in western countries) and research in India. The western research (predominantly conducted in Australia, Europe, United Kingdom, Sweden and France) , relating to human resources, is concerned with labour process theory, effect of performance monitoring, emotional labour, well being, role of call centres as unit of society, the new way of organizational arrangement, new economic networks, gendered work places, occupational and ergonomic studies, relationship of capital and labour, cost savings, quality of jobs, sociolinguistics enriched by qualitative and quantitative studies. Research outside India started with path breaking

work of, Fernie and Metcalf ⁹, 1998. However, many researchers who studied western outsourcing phenomenon also studied Indian BPO industry (as it is referred in India).

The literature brings forth the striking contrast of labour markets in western countries characterised by lower levels of educational attainment, older age profiles and different perceptions of opportunity and aspiration compared to Indian labour market which is characterised by young work force, with higher educational attainment, ambitious with curiosity and interest in western working practices. Research in India focussed on dimensions such as desirability of BPO, employee's perception of work, cultural ramifications and provided valuable insights for present research. The growth of BPO industry generated fierce debates, back-lashes and gave rise to socio-economic-political issues.

At macro level, Friedman (2005) described that BPO experimentation provide both sourcing countries and destination countries with opportunities for prosperity, flexibility, security, and freedom. Mishra (2006) argued these arrangements as moving of work to low labour economies leading to greater inequalities. Dossani and Kenny (2003) argued that BPO provides career and life prospects to young people. Remesh (2004) did not agree with these propositions.

⁹ Ibid., p.11.

He described the workers as cyber coolies; insecure, vulnerable causalities of the new economic order. He argued that the precariousness of the new economy is related most fundamentally to the increasing instability of worker's sense of who they are. In his analysis he argued that they led double life- an authentic Indian day time life, and pretend western by night time while working. Remesh analysis ignored the aspects of western culture that have long historical roots and its deep embeddedness in contemporary Indian society. However, mentioning these studies is not to take a position and argue. These studies provide contextual clarity and starting point for study of BPO industry.

2.2 Research and Issues of BPO industry

First chapter addressed in brief the conceptual issues regarding problems of BPO industry and identified job satisfaction as a major area of concern. A wide range of job, organizational and environmental factors is identified to affect job satisfaction at work (Zapf *et al.*, 2003). Job satisfaction is a multidimensional concept and both instrumental and expressive rewards proved to cause enhancement of job satisfaction. However, there are organizational factors such as performance monitoring, personality variables such as conscientiousness and social support, which have found to have effect on job satisfaction.

Different research results in BPO organizations conducted are examined with a purpose of identifying variables that need to be studied for present research.

2.2.1 Emotional Exhaustion, Conscientiousness, and Role Clarity

Witt, Andrews, and Carlson (2004) studied emotional exhaustion and its relation with conscientiousness of customer service executives of call centres. They identified that emotional exhaustion¹⁰ is associated with conscientiousness¹¹. Emotional exhaustion is caused by role conflict or by role clarity; workload and work pressure and reduce job performance (Babakus *et al.*, 1999). High conscientiousness persons performed low compared to low conscientiousness persons when faced with high emotional exhaustion. The research outcome is important in the sense that emotional exhaustion that is dependent on role scope, role clarity and work pressure caused the lowering of job performance mediated by personality variable conscientiousness. This role clarity is one of the important dimensions that are likely to affect the performance.

A person's role in BPO organization is not comprehensible and, he or she must know it only through working in the organization.

¹⁰ Emotional exhaustion is feeling of lack of energy and feeling that one's emotional resources are used up.

¹¹ Conscientiousness is a personality variable associated with being thorough, efficient, organized, reliable and responsible.

This aspect is intuitively explainable as the industry is novel and no previous models of employment are available for prospective employees. *Role and role scope of BPO frontline employees are yet to be researched in India. This has been identified as a gap in present literature and taken up for study.*

2.2.2 Skill levels of Employees and Job Satisfaction

Rose (1994) studied relationship between skill levels and job satisfaction. If an employee has low skills and given a job that require high skills, he is likely to have positive job satisfaction. The following table provides information on skills and job satisfaction relationship.

Table 2.1 Types of Skill-Matching and Satisfaction Levels

Skill Situation of Subgroup	Satisfaction Level
Under-utilized	
Low job skill-moderate own skill	-27
Moderate job skill, high own skill	-15
Low job skill, high own skill	-10
Matched	
Low job skill, low own skill	+1
Moderate job skill, Moderate own skill	+5
High job skill, High own skill	+4
Under-qualified	
Moderate job-skill, low own skill	+12
High job skill, moderate own skill	+13
High job skill, low own skill	+33

(SOURCE: Rose, 1994)

Considering the Indian BPO sector high qualified employees are presumed to take up the jobs. The term high qualified is a relative term. The state government having a policy of liberal education, it is comparatively easy to obtain graduation unlike any other foreign country. The high qualified does not mean high skilled.

The situation may be propositioned as low job skill and low personal skill with higher qualification. Rose, 1984 has not studied this aspect. The higher qualification and relation with satisfaction has not been studied it has been considered as a gap and included for further research.

The strategy of organizations is reduced cost and increased customer satisfaction. They are mutually dependent aspects. Higher customer satisfaction can be achieved with higher leverage for employee to decide the strategy to meet the customer query. However, the cost considerations may not permit such an interaction and only prescribed scripts with defined call timings and embedded in ICT architecture is possible given the need for reduction in uncertainty and increased standardization. Thus giving rise to *requirement* of lower skills. However, this kind of classification of skills and in turn satisfaction may not reflect the way in which competencies are viewed by organizations. Beffa, Boyer, and Touffut (1999) present a typology of workers that are not based on traditional worker statuses such as blue collars and white collars but depend on the type of knowledge and abilities that they used on the job. The first category of workers is referred as “*stable polyvalence*;” they have important knowledge and abilities which are linked to a specific company.

A second group of workers are presented as “*professionals*”: their competencies can be transferred to other organizational situations. The last set is called “*market flexibility*”: their competencies are highly standardized and can be transferred easily. It may be propositioned that the BPO organization requirement of competencies ranges from usually market flexibility to professionals. There is a paradox to be addressed here.

While employees based their satisfaction on skill levels and jobs offered to them, organizations look at the competencies from different dimension.

2.2.3 Performance Monitoring Controls in BPO

One of the major areas of concern that lead researchers to call the BPO organizations as Panopticon and sweatshops are the different types of performance monitoring¹² and control mechanism. There is a need for clarifying the characteristics of performance monitoring. The characteristics are grouped into two broad areas, namely *content* and *purpose* (Cryon, 1993; Stanton, 2000). The “*content*” of performance monitoring concerns objective qualities of monitoring process.

¹² Performance monitoring is defined as those practices that involve the observation, examination, or recording of employee work related behaviors (or all of these) with or without technical assistance (Stanton, 2000).

It includes: *frequency*- which is either continuous or episodic; *feedback* - frequency of providing feedback – daily, weekly or fortnightly; *performance criteria*- qualitative, quantitative, referring to clarity; *source*- the person who collects the feedback; *target*- is it directed towards person, group or the organization.

The “*purpose*” of performance monitoring covers the uses to which the data collected is put. The data may be used for three purposes; punitive purpose; development purpose; monetary reward, or recognition purpose. In addition, research by Stanton and Barnes Farrel, (1996) and Stanton (2000) indicated third factor “*monitoring cognitions*”. This factor covers employee perceptions of monitoring and includes attitudes towards monitoring, assessments of its fairness, trust, and perceived intensity of monitoring (Chalykoff and Kochan, 1989).

Performance monitoring is supposed to enable organizations to improve employee performance, reduce costs, and ensure customer satisfaction. Employees are thought to benefit from it due to timely feedback, recognition, and assessment of performance fairly as all others performance is displayed. It is also assumed to improve their performance and develop new skills.

However, Smith *et al.*, (1992) argue that performance monitoring is intrinsically threatening to employees because the information gained may adversely affect the employee's remuneration or their relationship with co-workers. It is also considered to intensify employee's workload and to increase the level of work demands. However, academic debate goes on with respect to performance monitoring, BPO organizations use extensive electronically monitored and computer-mediated performance monitoring that is considered as totally objective. The contention of employee's dissatisfaction is regarding the performance appraisal is inability of employee to deviate and use his or her knowledge inputs to improve performance and comparison with other co-workers without focus on outcome of the call. As an extension of this discussion, following research papers are examined.

Rose and Wright (2005) studied different dimensions of control among call centre employees and found that higher focus on call monitoring and other electronic controls lead to dysfunctional outcomes in call centre operations. The following types of controls are adopted by typical BPO organizations.

1. Automated call distribution (ACD) system.
2. Electronic foot printing.
3. Taping and playback of calls.
4. Qualitative and quantitative performance targets.
5. Silent listening by team leader.
6. Team scoreboards.
7. Team meetings for assessing monthly performance.
8. Annual performance appraisal and team competitions.
9. 'On report' disciplinary close monitoring.

The research identified lack of control on their jobs (as most of the talk is designed by the organization) and intense electronic monitoring lead to dissatisfaction with jobs. In addition, studies by Houlihan (2001, 2002) also confirmed similar results. Comparatively an older study by Holman, Chissick, and Totterdell (2002) studied relationship between performance monitoring and well-being in call centre employees came up with different conclusion. It was found that monitoring could play a role in improving well-being if it is seen as part of broader system aimed at improving employee's skills and competencies.

It is the employee's increased ability to cope with demands of job that produces improvements in well-being. The research also suggested that if the perceived monitoring is intense then negative effects start manifesting in the well-being. The results did not support the argument that monitoring is an intrinsically threatening and anxiety-provoking event. The researcher agrees with findings of Holman, Chissick, and Totterdell (2002). This aspect has been discussed with human resources managers of BPO organizations, and twelve employees concurred with the researcher's proposition. It is observed by them that sometimes employees in India themselves volunteer to obtain feedback to know his or her interaction experience as it improves their subsequent performance. However, an item was included in the job satisfaction instrument to reflect this dimension as "*international performance culture at work place*" as it is referred in BPO organizations in India, informing the employees that it is required by client organizations.

2.2.4 Psychological Contract and BPO Employment

Christine, Gillian, and Garavan (2008), argued that the reason for poor job satisfaction and human resources issues are due to not communicating expectations of organizations to employees by way of

psychological contract (Baccili, 2004). They found that in the same organization there is existence of two types of contracts; the first is *relational contract*, which is perceived by permanent employees as fulfilling if the conditions are met and exhibited high commitment; the second is *transactional contract* perceived by temporary staff as they are playing non-essential task of organization's competitiveness and exhibited low commitment. This kind of arrangement is not there in India and most of them are only permanent employees. However, the suggestion regarding relational contract will be used for providing recommendations.

2.2.5 Teams and Team work in BPO Operations

While call centres undertake routinized work, and designed to be performed by an individual as a part of technological structure, if that were the condition there is no role for team working in BPOs. However, many of the BPO organizations have teams, which have different meaning than what is being referred. Mueller (1994) defines team *is to be understood as a group of 8–15 members and is responsible for producing a well-defined output within a recognizable territory, where members rotate from job to job with some regularity, under a flexible allocation of tasks.*” However, teams in BPOs do not exhibit these characteristics.

Batt's (1999) examination of call centre teams showed that effective performance relied on group learning, notably sharing information about problems with customers and software systems rather than job rotation and multiskilling or as a part of being communities of coping¹³.

Thus, while interdependence and autonomy are being low, Batt-opined more limited form of teamwork is observed in call centres. Managerial interest in teams could also reflect their use for performance management purposes; first as a unit for appropriate measurement of processes and outcomes, or two as a means of introducing competitive mechanisms across teams to boost productivity, it has been observed by researcher that the second purpose is more predominant in BPO organization in India. Under such circumstances, the focus would be on interdependence in outcomes.

Furthermore, management set objectives for team leaders that have a different balance between control and coaching functions. Thus, there can be indirect task dimensions. On the other hand, there are also normative objectives. Through recruitment, training, appraisal and other mechanisms, organizations seek to identify and modify the behaviour and attitudes of employees (e.g., in the direction of acting as a

¹³ Ibid., p.10.

‘team player’). In the context of BPO, it could be argued that a primary purpose is to offset the individualistic and regulative character of the work through some sense of shared identity and sociability, thus indirectly contributing to enhanced commitment and ‘discretionary effort.’

Korczynski (2001) research suggested that call centre workers accepted the teamwork despite the fact that they were *pseudo-teams* that is administrative categories in which supervisors had control. The motivation for using teams for management was to reinforce unitarist ideology while workers used this rhetoric to reinforce ‘positive peer relations on the office floor’ (Korczynski, 2001). This emphasis on the normative characteristics of teams in call centres leads to a third potential explanation, one that rests on maintaining a clearer distinction between teams and teamwork. Organizational behaviour literature promoted benefits of small groups for enhanced satisfaction, well-being, performance, and decision-making. These putative benefits have then been linked to the existence and expansion of teams in contemporary work environments (Parker and Jackson, 1993). Organizational behaviour perspectives rest in part on the parallel distinctions between formal and informal, task and sentient groups.

The latter issue is a distinction is drawn by Miller and Rice (1967), with task groups being based on the human resources necessary for work activity, while sentient groups are those to which individuals are prepared to commit themselves and on which they depend for emotional support. Deriving initially from the human relations tradition (Roethlisberger and Dickson, 1964), an attraction for management is the potential for the emotional closeness associated with informal and sentient groups at work to be transferred to the formal, task environment. The creation of teams thus becomes a means for ensuring that the boundaries of task and sentient groups coincide organizationally (Thompson and McHugh, 2002). Therefore, devolved responsibilities, supported by high trust organizational climates, are seen as encouraging employees to engage in positive behaviors that lead to improved job performance and intra-group dynamics. The relevance of this discussion is; the teams are not organized not in traditional sense; are designed for emotional coping. The teamwork recognition happens inside organization and outside organization in the form of parties and as stress relieving practices paid by BPO companies termed by researchers as fragility of fun¹⁴. This dimension is considered while providing recommendations.

¹⁴ Ibid., p.12.

2.2.6 BPO Employee Attitude towards Union Membership

Sarkar (2007) studied with focus on investigating attitudes of BPO industry employees towards union membership. He found that while class based collectivism is experienced by old economy, if choice is given for employees to be neutral, there will be shift towards greater societal individualism. The demographic characteristics of BPO employees are one of the reasons cited for this trend. Hofstede 's (1980) study shows most of the western nations to be high on individualistic dimensions of work value orientation and attributed the growth of the new industrial cities, which are inhabited by floating populations as the main reason behind the decline of collectivism in western civilization. However, there is a need to establish why employees preferred not to have unions despite tougher working conditions. *This dimension is identified as a gap and included in the present research to find the attitude towards collective bargaining.*

2.2.7 BPO Employee Satisfaction Survey-India

Every year Dataquest in conjunction with IDC India conducts a comprehensive Employee Satisfaction Survey for BPO industry. The purpose is to find the job satisfaction levels from the perspective of the BPO employees.

There are six big BPO companies (with over 5000 employees) featured in 2007 survey list. It is the mid-sized (greater than 1000 and lesser than 5000 employees) companies that occupied 50% places. The main highlights of the report are higher attrition rates, and wage hike that came down to 14.8% from 17.2% (2006). Major health ailments reported by them which have been increasing over the years are sleep disorders (32.4%), digestive system related disorder (25.3%), eyesight problems(19.5), severe stomach related problems(12.2%), depression, lethargy, anxiety, ear problems and voice loss. Insomnia is the most common of the ailments for the industry and it mostly affects the agent or customer relations executive level employees. BPO employees are also known to have panic or anxiety attacks. The survey has also for the first time collected data on back pain and close to 2.34% complained about persistent and niggling back issues. Most of the BPO companies have a doctor on-board. There is no comprehensive study by a panel of doctors to study and suggest suitable occupational therapies. The reason for stress at work as given by employees are, travel time (32.1%), work timing (28.9%), insufficient holidays (27.4%), workload (25.9%), long working hours (24.4%), pressure to perform on metrics (20.2%), repetitive nature of work (20.1%) and irate customers (15%). The major reasons quoted for leaving job, salary (34.2%), no growth opportunity (20.7%), higher

education (14.1%), timing (13.5%), no peaceful life (12.9%), and working on holidays (12.1%).

These dimensions especially relating to work logistics (travel time, work timings, change in jobs) are taken into account while designing the research instrument.

2.2.8 Study by Occupational Physicians

In a study of French BPO organizations studied by human resources experts and occupational physicians, Choffat *et al.*, (1999) reported that the mental strain involved in these new kinds of job would seem to be more than for other similar occupations. The physical demands of the job persist, but psychological and mental demands have become predominant. Occupational physicians have observed an increasing number of complaints from employees related to stress and working conditions. Some authors speak of “job-strain” to refer to a combination of high demands and low decision latitude (Brissonet, Larocque and Moisan, 2000; Niedhammer *et al.*, 2006), while a combination of high demands, low decision latitude and low social support has been referred to as “*iso-strain*” (Niedhammer *et al.*, 2006). Similar study in United Kingdom by (Hyman *et al.*, 2003) conformed work life imbalance in the call centre employees.

Since occupational physicians conducted the study, it is also right for mentioning the characteristics of sample. The population was 71.9% female, with a mean age of 32.4 years (median: 30 years). This young population included a substantial proportion of singles (884; 41.7%); 1,311(62.0%) were childless.

The general educational level was high, 68.2% of French employees having at least 2 years' higher education. Most (1,937; 91.2%) had permanent work contracts. The demographic typology of the employees studied is similar to that of Indian employee and may be explored for research. In this research, psychological demands were considered high for 56.1% of employees. High psychological demands can be a good thing if associated to high decision latitude but in the present study, it was associated to low latitude for 34.5% (job strain). Taking account of organizational limitations, French physicians, and work psychologists of United Kingdom concurred and recommended that there should be efforts to be focused on increasing employee autonomy (HSE, 2003). They established empirical evidence that there is a significant correlation between workload, task monotony and the occurrence of episodes of emotional exhaustion in their population of call-center employees. Social support from co-workers and superiors is often a good defense against stress; a call-center employee who feels supported by his

or her supervisor will have a more positive perception of controls, show less absenteeism and fewer tendencies to emotional exhaustion (Deery *et al.*, 2002). In summary, job stress should be combated with higher job latitude or autonomy with social support and the researcher agrees with these findings. *However, in the absence of possibility of job latitude or autonomy that is dictated by market conditions and client's requirement, what kind of alternatives are possible? This is one of the gaps identified and included in the research.*

2.3 Technology- Axial Principle to Scrutinize the Different Dimensions of Society

There is a need to answer the question why to use social forecasting for BPO industry problems. Present approach to solve attrition rates is based on reductionist approach and on the assumption that society, its composition, and forces that provide trajectory to the society remain constant. Assuming constancy of society and societal relationships is not in tune with reality. Another method is to borrow solutions developed in the context of western society and implementing in Indian environment. The composition of society is unique to each country and more so in the cases of country like India with diverse people with diverse cultures and aspirations working together.

As generally observed; technology changes the nature of relations, occupational structure, polity, and values. Social forecasting considers technology as an axial principle to examine society. This is prime reason for considering social forecasting as a tool to analyze and provide solutions to BPO industry challenges. The historical roots need to be understood to appreciate social forecasting application to business. Bell (1973) initiated his study on social forecasting with the features of post-industrial society. He deliberated his idea of social forecasting by providing an axial principle- *technology* to examine different dimensions of society. The term "*post-industrial,*" is employed to emphasize "*intellectual technology.*" Such emphasis does not mean that technology is the only determinant of all other societal changes as no conceptual scheme ever exhausts a social reality. Each conceptual scheme is a prism that selects some features, in order to highlight historical change to answer certain questions. Capitalism refers to socio-economic dimension, while post-industrial refers to the socio-technical dimension of a society. Bell (1973) pointed out that, Marx thought that the mode of production (the sub-structure of society) determines and encompasses all other dimension of society.

Since the capitalism was prevailing mode of production in most of the western society, Marx sought to use capitalism to explain all realms of social conduct, from economics, politics to culture.

Marx expected capitalist production would spread through out the world, it would determine the other realms of life and consequently national differences will disappear, and only capitalists and workers will be left to have final confrontation. However, the nature of polity do not rest on economic foundations only, but on historical traditions, on value systems, and on the way in which power is concentrated or dispersed throughout the society. Therefore, Bell (1973) argued that the mode of production alone do not determine the social relations. His focus has been on the influence of *technology*, not as an autonomous factor but as an analytical element, in order to see what social changes come in the wake of new technologies, and what problems the society, and its political system, must attempt to solve. Present research of BPO focused on assumptions that do not take into consideration of technology, its effect on changes in occupational characteristics, changes in the structure of economy in the from of network economy and role of mobility of capital. Social forecasting encompasses these dimensions as meta phenomena that affect every dimension of society. The component to be studied within the framework of social forecasting is given in the next section.

2.3.1 Social Forecasting and Dimensions of Society

At the macro level of study of social forecasting, Bell (1973) suggested society to be divided into three parts, social structure, polity, and culture. The social structure consists of economy, technology, and occupation system. The polity regulates the “*distribution of power and adjudicates the conflicting claims and demands of individuals and groups.*” The culture is the domain of “*expressive symbolism and meaning or total way of life shared by members of society.*” It includes language, values, and symbolic meanings, but also material objects. Each of the aspects is built on axial principle, which at present is technology.

Western Societal Structure

In the western society based on free market forces, the social structure is based on economizing or optimization of allocation of resources according to the principles of least cost, profit maximization, and substitutability. The axial principle of polity is exclusion or inclusion based on affordability. The axial principle of culture is desire for fulfillment and enhancement of self. The three parts of society are linked by a common *value system*.

Indian Societal Structure

In the context of India, while, equality and participation are the axial principles of polity, the essential task of the socio- political system in India is to provide legitimate, rational, and acceptable bases for inclusion and exclusion of population in various spheres of its activity. Technological inventions do increase goods and services. However, socio-political system mediates demands of diverse groups. However in the case of India, norms, values, ethos, and social customs based on age, gender, religion, caste, culture, conventions, place of origin, are more effective instruments that work beyond the institution of market (Social Development Report, 2006). In the case of BPO industry young people fresh from college are only preferred specifying the upper age limit of twenty-six for employment (Remesh, 2004) and exceptionally low number of persons from rural areas are employed. *This is one of the gaps identified and present research addresses issues relating to demographic and social variables.*

2.3.2 Essential features of Social Forecasting

Lebell and Krasner (1977) have discussed selecting environmental forecasting techniques from business planning requirements. They studied the business planning requirements of different business organizations and identified different planning levels.

The business organization moves from one phase of development to another phase of development. However, at each stage the environmental factors to be studied also change. A range of techniques is suggested including qualitative and quantitative measures in economic, technological, and political domains.

Therefore, for the present study economic, technological, political models are also included to enrich the forecasting exercise.

Gordon and Jakil (2005) drew attention to role of judgment heuristics, the assumptions of reductionism and the potential offered by new sources of social data in social forecasting. Judgment heuristics documents decision making based on psychological irrationalities such as thinking that murder is more common than suicide while the fact is other way round. There is assumption in forecasting to arrive at solution by breaking down problem into its elements for better accuracy-reductionism. However, notion of reductionism is unproven and this has to be taken into account while disaggregating data. Due to awareness, new social databases are created, are made available, and need to be taken and integrated in forecasting. *Effort has been taken in the present research to integrate the suggestions.*

2.3.3 Initiation of Study of Social Forecasting

An examination of literature with respect to initiation of social forecasting resulted in identifying extensive study by Taylor (1977), regarding importance of study of values.

His study examined work of Eysenck (1954), Morris (1956) and Fowles (1977) on values. Taylor strongly suggested the need for study on values in social forecasting. Harman (1978) commented on the need for including study of values, focusing on some of the limitations that are likely to impede study. Nonetheless, he agreed that study of values is most important for prediction and change. Therefore, to initiate social forecasting in BPO industry, a study of values or specifically value priorities of employees have been taken up. *There has not been any study of value priorities of employees that is available in India and this gap is addressed in the present research.* Value is a term used in different contexts and in the next section, literature on values is examined.

2.4 Values

Theorists from different disciplines have given different definitions of values. There are many words used in values literature, such as value systems, value priorities, personal values, social values, cultural values, cardinal values, and organizational values to describe the construct. There is a need to have clarity in what is used in the present research.

Values Definition

Allport (1962) suggested, “*Value priorities were the dominating force in life because they direct all of the person’s activity towards their realization.*” The first question to be addressed is whether values should be investigated from the perspective of an entity being evaluated. For example, how much value does the entity have? Alternatively, from the perspective of a person doing the valuing exemplified by, what a person value? It is now agreed by all theorists that values construct is from the perspective of the person who evaluates the entities in his or her own environment (Feather, 1971, 1975, 1982).

As an aid to the persons' evaluation of the stimuli in their environments, values would be a cognitive structure in which information on past evaluations are collected (Bargh *et al.*, 1992). There are five features of values construct that are commonly used: (a) beliefs, (b) desirable end states or behaviors, (c) trans-situational guides, (d) selection and evaluation of behaviour events and (e) relative ordering of beliefs, desirable end states or guides as given by Schwartz and Bilsky (1987,1990). These features are consistent with the suggestion that the *value system is a stable meaning producing superordinate cognitive structure.*

An examination of definitions and comments given by various theorists will be appropriate here.

Table 2.2 A selection of values definitions

Definition Given by	Definition
Kluckhohn (1951)	A value is a conception, explicit or implicit, distinctive of an individual or characteristic of a group, of the desirable that influences the selection from available modes, means, and ends of action.
Lewin(1952)	Values influence behaviour but have not the character of a goal, (i.e., of a force field). For example, the individual does not try to "reach" the value of fairness, but fairness is "guiding" his behaviour. It is probably correct to say that values determine which types of activity have a positive and which have negative valence for an individual in a given situation. In other words, values are not force fields but they induce force fields. That means values are constructs that have the same psychological dimension as "power fields."
Rokeach , 1973)	A value is an enduring belief that a specific mode of conduct or end-state of existence is personally and socially preferable to an opposite or converse mode of conduct or end-state of existence.
Schwartz (1994,1996)	Values are desirable transsituational goals, varying in importance, that serve as guiding principles in the life of a person or other in society.
Schwartz (1999)	Values as conceptions of the desirable that guide the way social actors (e.g. organizational leaders, policy-makers, individual persons) select actions, evaluate people, people and events, and explain their actions and evaluations.
Méndez (2002)	We cannot be indifferent about values, they demand a response from us, and this is what sets them apart from mere tastes and preferences.
Ravlin (1995)	Values are normative: they tell us how we should behave-although often they are prescribed in positive terms.
Argandoña (2002)	Values are reflected in decisions; the repetition of values in decisions shows the existence of virtue and strengthens it; and the body of virtues shapes a character, which gives consistency to subsequent decisions until a conduct is defined. In turn each of these stages makes a mark on other people's values, in the same way that their decisions, virtues, values are interrelated; they influence each other mutually-which is not to say that our values are imposed on us by other people's values.

SOURCE: Prepared by Researcher.

Based on the discussions following definition is adopted for the present research. Value is *“specific mode of conduct or abstract meaning producing cognitive structure that is personally and socially desirable, and the importance of this specific mode of conduct to a person or group that is transsituational and influences the selection from available modes, means, and ends of actions.”*

Values are transsituational indicating that they do not depend on situations and largely transcend time and geography to become an integral part of way of being, influencing attitude, and behaviour and to the point of shaping character.

They are distinct of an individual or a group. Therefore, value system for all the individuals is same and universal and referred as universal value system. However, people differ with respect to priorities they set on the universal value system. *The priorities by individual or group on universal value system are known as value priorities.* (Schwartz, 1992, 1994, 1996).

Dimensions of Value System

Rokeach (1973) in his seminal study discussed dimensions of value system. The present research's theoretical basis of operationalization of value priorities definition is based on Rokeach findings and later moderated by other experts especially by works of Schwartz and Bilsky. The first research document used by Rokeach has named values with brief explanation of their meaning, and asked people to arrange the words in the order of importance to them. There were two types of value words in the list: goals or terminal values and modes of conduct or instrumental values.

The list of goals included statements such as comfortable life, self-respect, or self-esteem, and the mode of conduct list included such things as broad minded, forgiving, and helpful. Respondents arranged the list of values in terms of importance placed on them. The list as suggested by Rokeach (1968, 1969, 1970, 1979) and Rokeach and Parker (1970), meant to cover most of the values. However, Braithwaite and Law (1985) identified four omissions from the list: values relating to physical development and well-being, individual rights, thriftiness, and carefulness. Schwartz (1992) questioned the need for the usefulness of the terminal- instrumental distinction. Schwartz and Bilsky (1987, 1990) developed a theory about value system with focus on motivational concern that is embedded in each value.

Holding the fundamental assumption that people differ only in relative importance they place on universally important values, they proposed a set of value types, the implications of priorities on one value type over the other within an integrated system.

Value Types- A Paradigmatic Explanation

Schwartz (1992) suggested that two motivational dimensional structures for the value system. The dimensions are based on two fundamental human problems that need to be solved.

The first dimension, named as conservation-openness to change continuum, relate to the conflict between being motivated “to follow their own intellectual and emotional interest in unpredictable and uncertain directions” or “to preserve the status quo and “the certainty it provides in relationships with close others, institutions, and traditions”. The second dimension, named as self-enhancement-self-transcendence continuum, relating to the “*conflict between concern for the consequences of own and others actions for the self*” and “*concern for the consequences of own and others’ actions in the social context.*” Ten value types are arranged along these two dimensions. The self-enhancement-self-transcendence dimension or individual-social context outcomes reflect about people belief in human nature (Wrightman, 1991). People who have greater focus on the social context outcomes may believe that humans are essentially good, while people who have a greater focus on individual outcomes than on social context of outcomes may be less positive about others’ essential goodness (Rohan, 2000). The focus on the opportunity-organization dimension (i.e., the openness to change-conservative dimension) may relate to temperament.

Table 2.3 Value Types, definitions, and representative values

Value Types and definitions	Representative Values
Power: Social status and prestige, control or dominance over people and resources.	Social power: control over others, dominance. Authority: The right to lead or command. Wealth: Material possessions, money.
Achievement: Personal success through demonstrating competence according to social standards.	Success: Achieving goals Capability: Competence, effectiveness, efficiency. Ambition: Hard work, aspirations. Influence: Have an impact on people and events.
Hedonism: Pleasure and sensuous gratification for oneself.	Pleasure: Gratification of desires Enjoyment in life: enjoyment of food, sex, leisure and so on.
Stimulation: Excitement, novelty and challenge in life.	Daringness: Adventure-seeking, risk taking. A varied life: Filled with challenge, novelty, and change. An exciting life: Stimulating experiences.
Self-Direction: Independent thought and actions-choosing, creating, exploring.	Creativity: Uniqueness, imagination. Freedom: Freedom of action and thought. Independence: Self-reliance, self-sufficiency Curiosity: Interest in everything, exploration. Choose own goals: Select own purposes.
Universalism: Understanding, appreciation, tolerance and protection for the welfare of all people and for nature.	Broadminded: Tolerant of different ideas and beliefs. Wisdom: Mature understanding of life. Social Justice: Correcting injustice, care for the weak. Equality: Equal opportunity for all. A world at Peace: Free of war and conflict. A world of beauty: Beauty of nature and arts. Unity with nature: Fitting into nature. Protecting the environment: Preserving nature.
Benevolence: Preservation and enhancement of welfare of the people with whom one is frequent personal contact.	Helpful: Working for the welfare of others. Honesty: Genuineness, sincerity Forgiveness: Willingness to pardon others. Loyalty: Faithful to my friends, groups. Responsibility: Dependable, reliable.
Tradition: respect, commitment and acceptance of the customs and the ideas that traditional culture or religion provide the self.	Humility: Modesty, self-effacement Acceptance of my portion in life: Submission to life's circumstances. Devotion: Hold to religious faith and belief Respect for tradition: Preservation of time-honored customs. Modest: Avoiding extremes of feeling or action.
Conformity: Restraint of actions, inclination, and impulses likely to upset or clam others and violate social expectations or norms.	Politeness: Courtesy, good manners Obedience: Dutiful, heed obligations. Self-discipline: Self-restraint, resistance to temptation. Honor parents and elders: Showing respect.
Security: safety, harmony, and stability of society of relationship and of self.	Family security: Safety for loved ones. National security: Protection of my nation from enemies. Social order: Stability of society. Cleanliness: Neatness, tidiness. Reciprocation of favors: Avoidance of indebtedness.

SOURCE: Schwartz, S.H (1996). Value priorities and behaviour: Applying a theory of integrated value systems. IN C.Seligman, J.M.Osion, & M.P.Zanna (Eds). The Ontario symposium: The psychology of values (Vol. 8 pp. 1-24). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.

Identification of the underlying value system structure, Schwartz (1992) specified the relations among the value types in the value system: People's priorities on adjacent value types will be similar, while differences in priorities will occur when value types are opposite to each other.

Figure 2.1 Locations of Ten Value Types in a Two-dimensional Space.

SOURCE: Bardi, A., and Schwartz S.H. (2002) Values and Behaviour: Strength and Structure of Relations, *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, Vol. 29, p. 1209.

All the value types in the human value system are important in the human functioning. The relative importance or the value priorities people place on each value type reflects their choices. However, this does not mean that for every value priority people will allocate something.

A careful observation of the figure, indicate that if higher value is placed on achievement, there is chance of placing lower value on conformity.

Nature of value priorities

Value priorities should they be what people ought to do? Alternatively, what people want to do? To answer this question, Schwartz, and Bilsky (1987, 1990) definition of value based on three universal needs of human existence will be helpful. The value construct is described in terms of cognitive representation of three types that is biological needs, social interaction demands for interpersonal coordination, and social institutional demands for group welfare and survival. Thus, it is a mix of both desired and desirable. Values as guide for survival for both biological and social needs deserve further discussion. In many occasions, people ignore their personal safety to help others. The actions of heroes to sacrifice life for the sake of values, provide a cue that value are more than mere guides for survival. Similarly, value priorities may provide guides for goodness. If one lives by drives alone, then there is no difference between man and animals (Tomkins, 1962) and some people believe that humans strive

to be moral and ethical (Aronson, 1992). Therefore, value priorities provide the principles for moral and ethical living.

Value priorities as guides for best living

The next point is value priorities as guides to “best possible living.” The dynamic organization of peoples’ ability to cognize environment enables them to live the best possible living. They are not simply driven to satisfy simply basic survival needs, they are driven to live as pleasantly as living. However, the constraints in the environment may not help a person to behave in a way that is always consistent with their value priorities. People choose fast and frugal satisfying strategy-named as “*take the best strategy*”, (Gingerenzer and Goldstein, 1996). Their progress in living, can be understood as the evaluation that underlie self-esteem, in which self-esteem is described as resulting from an estimate of progress in living the best way possible (Rohan, 2000). People who have high priorities on tradition and conformity will judge personal desires to be less important than being a cooperative member of a group. On the other hand, people who have higher priority on being hedonistic may consider personal desires have more important than group requirements. According to psychologists, people strive to view themselves in four ways (Aronson, 1992):

as competent, predictable, consistent, and moral. The other most important need is the need for relatedness. Combining these two views, these striving is dictated by value priorities.

Therefore, people who judge that belongingness is more important may emphasis the social context of value priority more than the individual context. Configurations and experiences of and personal attributes will result in variations in peoples' views of what best living means to them. Similarly, if circumstances change the value priorities also undergo a change. If a person becomes a parent, the value priority on conservation that is on tradition, conformation, and security will be more as they must provide an environment that is comfortable and happy for the new born (Altemeyer, 1988). However, identification of values priorities alone may not be sufficient. There is a need to identify value typologies.

Value Priorities to Value Typologies

Value space has been studied and documented in the form of value typologies by Zetterberg and Zetterberg (1997). The value priorities factors are transformed into three-dimensional space. The first dimension of value space moves from stability to modernity. It corresponds to a scale from traditionalism-innovation. In the innovation phase, importance

is given to new ways of experimentation as opposed to stability. The second dimension corresponds to scale from fidelity-pragmatism. While in the value of fidelity, one dramatizes his or her values.

In the case of value of pragmatism, one compromises his or her values. The fidelity includes matters relating to conscience- loyalty towards family, solidarity with weak, compassion for suffering and saving planet for future generations. The opposite of this is pragmatism or instrumentality. The third dimension separates a concern with material things from a concern with human beings representing the continuum of materialism and humanism.

Typology of Value Carriers

A division of the population according to types depending on their high or low position on each of the three dimensions is known as typology. There are eight types of value carriers. These groups' typologies are from studies of western economies. To present research, the value priorities are identified and analyzed through the three-dimensional scaling. The typologies (of western societies) described by the researchers are used as there are no Indian counterparts are available. The typologies are given from point of view of marketing research; however, they may be adopted with appropriate modifications.

One major limitation of adoption is value typologies by Zetterberg and Zetterberg (1992) is proprietary and copyrighted and, therefore, independent verification of results is not possible.

At the present stage, there is a need to understand the relation between value priorities and work related behaviour, especially job satisfaction, as it has been pointed out the reason for job attrition is due to low job satisfaction.

2.5 Value Priorities – Work Related Behaviour - Job Satisfaction

Role of value priorities and work related behaviour received renewed interest over the past decade (Furnham *et al*, 2005), studies have started examining the effect of values on commitment, job satisfaction and performance (Ang, Van Dyne and Begley, 2003; Farh, Hackett and Liang, 2007). Fischer and Smith (2006) argued that employees from different socio cultural backgrounds would bring different career aspirations and value priorities to the work and highlighted importance of study of values. Values are supposed to play a functional role in work related processes and outcome of job satisfaction and work performance (Chew and Putti, 1995; Lam, Schaubroeck, and Aryee, 2002). For the study of values and its relationship with job satisfaction, there is a need to clarify whether work related values are to be used or general value

priorities are to be used? Roe and Ester (1999) indicate that role of general value priorities must be taken into account.

Furthermore, Berings, De Fruyt, and Bouwen (2004) emphasized that value priorities have ascribed a significant role in determining the fit between individuals and employment organization. The underlying assumption is that persons will be happier and more motivated and satisfied when value priorities are congruent with those emphasized in the organization. Understanding of individual-level differences in value priorities could provide insight into better ways of managing different employees (Francesco and Chen, 2004). Literature survey and studies agree with the proposition that value priorities of employees have a strong relationship with job satisfaction.

The initiation of social forecasting and need for study of job satisfaction coincides with study of value priorities. *Thus, studying on value priorities is undertaken to help understanding of value profile of employees of BPO organizations. There is no prior study on value priorities available, this is considered as a gap in literature and research is undertaken in this area.*

2.6 Job satisfaction

Introduction

The BPO employee's status would appear to be representative of the ideal-typical white-collar employees of the late 1980s of Indian state and central governments. However, keen observation of the tasks indicates that the work acquired routinization, technological intensity, high monitoring, and dealing with persons from different country, faking their accent, providing fake name and address in the context of BPO work. Similarly, there are night shifts and working on Indian cultural events and having a holiday on client country's cultural events. Given the deterioration in work, market and status situations of clerical and BPO labour to such an extent that it is seen by some as being progressively analogous to assembly-line work¹⁵ (Bain *et al.*, 2002; Taylor and Bain, 1999); it is appropriate to raise research issues concerning job satisfaction.

¹⁵ Ibid., p.12,13.

Job Satisfaction-Definition

Satisfaction is an affective attitude- a feeling of relative like or dislike towards something. Job satisfaction has different descriptions. It is defined in several ways by researchers. Job satisfaction is the stance which people take toward their jobs; it is the fact of being happy based on the person's motivation, morale and the job (Weiss,2002); it can be the expectation of success obtained as a result of the efforts exerted; it is a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job; an affective reaction to one's job; and an attitude towards one's job (Dunnette, 1970).

For the purpose of present research job satisfaction can be defined *“as the stance taken concerning the job as a result of the salary, inspection, working conditions, promotion opportunities, recognition of skills, evaluation of the job, social relations at work, and the work environment.”* Job satisfaction is a multidimensional concept. Job characteristics, organization, and management, salary, working conditions, co-workers, promotion opportunities, and inspection are included in the job satisfaction concept as well as factors such as the expectations that individuals have of their jobs.

The type of work, whether it necessitates creative skills, the difficulty of the objectives and if the work is monotonous, has an impact on performance.

Because of the job being monotonous and boring, individuals become dissatisfied with their work and are alienated from the job whereas innovation and creativity in profession contribute to the attachment of individuals to the work (Mitchell and Larson, 1987). All emotional, logical, and behavioral tendencies of the individual in relation to their work result in the person taking a negative or positive stance towards that job (Gilmer, 1971). The most effective use of work force is enabled when individuals are satisfied with their jobs when they work in accord with their own concept of individual freedom. Job satisfaction affects all of the social life of individuals. If employees are satisfied with their work, this satisfaction spreads over their whole life. Some studies have suggested that individuals with an elevated level of job satisfaction display positive behaviors, and their psychological health is ameliorated in their social life (Robbins, 1996). In essence, job satisfaction is a hybrid concept that has attracted contributions from a number of related disciplinary perspectives mainly stemming from psychology or *psychological humanism* (Watson, 2004) and sociology. Of the psychological humanist offerings, that of Herzberg (1968) has

informed subsequent research which seeks to validate the view that higher levels of employee productivity are an outcome of satisfaction with intrinsic or job-related factors, provided that extrinsic factors such as pay, job security and promotion prospects are acknowledged. This strand of research therefore brings to the fore the dialectic of the intrinsic and extrinsic and has attracted the concerns of sociologists, some pre-dating the contribution of Herzberg, would place the job satisfaction debate firmly within the context of the broader human condition of either alienation and instrumentalism (Goldthorpe *et al.*, 1968). For the purpose of present research, the intrinsic and extrinsic factors of job satisfaction relevant to BPO organization are taken into consideration.

2.6.1 Absenteeism and Attrition Relationship with Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is more a matter of determinants of working conditions, salary, prerequisites, and organizational treatment. Varoom (1954) indicated that, if an assumption is made that measures of job satisfaction reflect the value of the job to its occupant, then it follows that job satisfaction should be related to the strength of force on the person to remain in his job. The more satisfied an employee, the stronger the force on him to remain in his job and the less probability of his leaving it voluntarily. Job Satisfaction can be an important indicator of how employees feel about their jobs and a predictor of work behaviors such as

organizational citizenship (Organ and Ryan, 1995; Wegge, Parkes, and Van Dick, 2007; Saari and Judge, 2004). Job satisfaction can partially mediate the relationship of personality variables and deviant work behavior (Mount and Johnson, 2006). Thus attrition, absenteeism, and deviant work behavior is caused by job dissatisfaction. *As job satisfaction is a major outcome and not being studied, it has been included in the present study to fill the research gap of literature in this area.*

2.7 Role Scope

It has been identified that role scope of employees is not studied in BPO organizations and there is a need to understand the theoretical underpinning of the concept. The role theory perspective emerged simultaneously across disciplines in the social sciences during the 1920s and early 1930s. Biddle (1979) concisely defines role theory as *“role is concerned with the study of behaviors that are characteristic of persons within contexts and with various processes that presumably produce, explain, or are affected by those behaviors.”* A role is an expected pattern or set of behaviors associated with a particular position or status. Role is one of the building blocks of social systems and the summation of the requirements with which the system confronts the individual member.

Linton (1936) was first to provide *role* a principal place in social sciences; Newcomb (1950) borrowed the concept of role from anthropology into social psychology.

Parsons (1951) and Merton (1957) consider it essential to understand social action and social structure. Human organizations are defined as role systems, and the psychological basis of organizational functions is approached in terms of motivation to fulfill organizational roles. Niehoff and Moorman (1993) asserts that if employees perceive the outcomes of their evaluations in the light of values to be fair, they will be likely to reciprocate by performing behaviors to benefit their organizations that go beyond the role performance of their jobs (Pare and Tremblay, 2007). One of the important outcomes of committed employee is the enhancement of role performance (Somers and Birnbaum, 1998). However, there is a need for understanding how organizational roles are defined, and role behaviour is evoked by an organization. Role behaviour refers to *“the recurring actions of an individual appropriately interrelated with repetitive activities of others to produce a predictable outcome.”* Some related concepts are defined here to understand the concept of role further. Role expectations *“are evaluative standards applied to the behaviour of any person who occupies a given organizational role.”* Sent Role, which consists *“of communications*

stemming from role expectations and sent by other members of the organization of the role set as attempts to influence a given person who is given a particular role.”

Received role is “*the given person’s perception of the role sending addressed to him, including those he sends to himself.*” “The role expectations and sent role have to do with the cognitions, motivations, and behaviour of the members of the role senders; the received role and role behaviour have to do with cognitions, motivations, and behaviour of the given person. The process can be viewed as role episode involving cycle of sending role expectations, receiving the role, responding, evaluating, and sending again by the persons to the given person.

Role negotiation

The process by which role develops is referred to as role making or *role negotiation* (Turner, 1956; Graen, 1976; Graen and Scandura, 1987). These terms emphasize the fact that role development is more involved than the person simply understanding and complying with the expectations of the role set. Instead, the person and other members of the role set *actively and collaboratively work* to define the role in a way that is mutually satisfactory. There is an evaluation process of performance by given person, by role senders that is each other try to perform to the

expectations. If role expectations are not in tune with the values of the given person, there will be resistance. If the performance of the given person is not in tune with expectations, there will be changes in the role expectation. These cycles go on so that the person is set in the role in such a way that he meets other expectations, his expectations from others are met, and effective role negotiation has taken place. In this sense, role scope is *“perception of an employee regarding the opportunity given by the organization in the context of task environment to satisfy the basic human needs such as achievement, influence, control, extension, and affiliation.”* Role scope describes the task environment in motivational term, and it is *There is no study on role scope of front line employee of BPO industry are available study is undertaken to fill the gap.*

2.8 Occupational Changes Due to Technology

With respect to economies of information society there is a clear tendency towards the service sector as a key generator of new employment and products. The growth of telecommunication and convergence of technologies provide required fillip to telemarketing (Lara Rodriguez, 2003) and in turn to call centre industry.

World research indicate that higher number of people are employed in services compared to any other period in history. Work as a necessity to serve higher purpose is slowly replaced by the view that work is a means for being autonomous, creative, enabling individuals to express one self and develop ones own self by constant up gradation of skills and knowledge due to constant changes in technology. In a similar vein, the values related to work also underwent change from tradition, religious, familial values to individualistic value orientation. This development is *reflected* in the shift from instrumental orientation to expressive orientation of job content (Hindered, 1983; Yankelovich *et al*, 1985) and product of globalization of work (Altvater and Mahnkopf, 1997). In traditional order, the values relating to work are based on tradition and legitimized by institution of religion such as Protestant work ethic or Confucius work ethic. In the modern era, they became subject of individual freedom and personal autonomy. The individual has become free and independent from traditions and institutions (Wagner, 1995). The technological development also created two types of labour – *generic labour* and *self-programmable labour* according to Castells (1996, 1997a, 1997b). Generic labour refers to a person who is unskilled, possessed lower skills, or has a low level of education. They work for low wage labour and referred to as casual or substitutable labour.

Self-programmable labour refers to highly educated people who manage and control information with high creativity; this indicates need for continuous learning on the part of this type of labour force. Castells (2000a, 2000b, 2000c) views these trends as reversal of trend of socialization of labour that is in existence in industrial society. It is absence of *collective identity of workers* and a tendency to build careers by job-hopping and consequent lack of job security. This led to emergence of *entrepreneurial employee* who constantly upgrades his or her skills to remain employable given rise to new phenomena of work. The outcome is choices and responsibility for self-initiated action replaced collectively defined status. (Heller and Wellbery, 1986). People's decisions are increasingly grounded primarily on realization of personal interests from that of collective interests. An ethic of personal fulfillment is prevailing in modern society. (Middendrop, 1978; Felling and Peters, 1984; Wood and Zürcher, 1988; Halman, 1991; Van Den Broek and Heunks, 1994). Social theorists study globalization and changes in occupations and culture and they regard this phenomenon as a new kind of modernity. Organizations and individuals located in geographically wide places linked together through complex economic and communication networks, blurring temporal, spatial boundaries, or geography (Alvarez, and Kilbourn, 2002, Castells, 1999), characterize it.

Digitalization has facilitated the *flexibilization of labour* and *virtualization* and *rationalization* of the work process (Arunachalam, 1999) which in turn have enabled work to be delocalized, transnationalized, and globally managed with information technology.

The phenomena of individualization need to be understood in the context of sociological studies and need to be borrowed into mainstream human resources study.

2.9 Individualization

Contemporary research on study of individualization is drawn from works of Beck (1992), Beck, Elisabeth Beck, and Gernsheim (2002) and Anthony Giddens (1991). However, classical social theorists such as Durkheim, Max Weber, and Georg Simmel worked with the concept of individualization, which demonstrates its enduring relevance. Individualization refers to *the structural transformation of social institutions and change in the relationship of an individual to society*. The crucial point here is the manifold characterization of the construct of individualization, which had its origins from politics and economics in the nineteenth century to its contemporary focus on private lifestyles and self-expression. Individualization is understood *as a process in which fundamental social change took place in a transition from a*

stratified tradition to a modern society and which until today has continued to be accompanied by processes of modernization (Vendramin, 2004). Until now different thrusts of individualization have been identified (Junge, 1996).

Individualization is considered *as moving of relationship from institutional dependency to opportunities of individual choice*. (Leistering, 1997; Wohlrab-Sahr, 1997). Beck, Elisabeth Beck, and Gernsheim (1993,1994,and 2002) characterize individualization as *intentionally ambivalent and polymorphous. It is used as both an explanatory factor driving social change and as an outcome at the individual level*. Applications range from studies of large macro level societal changes and social class inequalities to psychological level of self-actualization and identity formation. It is non-linear, open-ended, and highly undecided. It is *not individualism, which is opposite of collectivism* as characterized by other theorists (Prabhakar, 2007b). This discussion leads to study of life course research, which is different from life cycle concept that is familiar in management literature.

2.9.1 Individualization and Life Course Research

Understanding of the construct of individualization requires brief mention of life-course research. Life-course research examines the interrelation between individuals and their institutional context over the

life span of individuals. Its focus is on how social processes, such as family, education, employment, and health domains of individual's life are structured over the individual life span. A life course is a culmination of multiple life events.

Life events refer to *significant incidents such as education, migration, employment - entering and exiting the labour force, entering, and leaving a relationship such as marriage, or becoming a parent.* These life events make up life-course domains or careers that are interdependent and interact with each other such as marriage leading to parenthood. The combinations of events that occur over individual life-course careers in turn produce unique individual life-course trajectories. The life-course perspective has been referred to as organizing principle or framework to understand the construct of individualization. This approach serves as a model to understand how the dynamic biographies of individuals differ or evolve over time across various societies. The study of life course centers on several aspects. Researchers focus on subjective meaning given to the life events through qualitative study of biographies such as meaning attributed to being divorced from spouse or being unemployed. Other focus is on quantitative focus of life events such as how often individuals enter unemployment or marriage and the absolute levels within a society that is number of unemployed or

divorced. Life course researchers suggest that individuals actively shape their own life courses based on a unique and meaningful sequence of decisions, which are embedded within an individual, network characteristics (including family and employer), and historical, cultural, social, and other institutional constraints. The life course is *not predictable life stages* as in the case of *life cycle*. It is the current life-course position of individuals, which reflect cumulative past events and an anticipation of their future life trajectory. It is examination of how life courses are affected by macro level societal changes such as globalization, economic depression, or war; how institutions such as educational system and employment play a role in the way these momentous changes influence individual opportunities, constraints, and decision-making. The structural and cultural context provide a person with resources, constraints, and habits, or frames that serve as national, cultural or class; and specific ways to interpret decision situations and produce a selective alertness to information.

This is referred as the *collective conscience, which is a common external social force consisting of ideas, values, norms, beliefs that are institutionalized in the social structure and internalized by individuals within that culture*. Individuals make life-course decisions at the micro

level by developing various strategies or risk calculations within their cultural domain of opportunities and constraints.

The term individualization has its roots from detraditionalization or freedom from traditional ties and affiliations and the dissolution of collective structures.

The implicit assumption is that the detachment from traditional values, ideas, norms, beliefs, or ideologies generates greater individual freedom, autonomy, and choices. The waning of tradition is a topic over centuries of human existence, which leads to an observation that it is not new phenomenon and it is cyclical phenomenon that assumes different forms. Beck's (1986, 1992) specifications of three moments of individualization include liberation (freedom from institutional structures), destabilization (loss of traditional certainties), and reintegration (control and new forms of social integration). The process of individualization denotes a shift in the responsibility of risk from the social structure (responsibility of government to provide unemployment allowance or welfare state or dependence on employer by way of retrenchment allowance) to that of individual, which is called as individualization of risk. Beck, Giddens, and Lash (1996) argues that post-industrial society is seeing the dis-embedding of the individual – that is the decline of traditional social communities such as social classes into

which one was born and the re-embedding of individuals in new 'life worlds' such as new social movements that are chosen by the individual. Due to demise of tradition, there is uncertainty and risk giving rise to growth of risk society. Risk in the pre modern era involved natural hazards, violence from armies, robbers, or risk of offending religious order. Risk in modern world emanates from reflexivity, human violence from terror, environmental degradation and specifically related to life course-the threat of personal meaninglessness with higher emphasis on self-identity, self-actualization, individualism, and personal responsibility. This necessitates individuals to develop their own biographies as he or she is confronted with plurality of choices in life course options. Three types of life courses are proposed by sociologists- *destandardized individualization*, conformist or *default individualization* and *fragile individualization*. The assumption in destandardization is that individuals calculate risk and exercise choice rather than to adopt a lifestyle that is handed over by tradition or former generations. In the case of conformist individualization, the individual is emancipated from social bonds- however; there is lack of appropriate capacities such as those who lack social capital in the form of education or social network. They select options that are default, without much thinking or mental effort available in the consumer-corporate society and mass culture. These individuals

follow a path that is different from that of previous generation, yet confirm to patterns held by most of their contemporary peers. This life course behaviour which is initially innovative and non traditional such as working mothers, choosing life of being single, children outside marriage eventually diffuse across individuals.

As it reaches a threshold level (that is considerable number of people engaged in the said behaviour), it becomes an accepted behaviour replacing long-standing tradition with new tradition. Most of the contemporary individualization theorists argue that leaving tradition from every-day decision-making process results in less of social control. From this weakened tradition emerges unpredictability of the consequences of outcomes of their decision making results in higher levels of uncertainty and risk as the individual is forced make choices about life events. With focus on individual choice and responsibility coupled with detraditionalization gives rise to fragile individualization. The detraditionalization liberates a person; however, it enhances uncertainty and individual responsibility. From this weakened tradition and unpredictability of consequences of outcomes gives rise to risk society. It is an environment where living and acting in uncertainty becomes a kind of basic experience (Beck and Bonb 1994). Life course choices progressively get blurred with uncertainty. The task of collection of

information is costly and time-consuming for decision making. As a result Beck (1994) argues that individuals may develop fragile identities that are constantly open for reinterpretation; experience a discrepancy from their desires and actual courses. The opposite of *risk* in sociological sense is *trust*, which entails commitment to another individual, group, system, or employer, or the binding of oneself to a long term decision. *Trust is the means of coping with risk.* In the environment of risk shifting to individual, trust in partner, employer or in the welfare state gets weaker, resulting in postponing of life events, choosing life course options that are more flexible and less binding across future time such as taking a break from work, accepting temporary assignments, postponing marriage or child birth. *The darker side of freedom of choice is that it brings high anxiety, feelings of individual responsibility and even depression.* The life course becomes an increasingly experimental process that is the responsibility of an individual. The growth in leisure time coupled with focus on self-actualization provides individuals with more time to ponder over their existence and life choices as opposed to getting along. *The dimension of individualization with respect to work and its effect on employees' perception towards job satisfaction is not studied in BPO organizations and identified as a gap to be addressed in present research.*

Measurement of Individualization

Accordingly, the central empirical-conceptual question of present study is: How can individualization be measured and operationalized at the actor level? The literature study recommends both qualitative and quantitative study and in the present research, quantitative research is adopted.

2.10 Typology of BPO Organizations

The occupational characteristics of BPO sector and competency requirements from employees is different from that of information technology organizations giving rise to different human resources issues from that of IT sector. The typology of BPO organizations is dissimilar to IT sector. A unique situation arises where BPO organizations are neither like that of manufacturing or service sector or to IT sector. There is a need to understand how BPO organizations are different or like that of other types of industry. As per discussion with different human resources managers regarding the typology, the comment by them is that, it is a new industry at infant stage of growth and the organizations have to pass through learning curve to be a mature industry as everybody is learning from customers, the management, and business organizations. To a certain extent, it is true. Nonetheless, this input is not sufficient to describe the typology. There is a need for

theoretical basis for analysis of typology of BPO organization. Typology is proposed based on extensive studies of Allport (1962). The genotypic function is defined as “*a function performed by organization as a subsystem of the society.*”

The genotypic function consists of four functions, with four types of organizations identified on the following basis:

Productive or economic organizations: These organizations are concerned with providing goods and services, and include mining, manufacturing, farming, utilities, and communication.

Maintenance organizations: These organizations are concerned with the socialization and training of people for roles in other organizations. Schools, religious organizations are examples of maintenance organizations.

Adoptive organizations: These are organizations that create new knowledge, innovate, find solutions to problems etc. The universities and research organizations are examples of this category.

Managerial-political organizations: These organizations have to do with the coordination and control of people and resources, and with arbitrating among competing groups. The state and agencies of government are examples of this category.

Society sustains these organizations by way of economic rewards to desirable behaviour, by maintenance of structure of education that inculcate the general norms and specific behavioral codes and by the political structure, which enforces the law.

These are the expressions of three basic social systems. They are, task requirements in relation to needs, shared values and norms and rule enforcement. In short, for the society to sustain there must be economic productive activities to satisfy needs, there must be a set of values and norms which are inculcated by socializing agencies to play distinct roles. Consecutively, to ensure integration and sustainability an authoritative decision making structure for the allocation of resources and rewards. To increase the overall capability of the society the universities and research organizations are created and maintained. Though an organization is typified by a particular genotype, which is predominant, it also supplements other institutions.

The second-order characteristics reflected in the following terms.

Nature of organizational throughput: Distinction between objects and people as the products of working of organizations. For example, output of BPO organization is people satisfied with their informational needs.

Nature of maintenance processes: a distinction between expressive or intrinsic rewards and instrumental or extraneous rewards as a way of attracting and holding members in organizations.

Nature of bureaucratic structure: a distinction in terms of ease of joining and leaving the organization, and the structure elaboration (degree of role scope or role elaboration and number of levels within an organization).

Expressive Cycle and Instrumental Cycle

There is a need to distinguish between Expressive Cycle and Instrumental Cycle. The example for expressive cycle is activities in a sports club. The members interact for self-enjoyment. The very task of sports club activity provides them with satisfaction. The energy spent on maintenance of the system is simple as there is total motivation to go through the process of input-process-output and come back to original state for next cycle with same energy. As mentioned in the introduction, the creation of Wikipedia is based on volitional trait.

The task of creating content that is read by the entire world itself provides enjoyment and the expressive cycle goes on, on a virtual momentum. The same case with ORKUT and FACEBOOK, The urge to share information and personal feelings and creative expression of self is an expressive cycle where people return to same tasks with more energy,

to keep the cycle move on. The other extreme of this typology is all negative emotions but for the pay or salary at the end of the month.

For example, dropping bombs in an enemy territory may not be a pleasant task, however, the instrumental reward in terms of money, fame etc. keep the cycle moving.

The expressive versus instrumental cycle of activities is related to the three bases of the organization. The *task requirements, shared values or expectations, and rule enforcement*. If the task generates its own motivation, people will carry out their activities in accordance with their values and opportunities for expressive satisfaction are maximized. Where performance is needed to follow rules, which must be followed to obtain rewards, the satisfaction tends to be instrumental. This discussion must be cautiously interpreted. Expressive cycle is an excellent reward; however, not all social and economic goals can be achieved by expressive cycle alone. There is a need for instrumental cycle. The process of individualization of work, which was found to be high in BPO organizations, a transition occurred with respect to reward of job from instrumental and extrinsic towards intrinsic and expressive. Personal development, autonomy, self-expression, self-unfolding are the most important needs of the people.

Partial Inclusion, Potency of Involvement, and Priority of Commitment

The way of looking at the nature of maintenance inputs in an organization, is in terms of the degree of inclusion of the individual's personality in the organization. The concepts are developed by Allport (1962) to describe the relations of the individual to social systems.

Partial Inclusion: An individual can be included in any organization partially. The individual as a personality does not need to enter into role requirement with anything that is his "*full potential*" or "*total response.*" The worker on the shop floor or a nurse in a hospital can meet their responsibilities with much of their mental energy is directed elsewhere. Segmental involvement of individuals is the basis for organizational structure. Only part of the "*life space*" is occupied by the organizational role. Individuals can belong to many organizations in addition to being members working for a particular organization and satisfy their motivational needs. Therefore, organizations consist of segments of people, rather than integration of their whole personality. Segmental involvement of individuals is the basis of organizational structure. Katz and Kahn (1970) opined that organizations consist of segments of people rather an integration of their whole personalities has been ignored by scientific theory.

Kunda (1992) while studying the nature of inclusion of information technology employees into organizations and found that the nature of inclusion is highest at the exclusion of other social organizations causing disturbing psychological and family issues.

Potency of Involvement: It is a related concept to partial inclusion. An employee who gets his major satisfaction outside his job is low on the dimension of inclusion may nevertheless be highly involved in the organization. His job provides the earnings so that he can carry on life satisfactorily. The potency of involvement can be supplemented with the concept of priority of commitment.

Priority of Commitment: As an individual belongs to different social organizations, he is faced with competing demands. He or she can meet the competing demands with the help of values. The values that are inculcated help an individual to achieve a balance of competing demands. The genotype of the BPO organization is that of production or economic organizations that are concerned with creation of wealth by way of providing service. There are two dimensions, creating wealth and providing service. If creating wealth for the country, or for self (as in the case of employee stock options), the expressive satisfaction will be higher. If a middle-class technocrat, who prospered and created wealth for others the expressive satisfaction will be more.

The shared values created by the chief executives of the organization will ensure success of the organization. The next point is the object of providing service. In BPO industry, it is molding behaviour of people or helping people to achieve their goals. The employee should know the outcome of his or her service as it would lead to better expressive satisfaction. The second order characteristics- output consists of satisfied people. Therefore, though the industry is technology intensive, people orientation and human interface are the most important considerations. Nature of bureaucratic structure is characterized by structured work specifications with stringent norms and flat structure. The maintenance of the BPO organization is more through instrumental cycle rather than through expressive cycle. In order to compensate for the expressive satisfaction, the bpo organizations provide an environment of fun. There are unwinding sessions for the employees in the form of cultural, games, picnics etc. While partial inclusion is the condition in traditional industries, the inclusion tends to be more than required by any other type of industry. The individual loses daytime social activities and other social events such as festivals as they are not holidays for the client organizations.

The potency of involvement expected out of employee is also extremely high. The employee is not expected to take leave and he or she is

provided with only one-week leave per annum. Due to uncertain environment, the employee is unable to prioritize his commitments, which leads to higher stress in performance of tasks. Summary of typology is given in the following table.

Table 2.4 Present typology of a typical BPO organization

First order Factors	Economic organization concerned with producing services.
Second order factors	Less of expressive cycle and more of instrumental cycle.
Partial Inclusion	BPO organizations require a person full inclusion while only partial inclusion is possible.
Potency of Involvement	High potency of involvement; The employee is expected to be incredibly involved in the organization at the cost of his or her tradition. This is not a sustainable in long run.
Priority of commitment	Priorities of commitment do not depend upon his or her values and pressurized to accept organizational tasks only. The important fact is he or she is supposed to have different name (generally name of client country), accept fake client country address, and mimic the accent of client.
Expressive and Instrumental cycle	The reward system emphasizes instrumental cycle in the form of salary, bonus, incentive, trips to foreign countries etc. compared to expressive reward system.

The typology described is unstable and prone to disequilibrium. If this typology is projected into a dynamic and changing global business environment, there will be more uncertainty. This is one of the

majors

reasons for multinational BPO's such as GE and others to divest and move away from this sector, though the profitability is highest. The typology of BPO needs attention while providing human resource recommendations.

2.11 Research methodology adopted for study

One of the objectives of the study is to develop an appropriate base for development of theory for social forecasting. For this purpose, Carlile and Christensen (2004) developed a model that can be effectively used for the present purpose. This model's objective is to provide a common language about research process that is likely to help research scholars of management to build on each other's work. The model given is a synthesis of works of Kuhn (1962), Campbell and Stanley (1963), Glaser and Strauss (1967) and Yin (1984) who have cumulatively build valid and reliable theory. The model described is a three-stage process by which researchers build theory, stage one consists of first lap that is descriptive and second lap is normative. The second stage is dedicated to discoveries of anomalies that play a role in building better theory, and describe how scholars can build theory whose validity can be verified. Finally, a suggestion is given for scholars on how to define research questions, execute projects, and design course work that leads to better theory building.

However, for the purpose of literature survey, the research has described the first stage. The model is a synthesis of models that are developed by different scholars.

The building of the descriptive theory is the preliminary stage. The next stage is to develop normative theory. In this stage the researcher observes, document describe and measure the phenomena in words and numbers as the subsequent researchers can build on the work. The base of the pyramid given in the figure represents this. Without insightful description, researchers are likely to build optimizing misleading concepts. Researchers develop abstractions from details of phenomena that are termed as “*constructs.*” Constructs help to understand and visualize the phenomena.

The next step is to classify the phenomena into categories. The constructs are defined by attributes of the phenomena. This descriptive categorization schemes are referred as “*frameworks or typologies.*” In the third step, researchers explore the association between the category-defining attributes and the outcomes observed. At this stage, researchers recognize and make explicit the differences in attributes, and the differences in the magnitude of attributes, correlate strongly with the pattern of outcomes of interest. The output of the study is known as “*model.*”

The author suggests that in the next stage of research from step one to step two the researcher have to find anomalies to improve upon the existing knowledge.

Figure 2.2 Research process undertaken for study.

Source: Adopted from Carlile, P.R., and Christensen, C.M. (2004), The Cycles of Theory Building in Management Research, Harvard Business School Working Paper.

Research Gap

Job attrition is a major human resources issue to be addressed by present research. Job satisfaction is a surrogate measure that affects the job attrition is identified as a major outcome that needs to be studied.

Job satisfaction is propositioned to be influenced by role scope, value priorities, and individualization with respect to work of BPO front line employees. Similarly, different sociodemographic variables are proposed to have an effect on the job satisfaction. Based on study social forecasting has to be performed from 2009-2014.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

Chapter Overview

This chapter started with addressing issue relating to theory borrowing of organizational studies especially from sociology. Subsequently, research methodology, hypotheses, research model, instrument design, sampling method, validity, and reliability are considered. The conceptual underpinnings and assumptions regarding job satisfaction are discussed. Hypothesized model is proposed and the limitations of the study are provided.

3.1 Research Methodology

The present research with social forecasting approach is undertaken in two paths. The social forecasting methodology prescribed two types of variables for study. One set of variables require study and another set of variables require intensive study relevant to the industry or organization. Thus economic, technological, demographic, and political forecasting is undertaken with the help of secondary data and while value priorities, job satisfaction, role scope and individualization of work are selected for intensive study with the help of primary data. However, to proceed with further discussion there is a need to justify theory borrowing from other disciplines and methodological aspects relating to theory borrowing especially relating to individualization. Next section addresses this topic.

3.2 Theory Borrowing in Organization Studies

The basic reason for borrowing a concept from other disciplines is organizational study itself lends to multidisciplinary investigation (Huff, 1999; Mowday, 1997). Organizations are comprised of individuals and knowledge about individual needs, identity, and personality, as well as judgmental biases and decision-making heuristics are relevant for studying organizational behaviour (Schneider, 1987). Organizations are embedded in larger environments, including organizational populations, sociopolitical contexts and cultures, and markets, and study of organizations is difficult without the aid of economic and sociological theory (Scott, 2001). The second reason for this approach for research is organizational and management research is often seen as an applied discipline (Zald, 1993; Boulding, 1958; Van de Ven, 2007). Whetten, Felin, and King (2009) suggest that borrowing theory can improve the quality of theory building.

3.2.1 Cross-level and Cross-Context Borrowing

There are two kinds of borrowing from theoretical concepts in Psychology and Sociology. They are vertical (cross-level) and horizontal (cross-context) borrowing.

Horizontal borrowing refers to borrowing concepts that are developed for the study of phenomena in other types of social contexts. This can be exemplified by acquiring insights from the social involvement literature in sociology (Davis *et al*, 2004) or market-related insights from economics (Zenger and Hesterly, 1997) and their usage in organizational research. *Vertical borrowing refers to borrowing concepts that were developed at various levels of analysis.* This can be exemplified by organizational learning, organizational decision making, or organizational identity. Agarwal and Hetker (2007) emphasized that borrowing concepts and theories has helped organizational studies to develop credibility as a legitimate form of social enquiry and it has fostered strong ties between the applied study of organizations and the core social science disciplines. Generally theories or concepts broadly fall into two categories; (a) paradigmatic theories are constituted as broad theoretical perspectives and they are used to explain a particular phenomenon, such as behavioral theory (March and Simon, 1958) and equity theory (Mowday, 1991) to explain differences in employee motivation and (b) propositional arguments involving the use of one concept to explain another concept, such as using level of environmental uncertainty (Lawrence and Lorsch, 1967) to explain the levels of integration and differentiation among organizational units and functions.

The present research borrowed individualization theory from sociology to explain differences in employee's discernment towards job satisfaction. It is a paradigmatic theory and corresponds to horizontal borrowing. From establishing the type of borrowing theory the next step is to move to a general standard to be adopted for borrowing. The standard governing borrowing theory is that the way in which a theory functions should be roughly equivalent in the new and old setting. In the case of paradigmatic theory, it is expected to visualize across settings, in the sense that the distinctive insights that have characterized a particular theory in its native level or context should hold true in the new setting.

That is, a concepts nomological network¹⁶ should not be altered significantly and it should be consistent across context and level. Present study borrowed the concept of individualization without any change in the nomological network. Furthermore, social forecasting is recognized as a management discipline and the approach is used for present research.

¹⁶ The nomological network was developed by Cronbach and Meehl (1955) as a part of American Psychological Association's efforts to develop standards for psychological testing. It means lawful network. Nomological network is developed to have construct validity. The network would include the theoretical framework for what the concept is trying to measure, an empirical framework for how it is measured, and specification of linkages among these frameworks (Trochim, 2006).

Figure 3.1 Research process adopted for the study

3.3 Research gap

The research gaps identified in the second chapter and elaborated in the following statements.

1. There is no data available with respect to social variables such as religion, social status, or place of origin of employees of BPO organizations.

2. There is no study undertaken to address the issue of individualization of work in Indian context.
3. There is no inventory with respect to design of instruments or administration of past studies for value priorities and individualization of work.
4. There are no empirical studies on job satisfaction and its relation to role scope, values priorities, and individualization of work.
5. There are no policy level guidelines for BPO industry with respect to labour practices available with the state.
6. At the methodological level, technological and economic models are only used to study industry growth and work force requirements.

3.4 Research Problem

Job attrition to the tune of forty percent, disillusionment with job tasks is some of the major challenges of BPO industry. Job attrition is related to job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is an outcome of an employee's engagement with organization. Varied factors such as social factors, demographic factors, value priorities, individualization of work and role scope are found to affect the job satisfaction of employees as per the

literature survey. There is a need to establish a relationship if any between these factors and job satisfaction.

3.5 Research Statement

The research statements are:

1. Identify the factors and they are on influencing job satisfaction of BPO employees.
2. Apply social forecasting as a methodological tool to address the issue of job attrition by developing an appropriate model.

3.6 Research Objectives

With the purpose of meeting the research gap, the following research objectives are devised.

1. Documentation and analysis of social, demographic, and educational aspects of business process outsourcing employees and find existence of any relationship with job satisfaction, role scope, value priorities, and individualization of work.

2. To analyze job satisfaction, role scope, values priorities, and individualization of work dimensions of BPO employees and delineate their interrelationship to design a human resources model.
3. Provide social forecasting (2009-2014) for BPO industry.

3.7 Hypotheses

In order to achieve the objectives of research, hypotheses are formulated for testing. The work area of respondents is not homogenous. There are nine major functional areas and twenty-six sub areas in the BPO industry in Chennai city. There are commonalities in their function such as technical interface by way of computer terminal with the help of voice and chat. However, there exists difference in content and remuneration for work. The following hypotheses are devised to test observations regarding gender, social class, and religion relationship with work area.

H₀₁: The gender of respondents and work area are independent.

H₀₂: The social class of respondents and work area are independent.

H₀₃: The religion of respondents and the work area are independent.

The second set of hypotheses are relating to the study variables and sociodemographic variables.

H₀₄: Job satisfaction groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.

H₀₅: Role scope groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.

H₀₆: Value priorities groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.

H₀₇: Individualization of work groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.

The third set of hypotheses is devised to test the relationship within study variables with the intention of developing a prototypical model for further testing.

H₀₈: Job satisfaction group and role scope group are independent.

H₀₉: Job satisfaction group and value priorities group are independent.

H₀₁₀: Job satisfaction group and individualization of work group are independent.

H₀₁₁: Value priorities group and role scope group are independent.

H₀₁₂: Individualization of work group and role scope group are independent.

H₀13: Value priorities group and individualization of work group are independent.

3.8 Research Design

The research design selected was cross sectional design based on descriptive methodology leading to conclusions. In the case of social forecasting methodology, exploratory research was undertaken. Secondary data is used for the purpose of forecasting technological, demographic, economic, and political phenomenon. For present study Carlile and Christensen Model (2004) for Theory Building in Management Research is used. The steps to be undertaken for implementation of the model are studied in chapter two¹⁷. The job satisfaction and related variables such as role scope, value priorities, and individualization are observed. Different abstractions are developed from the details of the phenomena by way of factor analysis and latent constructs are designated with appropriate nomenclature to help to understand and visualize the phenomena by adopting inductive process. The constructs are categorized to form typologies. For value priorities, the well-researched and widely accepted typology given by sociologists Zetterberg and Zetterberg (1997) is adopted and similarly for individualization the typology given by Storey and Bacon (1993) is

¹⁷ Ibid., p.90.

adopted. Based on the typologies associated model is designed and tested for goodness of fit.

3.9 Sources of Data

The data for the purpose of research has been collected both from secondary and primary sources. Data for social forecasting and its related topics are collected from the journal articles, research papers, newspaper reports, published theses and studies undertaken by different research groups. Primary data is collected from BPO organizations in Chennai city.

3.10 Instrument Development

The instrument for research consists of five segments; demographic data (including work area), job satisfaction, role scope, value priorities and individualization of work. The instrument is structured and undisguised.

Demographic data

Demographic data consists of items relating to age, gender, social status, religion, educational qualifications, place of origin, present salary, marital status, parents' (both mother and father) educational qualifications and occupation. The item relating to parents educational

qualifications and occupation is included instead of income of parents (in the pilot survey correct data could not be obtained). Social status consists of other castes or forward class, backward class, most backward class, scheduled caste, and schedule tribe as per norms of Tamilnadu government. The state to remove caste and religious barriers and to develop equitable development has segregated people based on castes and religion for reservation in education and employment. Forward class represent the highly developed followed by backward class, most backward class, scheduled castes, and scheduled tribes in that order. Similarly, Muslims a religious minority is also provided reservation in backward class. Place of origin consists of three classifications-urban including metropolitan, semi-urban and rural. Nine major functional areas and twenty-six sub areas of business process outsourcing industry are included for the study.

Job Satisfaction

As a first step, ten human resources managers are met and asked for content and suggesting two questionnaires with high reliability and validity. They suggested designing an instrument reflecting job satisfaction dimensions of BPO industry would be effective, as the

dimensions are different from that of the existing validated questionnaires.

Assumptions regarding BPO employees' satisfaction

There is a need to make certain a priori assumptions about BPO employee's job satisfaction based on literature and discussion with employees of BPO and HR managers. Certain degree of "*instrumentality*" regarding the employee's view of work, in the sense that work is regarded as a means to an end, and for this reason is *not a central life interest* within the call centre context (Hyman *et al.*, 2003). This assumption is reasonable in the sense no person's life ambition is to work in a call centre. The assumption is that an instrumental orientation towards work is now typical of those in low to moderately remunerated occupations such as BPO work as 34.2% of employees change jobs for salary hike as given by Dataquest-IDS Job Satisfaction Survey, 2007. It is probably more of a reflection of *supply for* and *demand of* labour within the local labour market (Gallie *et al.*, 1998). While BPO employees may prioritize salary, this may depend upon their '*definition of the situation*' at any given time. As Watson (2004) contended, "the employee acting to improve his or her pay packet is not likely to show much interest in job satisfaction at that point in time." However, once the individual returns to the work place the intrinsic satisfactions to be gained in that specific

context come as the crucial factor. Mumford (1972, 1991) stated that job satisfaction is largely concerned with a *fit* between what the organization *requires*, what the employee is *seeking*, and what the employee is *receiving*. This can take the form of both a rational- instrumental and an emotional-expressive evaluation of the cost and benefits pertaining to the effort or reward bargain. A refinement of the perspective offered by Baldamus (1961) and Locke (1976) in which satisfaction is '*the weighted sum of the discrepancies between how much of a certain valued aspect of working a job delivers and how much of this aspect the individual desires or expects*'. The deficit may be due, for instance, reluctance on the part of researchers to address some of the relevant sociological perspectives (Thompson and Warhurst, 1998). With this point of view, a common instrument of job satisfaction questionnaire has been prepared and distributed for discussion with human resources managers of BPO industry to reflect the present environment of BPO industry. The suggested list contained thirty-two items. However, seventeen of them are relating to salary or compensation. It has been decided to include only one dimension salary including prerequisites, as more number of items with respect to salary alone may cause difficulty as the nomenclature used by organizations are not the same for different components.

The human resources managers identified fourteen statements that are common to all the BPO organizations and agreed for the same.

Value Priorities

Value statements are identified from examination of literature survey. The instruments with respect to terminal values and instrumental values (Rokeach, 1973), the modifications (Schwartz and Bilsky, 1987, 1990) are examined in the context of BPO industry. Value statements relating to health, family are included considering Indian environment and BPO work culture. Fifty statements with respect to diverse types of values are identified and distributed to professor from Aligarh Muslim University, five human resources managers and two employees of BPO industry for content, layout, wording, and ease of comprehension of measurement items. Four statements that are ambiguous have been removed. Four statements that are duplicating the information in other statements are removed. Thirteen statements are converted to negation from positive sentences in order to obtain better responses. The statements are worded in such a fashion that they are in tune with the BPO work culture and considered for pilot testing. Likert type 1-5 point response scale has been used.

Analysis of Value Priorities

The primary representations in the form of answers are transformed to value types¹⁸. There are forty-two statements in value priorities and it is propositioned that they will fall into ten different value types. The value types are primarily based on Schwartz (1992) suggestion of motivational dimensional structure for value system adopted for Indian BPO organizational environment. The first dimension is conservation (focus on organization)-openness to change (focus on opportunity) continuum and the second is self-enhancement (focus on individual outcomes)-self-transcendence (focus on social context outcomes).

Figure 3.2 Representation of modified Value Types in two-dimensional space based on Schwartz Model.

¹⁸ Ibid., p.72.

The Schwartz Model in circular form and in present study it is represented in addition with quadrants with out any change in the nomological network.

The four quadrants are designed keeping in the view of the paradigmatic explanation of value types on individual-social context of outcomes continuum and opportunity- organization continuum dimensions. Schwartz's Model did not address the issue of health and family components of value system. The family security is considered as a component of security under focus of organization. Hence, Schwartz places it in quadrant of organizational outcome. This may be true from western values priorities context where there is social security system. However, in the case of Indian context, the individual value priorities are related to family and clan in the form of *extended family culture* (Hofstede, 1980a, 1980b) and in the opinion of the researcher should find place in individual context of outcome as there is no social security system available in India and an individual has to plan or depend for social security. Individual health as an important dimension evolved due to attrition rates relate to physical well being in BPO industry (Dataquest-IDS Job Satisfaction Survey, 2007) and Braithwaite and Law (1985) emphasized need for fitness value or health value to be included in the value type. Based on these suggestions health and family values is

included in the scheme of representation. The tradition and conformity are shown as separate segments in Schwartz's value types, however, specifying that they are adjacent and most similar. The next step is to aggregate the ten different values types in one single typology to describe the employee's value priorities, providentially such typology is given Zeterberg and Zeterberg (1997).

Three Dimensional Scaling of Value Types

The analysis of values using MDS is largely based on study of values by Bilsky and Koch (2000) 'on the content and structure of values: Universal or methodological artifacts?' The value questionnaire by Schwartz analysis is accomplished by means of nonmetric multidimensional scaling (Borg and Groenen, 1997; Shye, 1994). This analytic procedure has been successfully applied as a confirmatory approach of theory testing in a large number of studies, especially in the case of values structure, during the past two and a half decades (Elizur *et al*, 1991; Levy, 1990; Schwartz and Bilsky, 1987; Borg and Shye, 1995; Canter, 1985; Dancer, 1990; Guttman & Greenbaum, 1998).

It represents the empirical relations as correlations, between variables as distances in a low-dimensional space such that a closer relationship that is higher correlation corresponds to a smaller distance between the respective variable points.

On condition that there is a theory that suggests an a priori classification of items into conceptually homogeneous categories, there is a probability that, these variables form coherent regions when applying multidimensional scaling to empirical data. In other words, there is need to formulate theoretically grounded regional hypotheses about the structure of the variables under study. Shewartz while studying the value dimensions has done this extensively.

The empirical test of whether these hypotheses hold or not is carried out by inserting boundary lines according to the a priori classifications. Thus, boundaries are expected to clearly separate theoretically different variables from one another. While (nonrandom) enclosures of items in conceptually different regions violate the theoretical assumption of regional homogeneity, bends or curves of the boundaries are of no importance as long as partitioning of space follows some general rules specified by facet theory (Borg & Shye, 1995; Levy, 1985). It should be noted that regions are not necessarily clusters that can be identified by empty space around them. Rather, regional hypotheses are generally for a space that in principle has points everywhere. This assertion is important in the sense the three dimensional representation provides points in space. This means that some variables in one region

may correlate less with other variables of the same region than they do with variables from other regions” (Levy, 1985).

In other words, regional hypotheses relate to populations of items that can be distinguished from each other only on *conceptual grounds*. Consequently, when using multidimensional scaling in a confirmatory way, partitioning of space can only be achieved by referring to a theory-based a priori classification of items. Extensive research spanning fourteen countries in the world by Zeterberg and Zeterberg (1997) have lead to study of values and brought to existence of value graphics. While psychographics is extensively used in United States of America related to marketing research, value graphics remained predominantly European phenomena (Zeterberg, 1992). For the purpose of present research, value graphics methodology is adopted. The three dimensions are given in the pictorial form. The three dimensions are represented by stability- change to modernity continuum, fidelity-pragmatism continuum, and humanism - materialism continuum.

Figure 3.3 Representation of value types in three-dimensional space (Zeterberg and Zeterberg, 1997). (SOURCE: www.valuescope.com)

Sociologists suggested that society move from Gemeinschaft to Gesellschaft and may take different paths than that has been suggested. The three-dimensional view of values types' representation is given in the following diagram. Gemeinschaft is traditional stability, value fidelity, and humanism. Gesellschaft is change to modernity, pragmatism, and materialism.

Figure 3.4 Representation of value trajectory from Gemeinschaft to Gesellschaft. (Tönnies, Ferdinand. (1887). *Gemeinschaft und Gesellschaft*, Fues Verlag, Leipzig. www.valuescope.com)

Figure 3.5 Depiction of different value carriers according to relative position in the value dimensions. (Source: www.valuescope.com)

The value priorities are identified and analyzed through the three-dimensional scaling. The typologies (of western societies mostly of European origin: Austria, Australia, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Japan, The Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Spain, South Africa, and Sweden) described by Zeterberg and Zeterberg(1997) are used as there is no Indian counterparts are available. The division of the

population according to types depending on their high or low position on each of three dimensions is known as typology. There are eight types of values carriers identified. The typologies are; the upright; the folks; the matter of fact; the Belongers; the advocates; the zealous; the dare devils ; the minglers and centerites who do not form part of any groups. The detailed description is given in the appendix. They are given from point of view of marketing research; however, they may be adopted for the purpose present research. One major limitation of adoption is Valuescope (a tradename of ValueScope AB, Murarvägen 7 (2tr), S-168 33 Bromma, Sweden.) is proprietary, copyrighted, and independent verification may not be possible.

Role Scope

Role scope provides information on the scope offered by job to satisfy basic human needs of achievement, influence, control, extension, and affiliation. Organization role is likely to offer scope to achieve these dimensions. Higher motivation is likely for a person if higher role scope is offered. Twenty-five statements, five relating to each of the needs: achievement, affiliation, influence, control, and extension are adopted from instrument developed by Udai Pareek (1997) to measure role scope.

Individualization of work

There are no previous quantitative studies available on individualization of work. Therefore in addition to literature survey, working of five different BPO organizations are observed and ten employees are interviewed to understand their interpersonal interaction, their preferences in working, attitude towards willingness to go abroad for work, employment contracts, seeking recognition for decent work, etc. Sixty statements are developed and given to eminent professors of University of Padova, Italy and to three human resource managers for comments.

Thirty-six statements are considered for pilot testing questionnaire in the form of Likert scale has been used, with total disagreement anchored to one and total agreement anchored to 5. The three coordinates given by Storey and Bacon (1993) are procedural individualization that refers to removal of collective bargaining mechanism from determining terms and conditions of employment. Brown *et al.*, (1998) defines substantive individualization, which is the differentiation of individual employees, employment contracts like pay and non-pay terms and condition of employment that is individualization in human resources aspects of management strategy like nature of pay system or terms and

conditions. Functional individualization corresponds to how much autonomy is given to perform the job, type of supervision and accountability. In addition, there is a tendency to disembeddedness of work from traditional context of work to reembeddness to new and more variable context of global environment.

3.11 Suggested Research Model

The suggested research model is proposed based on the theoretical aspects enunciated in literature review and as given here.

Figure 3.6 Hypothesized Model for Job satisfaction of BPO employees

The latent variables for each of the study variables are to be identified by exploratory factor analysis. Job satisfaction is propositioned to be influenced by value priorities, role scope and individualization of work. The quantum and direction of relationships need to be established statistically and goodness-of-fit for the model is to be tested using logistic regression.

Pilot Testing

The questionnaire was tested among twenty-five respondents. Four statements in values and three statements in individualization are changed since they are not properly understood. Based on expert opinion, improvements were made in the total questionnaire with respect to clarity, readability, content enhancement and layout and the changes were incorporated.

Table: 3.1 Questionnaire structure

Description of parts in the Questionnaire	Number of items	Source
Demographic data	Thirteen items	Designed by researcher. Multiple choice type questions are used.
Job Satisfaction	Fourteen items	Designed by researcher with inputs from human resource managers.
Role scope	Twenty five items	Adopted from Udai Pareek (2005).
Value Priorities	Forty two items	Rokeach (1973) value Survey items are adopted and made suitable for BPO environment.
Individualization of work	Thirty six items	Designed by researcher with inputs from experts.
Total	One hundred and thirty items	

3.12 Validity and reliability of the instrument

Introduction

Construct validity refers to the logic of items which comprise measures of social concepts. It is the extent to which the content of the measurement scale appears to tap all relevant facets of construct it is attempting to measure. A good construct has a theoretical basis, which is translated through clear operational definitions involving measurable indicators. The concepts such as job satisfaction, role scope, values, and individualization of work are well established in theory.

Literature survey has been undertaken from research journals, articles, press releases, and web sites and papers are presented and published to ensure the construct validity. Experts from Aligarh Muslim University, University of Padova, Italy, and Professor from Anna University and from BPO organizations are consulted to ensure construct validity.

Table 3.2 Validation of Instruments used for research

Instrument	Validation
Job satisfaction	Validated by ten Human Resources Managers of BPO organization.
Role Scope	Validated by Sen (1982) by conducting survey among 500 employees of several banks in India using different tests and correlations.
Value Priorities	Primary validation has been done with the help of experts. While propounding theory of value structure Schwartz and Bitlsky suggested two dimensions. Conservation-Openness to change continuum and Self-enhancement-self-transcendence continuum for analysis of different value priorities. The multidimensional scaling results confirmed to the suggested framework and may be considered for validity.
Individualization of work	Validation has been done with the help of experts from Aligarh Muslim University, University of Padova, Italy and Anna University.

Convergent validity refers to “*the correlation among items which make up the scale or instrument measuring a construct.*” The constructs- job satisfaction, role scope; value priorities and individualization of work are correlated within their dimensions. The correlations within are higher indicating convergent validity. The correlation tables are provided in the fourth chapter¹⁹.

Discriminant validity

The second major type of construct validity refers to the principle that the indicators for different constructs should not be so highly correlated so as to lead one to conclude that they measure the same thing. In other words measures of constructs that theoretically should not be related to each other are, in fact, observed to not to be related to each

¹⁹ Ibid., p.138,153, 163.

other (that is, it should be able to discriminate between dissimilar constructs). This would happen if there were no definitional overlap between constructs. The constructs of role scope, individualization of work, value priorities, and job satisfaction are correlated and found to be having discriminant validity as given in the chapter four²⁰. The degree of practical distinctiveness depends on the absolute magnitudes of the correlations and the nature of components under examination (Bagozzi and Edwards, 1998). The average of all correlations is found to be lower indicating their distinctiveness.

Reliability

For reliability, Cronbach's alpha statistic is used (Cronbach and Meehl, 1955). Cronbach's alpha is a coefficient based on the average covariance among items in a scale. In the present research, assumption has been made that items on a scale are positively correlated with each other because all of the items are tapping into the same construct; that is, they are all measuring a common entity. The measure with .60 alpha was considered acceptable for exploratory purposes, .70 considered adequate for confirmatory purposes, and .80 considered good for confirmatory purposes. In this research, multi item scales are checked for reliability using reliability analysis with help of SPSS Version 10.

²⁰ Ibid., p.164.

The test also provides data on improvement of alpha value if any item is deleted. For this purpose the set of items are tested and appropriate changes are made.

Table 3.3 Reliability Scores for different testing instruments

Study Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Job satisfaction	.7529
Role scope	.8811
Value priorities	.8234
Individualization of work	.7476

The study used five tools and their Cronbach's Alpha is as given in the table. Since all the values are greater than .70, the reliability of instruments is assumed. Similarly, the items in each of the concepts-role scope, values, individualization of work and job satisfaction are correlated. The items showed elevated level of correlation indicating that they have convergent validity.

3.13 Sampling Procedure and Questionnaire Administration

Sampling procedure include identification of sample unit, sample frame, time of research, sample size determination, and sampling methodology.

Sample Unit

The sample unit consists of the front line employees of BPO who come in contact (voice or email or chat) with the customers directly. They are generally referred to as customer service representative, telephone sales or service representative, rep, associate, consultant, engineer, operator, technician, account executive, team member, customer service professional, staff member, attendant, specialist or in some firms as agent. The promotion to higher levels is considered from this level and approximately 85% of the employee strength in any BPO organization is from this level. For the purpose of research, employees with minimum of two years of experience only is considered, since dimensions of values and individualization are likely to be inculcated within that period, however, there is no empirical evidence for this assumption. The BPO space is operated by both Indian organizations and Multinational organizations catering to both Indian and International customer base. There are organizations employing more than three thousand employees such as Sutherland (during the period 2007-2008) and there is substantial number of smaller organizations having strength ranging between 50-100 employees. The employee numbers are not static and they are ramped up every month by 10%-15% by top operators. It is estimated that there are more than one lakh employees employed in the BPO sector and there are

eight thousand employees with a minimum experience of more than two years in Tamilnadu as per estimates of Information Secretary, Government of Tamilnadu.

Sample Frame

The sample frame consists of employees working in BPO organizations in Chennai having work experience of two years on the date of filling the questionnaire.

Time and Space

Field study is undertaken from November 2007 to December 2008. The research is done in Tamilnadu state and the firms are located in Chennai city. Most of the firms (65%) are established during the year 2003-2004 in Tamilnadu.

Sample Size Determination

In the proposed analysis, the data is predominantly nominal, categorical, and ordinal. Bartlett, Kotrlik, and Higgins (2001) suggested suitable sample size calculation for such data. For social sciences research, alpha level of 0.05 and the level of acceptable error at 5% are considered generally. The estimated standard deviation of the scale is 0.5.

Cochran's sample size formula for categorical data is:

$$\text{Sample Size (n)} = \frac{(t)^2 (p)^2 (q)^2}{(d)^2}$$

$$n = (1.96)^2 (.5)^2 (.5)^2 / (0.05)^2 = 384.$$

Where 1.96 gives t-value for selected value of alpha level of .025 in each tail. (The alpha level of .05 indicates the level of risk that the true margin of error may exceed the acceptable margin of error). Keeping in view, the estimates of Government of Tamilnadu that there are 8,000-9,000 employees with experience of more than two years in BPO sector , in order to increase the reliability of the study the sample size has been increased to four hundred and eighty to accommodate requirements of factor analysis of sample size to variables ratio of (10:1).

Sampling Methodology

The total number of BPO organizations in Chennai city is two hundred and twenty four. The sample units are stratified on the basis of number of employees employed during November, 2007. Nine organizations have more than 1000 employees followed by forty organizations having strength of 250 to 500, and seventy had employee strength of 50 to 100. The sample is distributed over these three classes in the order of 153, 237 and 90.

Similarly by inspection, organizations in functional area are also distributed among the samples. The list of employees of more than two years of work experience is obtained.

Data Coding

Eight hundred questionnaires were distributed and five thirty two responses were obtained. Thirty responses are rejected for inadequate data and improper filling. Twenty two respondents did not qualify for two years of service. Four hundred and eighty responses were taken for final analysis.

3.14 Tools and techniques used for data analysis

Data analysis starts with the profiling of samples. Descriptive statistics are used for various kinds of variables handled. Following statistical tools have been used to achieve the objectives of research. Each of the study variables contains latent variables and they identified using exploratory factor analysis. The latent variables are further aggregated using multidimensional scaling techniques to find typologies .The output is used for validation of the hypothesized model for goodness-of-fit using logistic regression.

Multidimensional Scaling

Job satisfaction and role scope manifest dimensions are analysed using multidimensional scaling. In addition, the output of factor-cluster approach is analysed with its help. Multidimensional scaling technique (Jones and Young, 1972; Carroll and Chang, 1970) offered several advantages over the more traditional sociometric techniques and interpersonal rating scales. The basis for the ratings comes from the participants and not from the researcher. Consequently, there is no introduction of bias on the part of the researcher in defining variables. Further, the salience of the participant's basis for decision-making is maintained. The Multidimensional scaling model is based on the premise that there exists an unspecified set, or number, of dimensions underlying the group members' perceptions-and hence their similarity ratings. Although the model assumes a certain kind of perceptual communality, it does allow for the measurement of considerable individual differences. In essence, the data result in dimensions that define an underlying psychological space common to all persons. Nevertheless, individuals may differ with respect to the importance, or salience, of the dimensions that define this common psychological or group stimulus space. This can be used to discover how many dimensions underlie the ratings by determining the amount of variance accounted for by one, two, three, or

more dimensions. The complexity of the group's perceptions can be judged by ascertaining the fewest number of dimensions that will account for the most variance. It will also yield a multidimensional picture of the composite similarity ratings and indicate where every member is seen to be in the stimulus space defined by the derived dimensions. This geometric representation is the group's underlying perceptual space. It indicates those aspects of the group (i.e., dimensions) that its members used in making their similarity judgments. It also indicates the interrelationships of the persons in the group. The group sees those persons, for example, who are clustered together with respect to certain dimensions as similar with respect to those characteristics. The tool has been used extensively in different disciplines especially in organizational studies and psychology and present research has adopted the same.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

In the present study, exploratory factor analysis methodology is adopted, as the scales are needed to be tested. The procedure given by Hair *et al.*, 2008 is adopted. The input data is in the form of statements termed as manifest variables with rating for each study variable- job satisfaction (14) role scope (25), value priorities (42), and individualization of work (36) is used. As a first step, correlations with in

manifest variables are examined and after sufficient satisfaction, that there is respectable number of correlations (approximately more than 70%) the next step is undertaken. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test of measuring sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of Sphericity results are obtained to test for suitability of factor analysis of data. Factors or latent variables with Eigen value greater than one are retained for further analysis. The scree plot is examined to confirm that Eigen values greater than one are representing given data. Factor loadings greater than .50 are considered as practically significant after varimax rotation. Latent variables are labeled according to theoretical interpretation.

Factor- Cluster Approach

Factor-analyzing original manifest variables to obtain latent variables and clustering their dimensions (k-means clustering) are used extensively in tourism research, especially for benefit segmentation. Haley (1968) reference is a methodological source for all studies and other researchers in marketing especially for by Goodrich (1980) and Calantone, Schewe and Allen (1980). Everitt, 1993 extensively explained its usefulness. Similarly, to study shopping attitudes, Mokhtarian, Ory, and Cao, 2007 used factor- cluster approach.

However, for the present study, factor –cluster analysis is appropriate as the latent variables dimensions may be tested for any clusters.

For the present research, the factor output is obtained and for each of the latent variables the individual scores are summated (Hair *et al.*, 2008) and are tested for any outliers as clustering algorithm is overly sensitive to outliers. The data is cluster analysed based on apriori selection of clusters. For the present research, three, four and five clusters are studied and appropriate number of clusters is arrived after examining the characteristics of clusters. The nomenclature of clusters is identified based on the characteristics of the groups given by cluster analysis. The output is further analysed using multidimensional scaling technique.

Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is applied in the present research to assess the hypothesized model's goodness-of-fit. It is used to predict a categorical (dichotomous) variable from a set of independent variables, which can be a combination of continuous or categorical variables. The predicted dependent variable is a function of the probability that a particular subject will be in one of the dichotomous categories given the set of scores in the predictor variables (Pampel, 2000).

The assumptions of multivariate normality, equal variance-covariance matrices across groups may not be met with respect to present data. However, logistic regression does not require these conditions and provides robust analysis (Demaris, 1995). In the present study, the job satisfaction is partitioned into low satisfaction group and high satisfaction group and subjected to logistic regression with study variables such as role scope, value priorities, individualization of work and respective interactions. Two ways are adopted to assess model estimation fit; the first is using pseudo R^2 values and the second is to examine the predictive accuracy. Though both the approaches examine model fit from different perspectives, they should yield comparable results for goodness-of-fit.

Model Estimation fit

Logistic regression measures model estimation fit with the value of -2 times log of the likelihood value referred to as $-2LL$ or $-2\log$ likelihood. The minimum value for $-2LL$ is zero which corresponds to perfect fit. The lower the value of $-2LL$ is better fit of the model. In the first step null model or baseline model is obtained with $-2LL$ value. Further, in the second step, the proposed model $-2LL$ is obtained and if there is a reduction in the $-2LL$ value and it is statistically significant using chi-square test, then it can be stated that the set of independent variables in the proposed model is significant in improving the model fit.

The sample size has to be 20:1 for obtaining appropriate decisions. The next stage consists of examination of pseudo R^2_{LOGIT} value measures, which ranges from zero to one with perfect model fit having a value of one. Cox and Snell and Nagelkerke developed different measures similar to pseudo R^2 measure and categorized as pseudo R^2 measures. Cox and Snell measure is similar to pseudo R^2 and higher the value higher the fit. However, it cannot reach value of 1.0. The Nagelkerke measure can achieve highest value up to 1.0.

Predicative Accuracy

Two approaches used in the present research for predictive accuracy classification matrix and chi-square based measures of fit (Hosmer and Lemeshow, 2000). Classification matrix measures how well group membership is predicted and developing a hit ratio and in the chapter four the calculations are provided. Hosmer and Lemeshow developed a classification test where the cases are divided into ten equal classes. The number of actual and predicted events is compared in each class with the chi-square statistic. This test provides a comprehensive measure of predictive accuracy that is based on actual prediction of the dependent variable. However, the measure is sample size sensitive and minimum of at least ten cases for each of the classes need to be ensured.

A convergence of these measures will provide the necessary support for the researcher in evaluating the overall model fit.

3.15 Limitations of Study

The methodology and findings of the present study should be interpreted with an acknowledgement of the following limitations. The study has been conducted in Chennai and the results may not be generalized for India. The definition that are provided for constructs are to be inferred only in the context of BPO industry. There is no study on value priorities and individualization of work available in India to make a comparison. Social forecasting is used for first time to address the issues of BPO industry. Economic, demographic, technological, and political forecasts are based on secondary data sources. The study does not include variables such as personality dimensions, performance levels of employees, intentions to stay with BPO industry, desire for higher studies, organizational culture, organizational policies, and procedures that are found to have an impact on job satisfaction. It is arguable that these factors may be more critical in job satisfaction than the value priorities, individualization of work and role scope of employees as proposed in the present research. At the broader societal level, it is also probable that cultural and other institutional arrangements will be expected to exert some influence.

While the inclusion of cultural, psychological, and broader societal factors might have enriched the content of the research model and explained a greater amount of the variance present, it might also have confounded the data analysis and interpretation of the results. While conducting the research, the researcher is aware of the problems posed by ecological fallacy. An ecological fallacy may be committed when the characteristics of groups are held to convey information about individuals within groups; or conversely when the characteristics of individuals are taken as equivalent to those of groups. Hofstede (1984, 2002) labels this latter phenomenon reverse ecological fallacy. In relation to values, Schwartz (1994) argues that reverse ecological fallacy occurs when researchers construct indices based on individual value measurements, without constructing culture-level analysis. The reliance on self-report data raises issues of the consistency motif (Neck *et al.*, 1999), which is defined as the urge of respondents to maintain a consistent line in a series of answers. The use of varimax rotation in exploratory factor analysis has given rise to providing higher number of latent constructs compared to other rotational methods is one of the limitations of methodology adopted, however, the other methods of rotation provided fewer constructs. Fu *et al.*, (2004) argued values are likely to be expressed in the form of behavioural intentions, which may differ from actual

behaviour. They maintain that in real-life, situational forces will exert greater pressure in forcing individuals to act in a spontaneous mode. A more objective measure of value priorities through observational studies or critical incident techniques would produce better results. Moreover, further research should consider examining the value profiles over time to obtain results that are more consistent. The social desirability of some responses is identified as one of the major limitations to the study. There is no agreement in the literature regarding the challenges posed by social desirability bias. While Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2002) argue that respondents to self-administered questionnaires are relatively unlikely to provide more socially desirable responses, Konrad and Linnehan (1995) disagreed, stating that there is pressure on respondents to present a socially desirable image of their organizations. In the present research there is likelihood of social desirability bias may be there as many BPO organizations urge employees to provide better feedback as it is being used as a marketing tool to attract employees.

Chapter 4: Analysis and Findings

Chapter Overview

Analysis and findings are presented in this chapter. The first section concerns analysis and testing of hypotheses regarding sociodemographic characteristics of sample. The study variables are analyzed using factor analysis, cluster analysis, and multi dimensional scaling and given in the section two to five. In the process, abstractions are developed from details of observed phenomena with identification of latent constructs with appropriate nomenclature. The constructs are formalized in the form of typologies. The sixth section related to establishing preliminary relationship within study variables with the help of statistical tools and testing hypotheses, to construct a prototypical model for further testing. The concluding section is devoted to rigorous testing of the model using logistic regression tool to identify vital predictors for job satisfaction model.

4.1 Sociodemographic Analysis

The data is relating to four hundred and eighty respondents working in different functional areas of BPO industry in Chennai. The respondents mean age is 25.8 years, with standard deviation of 3.64. This result indicates that the industry has youngest work force, with employees between 25-30 years age group contributing to 89.3% of workforce. Most of the employees are selected from campus interviews during the final

year of graduation or post graduation, based on aptitude test, language test consisting of oral, listening and writing and human resources interview. The youth of workforce is maintained by BPO organizations to create an easily trainable and flexible labour force. This is observed from the advertisements of BPO organizations aimed at fresh graduates only and they specify an upper age limit of 26 years (Remesh, 2004). The female contribution of work force is 42.1%, which is comparatively higher to that of other industries in India and lowest compared to global average. Majority of employees are single- 65.8 %, followed by married with 32.9%, and separated representing 1.3%. The religion of respondents - majority (69.2%) are Hindus while Christians and Muslims account for 15.8% and 9.6% respectively and the rest are from other religions. High percentage of Christians compared to their numerical strength is attributed to ability to speak English. There is less number of Muslims compared to their numerical strength.

Regarding social status, backward class contributes to the tune of 50.4%, followed by forward class with 27.5%. The lowest representation is for schedule castes and schedule tribes with 6.7% of the workforce. Absence of English language skills is sighted by human resources managers as one of the reasons for low representation from scheduled castes and schedule tribe categories.

Majority of the respondents (89.2%) are from urban and semi-urban areas signifying exceptionally low representation from rural areas with 10.8%. The fathers of majority of respondents (82.5%) have crossed primary education. The occupation of fathers of respondents is 87.9% employed, with 12.1% represented by farmers and other rural occupations.

Table 4.1 Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Characteristic (N=480)	Category	Number (%age)
Location	Chennai (Tamilnadu)	480 (100%)
Gender	Male	278(57.9%)
	Female	202 (42.1%)
Age (years) (Mean=25.87 years) (Median=25.00 years) (Standard Deviation=3.64)	21-25	262(54.5%)
	26-30	166(34.6%)
	31-35	44(9.2%)
	36-40	8(1.7%)
Social status	Other communities	132(27.5%)
	Backward communities	242(50.4%)
	Most Backward communities	74(15.4%)
	Scheduled castes/tribes	32(6.7%)
Religion	Hindu	332(69.2%)
	Muslim	46(9.6%)
	Christian	76(15.8%)
	Others**	26 (5.4%)
Origin	Urban	350(72.9%)
	Semi urban	78(16.3)
	Rural	52(10.8)
Educational qualification	BA	28(5.8%)
	BCom	60(12.5%)
	BBA/BBM	16(3.3%)
	BSC	80(16.7%)
	MSC	36(7.5%)
	MCA	52(10.8%)
	BE	122(25.4%)
	ME/MBA	62(13%)
Others	24(5%)	
Annual Income	< 2 lakhs	206(42.9%)
	2-3 lakhs	132(27.5%)
	3-4 lakhs	86(17.9%)
	4-5 lakhs	22(4.6%)
	5-6 lakhs	34(7.1%)

** including Jain, Buddhist, Sikh, and others.

The trends among mothers of respondents indicate that they are educated and 23.7% are employed. If education of parents is observed, majority of employees are from educated families consisting of middle class and lower middle class from cities. It appears that there is urban-rural divide in the employment of respondents. The poorer sections and rural sections of society are least represented. The workforce consists of engineers comprising of BE and ME (27.5 %) and postgraduates of other disciplines represent 29.1 %. Engineering and postgraduates combined group form the largest segment with 56.6 %; and graduates with 38.4%. This is a crucial point to be noted. Global research by Holman *et al.*, (2007) indicated that internationally only 22 % of the employees are having graduation, while Indian work force consists of postgraduates and graduates to the tune of 100% of workforce. Majority (42.9%) of the respondents are with income of 1-2 lakhs, followed by 2-3 lakhs constituting 27.5%. The salary levels at the entry levels are comparatively higher from that of other industries for similar qualified persons.

Table 4.2 Major Functional Areas of Respondents

S.No.	Major Functional Areas	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Finance and Accounting	20	4.2
2.	Sales and Marketing	32	6.6
3.	Human Resources	38	7.9
4.	Knowledge Services	46	9.6
5.	Consumer Service	114	23.8
6.	Support Technical	90	18.8
7.	Survey	38	7.9
8.	Research and Development	30	6.3
9.	Engineering	40	8.3
10.	Others	32	6.6
	Total	480	100.0

Table 4.3 Segments of Work Area of Respondents

Segments of Work Area	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Finance and accounting	20	4.2	4.2
Logistics and supply chain management	2	.4	4.6
Sales and Marketing	12	2.5	7.1
Human resources	38	7.9	15.0
Knowledge services	46	9.6	24.6
Customer care and help desk	12	2.5	27.1
Customer service	102	21.3	48.3
Technical support	54	11.3	59.6
.Product support	34	7.1	66.7
Pay role processing	2	.4	67.1
Voice out-bound sales campaigns	2	.4	67.5
Telemarketing	18	3.8	71.3
Surveys	38	7.9	79.2
Schedule changes	2	.4	79.6
Equity financial insurance research data search integration and management	4	.8	80.4
Research and information services in human resources	2	.4	80.8
Market research and competitive intelligence	4	.8	81.7
Engineering and design	40	8.3	90.0
Animation and simulation services	16	3.3	93.3
Para legal content and services	2	.4	93.8
Medical content and services	4	.8	94.6
Biotech and pharmaceuticals	6	1.3	95.8
Research and development	20	4.2	100.0

Inference

The samples represent nine major work areas and twenty-six segments derived from those work areas. As an example, sales and marketing is a broad classification under which other segments operate, such as telemarketing and market research and competitive intelligence. Diversified sampling is undertaken so that the characteristics of different work areas are reflected. However, the interactions and requirements of customers are not the same in different segments and require different skills on the part of employees, in the sense that not all interactions can be totally scripted by organizations and some leverage is given to employees.

Nonetheless, the consciousness about times that is possible to spend with the customer is regulated as it has been specified 190 seconds or 3 minutes and ten seconds²¹.

Table 4.4 Gender and Work Area Classification

Work Area	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Finance and Accounting	6	14	20
Sales and Marketing	14	18	32
Human Resources	10	28	38
Knowledge Services	36	10	46
Consumer Service	74	40	114
Support Technical	52	38	90
Survey	22	16	38
Research and Development	14	16	30
Engineering	32	8	40
Others	16	16	32
Total	278(57.9%)	202(42.1%)	480

Inference

The work area of BPO space is generally characterized as gendered work place with domination of female workers (Mirchandani, 2004). Indian BPO industry is an exception. However, there may be concentration of female workforce in certain areas such as consumer service. The following hypothesis is designed to find any dependency relationship between gender of respondents and work area.

²¹ Ibid., p.15.

H₀1: The gender of respondents and work area are independent.

H₁1: The gender of respondents and work area are dependent.

Chi-square test indicate (χ^2 (df = 9, N=480) =73.96, p=.000 at .05 significance level) rejection of null hypothesis and acceptance of alternate hypothesis. Thus, work areas seem to depend on gender. The female employees are more in the areas of finance and accounting, sales and marketing, human resources, research, and development while males are more in other areas of operations. There is a general perception that female employees represent consumer service more than male employees. The research indicates that in consumer service and support, males are more in number compared to that of female employees.

Table 4.5 Social Status and Work Area Classification

Work Area	Social Status			Total
	Other Community	Backward Community	Most Backward Community/SC/ST	
Finance and Accounting	4	12	4	20
Sales and Marketing	4	22	6	32
Human Resources	8	26	4	38
Knowledge Services	6	30	10	46
Consumer Service	56	30	28	114
Support Technical	26	48	16	90
Survey	14	20	4	38
Research & Development	2	16	12	30
Engineering	8	18	14	40
Others	4	20	8	32
Total	132(27.5%)	242(50.4%)	106(22.1%)	480

Inference

Social groups are classified as other communities, backward class, and most backward class (consisting of schedule caste and schedule tribes) as per government of Tamilnadu norms and cross-tabulated with work area.

H₀2: The social class of respondents and work area are independent.

H₁2: The social class of respondents and work area are dependent.

The chi-square test indicate (χ^2 (df = 18, N=480) = 35.385, p<.05 at .05 significance level) that the null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. There is a significant dependence of social class and work area. This is explainable, as even with positive ascription that is job reservation for most backward classes, scheduled castes and scheduled tribes in government services, their representation is low. Private sector with no obligation to reserve jobs, there is likely to be dwindling numbers. However, backward classes utilized the reservation in educational sectors and equipped with sufficient social capital are in a position to represent 50.4%. Similar model may be employed for other sections for better representation.

Table 4.6 Religion and Work Area Classification

Religion	Finance & Accounts	Sales & MKT	HR	Knowledge Services	Consumer Services	Support	Survey	R & D	Engg.	Others	Total
Hindu	14	24	22	36	80	66	20	20	32	18	332
Muslim	0	2	6	8	8	6	6	4	0	6	46
Christian	4	4	10	2	18	14	10	2	8	8	80
Others	2	2		0	8	4	2	4	0	0	22
Total	20	32	38	46	114	90	38	30	40	32	480

(Note: Five cells have zero scores and the results are to be interpreted accordingly)

Inference

The religion of respondents consist of Hindus, Muslims, Christians (others are consisting of Jains, Buddhists, and other religions) and area of work cross-tabulated. It is observed that Hindus form majority with 69.2%, 16.7% are Christians, and 9.6% are Muslims. The following hypotheses are devised to test the relationship of work area and religion.

H₀3: The religion of respondents and the work area are independent.

H₁3: The religion of respondents and the work area are dependent.

The chi- square test indicate (χ^2 (df = 27, N=480) = 172.90, p<.05) at .05 of significance level, thus null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. The religion and work area are dependent. English speaking language skills and social capital in the form of networks is one of the reasons for more number of Christian representation in BPO. However, Muslim representation is low compared to the numerical population need to be addressed.

4.2 Analysis of Study Variables

The study variables identified are job satisfaction, role scope, value priorities, and individualization of work. They will be analyzed in that order. Job satisfaction is an outcome, and it is influenced by varied factors. Each variable is analysed followed by cross tabulation of data with respect to different sociodemographic variables.

4.2.1 Analysis of Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is measured along fourteen dimensions. The respondents are asked to represent their satisfaction with totally satisfied getting highest score of five and highly dissatisfied getting the lowest score of one.

The descriptive statistics are computed with respect to each dimension of job satisfaction. The reliability of the instrument is given by Cronbach Alpha = .7529 indicating good reliability of the instrument.

Table 4.7 Descriptive Statistics of Job Satisfaction Dimensions

Dimensions of Job Satisfaction	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Salary	3.0500	1.2009	-.184	-.783
Timing of work	3.2292	1.1638	-.215	-.677
Changes in Job	2.9125	1.1580	-.201	-.691
Night travel	2.8375	1.3347	.120	-.315
Shift system	3.0333	1.2625	-.275	-.980
Opportunities to learn	3.4083	1.2629	-.417	-.765
Opportunities to go abroad	2.9583	1.3393	.076	-.368
Benching	3.0333	1.2458	.093	.147
Support of family	3.6792	1.1564	-.571	-.508
Opportunity to use knowledge	3.6167	1.1464	-.564	-.412
Work environment	3.7125	1.1214	-.736	-.117
Interpersonal relations with colleagues	3.8708	1.0479	-.898	.365
Western performance culture at work place	3.4250	1.1278	-.453	-.392
Immediate supervisor's/team leader's role in motivating you	3.7542	1.1568	-.664	-.382

Figure 4.1 Scores of Job Satisfaction Dimensions

Inference

It is observed that the mean values are all greater than 2.5 (the middle most value as the scale is 1-5 scale, lower than 2.5 indicate dissatisfaction) which indicate that all scores are above 2.5. However, negative skewness for majority of items indicates that the values are skewed towards lower values than higher values. The low standard deviation values indicate that the variations in responses are minimum. Satisfaction is highest with respect to interpersonal relations with colleagues, immediate supervisor's/team leaders role in motivating the employees, work environment, opportunity to use knowledge and support of family. Moderate satisfaction is expressed with respect to western culture at work place and opportunities to learn. Other dimensions are low satisfiers.

4.2.2 Cluster Analysis - Job Satisfaction

To facilitate further understanding of job satisfaction, there is a need to find if there are any commonalities among respondents with similar characteristics so that they can be grouped together based on quantitative approach. K-Means clustering is a tool that partitions data into specified number of groups (wherein, the number of groups created has to be suggested by the researcher) .The clusters of three, four and five groups are obtained and studied.

Three groups represented the following characteristics. The first group has uniformly lower values compared to other two groups. However, in the case of opportunities to go abroad, benching, opportunities use knowledge and immediate supervisor's role in motivation they expressed better satisfaction than the second group. Respondents in first group represent 37.5%, second group with 26.9% and third group with 35.6% of the sample.

Table 4.8 Descriptive Statistics of Job Satisfaction Groups

Job satisfaction dimensions	Job satisfaction groups		
	n=180 (37.5%)	n=129 (26.9%)	n=171 (35.6%)
Salary	2.60	2.65	3.82
Timing of work	2.70	3.21	3.80
Changes in Job	2.39	3.09	3.33
Night travel	2.13	3.52	3.06
Shift system	2.24	3.75	3.32
Opportunities to learn	2.96	3.09	4.13
Opportunities to go aboard	2.96	1.73	3.89
Benching	3.11	2.34	3.47
Support of family	2.92	3.78	4.40
Opportunity to use knowledge	3.23	3.10	4.41
Work environment	3.01	3.71	4.46
Interpersonal relations with colleagues	3.41	3.72	4.47
Western culture at work place	3.06	3.11	4.05
Immediate supervisor's/Team leader's role in motivating you	3.47	3.27	4.42

Figure 4.2 Scores of Job Satisfaction Groups

Since not all values are uniformly in low, medium, or high values, to obtain summary data the values are normalized through conversion to Z values (Valverde,Ryan,n, and Gorjup, 2007). As it is observed in the total column, the aggregate values are low, moderate, and high. Based on the observation the groups are named as low satisfied, moderately satisfied, and highly satisfied. However, as low, and moderate satisfaction is in the negative aggregation of Z values, they may be considered as one group for appropriate analysis.

Table 4.9 Z-Values for Dimensions of Job Satisfaction

Dimensions of Job Satisfaction	Low	Moderate	High
Salary	-0.3747176	-0.33211	0.644982
Timing of work	-0.4546818	-0.017	0.491489
Changes in Job	-0.4521673	0.149198	0.363413
Night travel	-0.5275772	0.510879	0.169944
Shift system	-0.6248684	0.569197	0.228362
Opportunities to learn	-0.3585219	-0.25581	0.57037
Opportunities to go aboard	-0.0021	-0.91814	0.694819
Benching	0.0624	-0.55565	0.353456
Support of family	-0.6545474	0.0897	0.621299
Opportunity to use knowledge	-0.3343936	-0.45003	0.691488
Work environment	-0.6254768	-0.0063	0.663155
Interpersonal relations with colleagues	-0.4387063	-0.14305	0.569711
Western culture at work place	-0.3275679	-0.2806	0.55649
Immediate supervisor's/Team leader's role in motivating you	-0.2485303	-0.4174	0.576492
Total	-5.3614565	-2.05712	7.195469

For better insights into data, various dimensions of job satisfaction are analyzed using multidimensional scaling technique, to be represented in two dimensions in qualitative approach. The purpose is to find the dimensions that can be combined together to find underlying human resources needs. Young's S-stress formula one is used to obtain stress and squared correlation (RSQ) in distances for two-dimensional representations. RSQ values are the proportion of variance of the scaled data in the partition (row, matrix, or entire data) which is accounted for by their corresponding distances. Stress values are Kruskal's stress for matrix is given by $\text{Stress} = 0.13782$, $\text{RSQ} = 0.91568$ indicating low stress and high correlation values for better representation. There are three groups that can be identified among job satisfaction dimensions. An observation of the output indicate that the X-axis is more representative of *expressive cycle* and Y-axis is more representative of *instrumental cycle*²² dimensions of job satisfaction.

²² *ibid.*, p.87.

Two Dimensional Scale

Job Satisfaction

Figure 4.3 Two Dimensional Model of Job Satisfaction

(Note: For visual clarity, codes have been used. The serial numbers for job satisfaction are attached with alphabet 's.')

Expressive cycle represent the urge to share thoughts, knowledge and information giving rise to creative expression of self, where in people return to tasks with more energy, to keep the performance cycle move on. On the other hand, instrumentation cycle is more related to tangible outcomes of performance of job. Salary is one of the major components of this cycle. The first group representing s2, s3, s4 and s5 (timing of work, changes in job, night travel and shift system) relate to the logistics to be undertaken to perform job effectively and efficiently. None of these activities can be avoided.

However, they can be made as less painful as possible. The second group- s6, s9, s10, s11, s12 and s14 (opportunities to learn, support of family, opportunity to use knowledge, work environment, interpersonal relations with colleagues and immediate supervisor's/team leaders role in motivating employees) relate to the social and emotional dimension of job satisfaction. The third group- s1, s7, s8 and s13 (salary, opportunities to go abroad, benching, and western performance culture at work place) indicate instrumental nature of rewards. Furthermore, in order to test the dependence of job satisfaction on socio demographic variables, the following hypothesis is devised for testing.

H₀4: Job satisfaction groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.

H₁4: Job satisfaction groups are dependent of sociodemographic variables.

Table 4.10 Cross Tabulation of Job satisfaction Groups with Sociodemographic Variables

Characteristic	Category	Job Satisfaction Groups			Chi-Square Test*
		Low 180(37.5%)	Moderate 129(26.8%)	High 171(35.7%)	
Gender	Male	110(39.6%)	67(24.1%)	101(36.3%)	$\chi^2_{(df=2, N=480)} = 2.74,$ $p > .05,$ not significant
	Female	70(34.7%)	62(30.6%)	70(34.7%)	
Social Status	OC	40(30.3%)	41(31.1%)	51(38%)	$\chi^2_{(df=6, N=480)} = 14.23,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	BC	104(43%)	54(22.3%)	84(34.7%)	
	MBC	26(35.1)	20(27.1)	28(37.8)	
	SC/ST	10(31.3)	14(43.7)	8(25%)	
Religion	Hindu	124(37.3%)	73(22%)	135(40.7)	$\chi^2_{(df=6, N=480)} = 32.88,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	Muslim	18(39.1%)	22(47.8%)	6(13.1)	
	Christian	24(31.6)	28(36.8%)	24(31.6)	
	Others*	14(53.8)	6(23.1)	6(23.1)	
Educational Qualification	BA	10(35.7)	8(28.6)	10(35.7)	$\chi^2_{(df=16, N=480)} = 30.80,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	BCom	28(46.7)	20(33.3)	12(20%)	
	BBA/BBM	8(50%)	2(12.5%)	6(37.5%)	
	BSC	28(35%)	23(28.8%)	29(36.2%)	
	MSC	16(44.4%)	10(27.8%)	10(27.8%)	
	MCA	12(23.1%)	14(26.9%)	26(50%)	
	BE	46(37.7%)	30(24.6%)	46(37.7%)	
	ME/MBA	30(48.3%)	12(19.3)	20(32.2)	
Others	2(8.3%)	10(41.7%)	12(50%)		
Origin	Urban	114(32.6%)	95(27.1%)	141(40.3%)	$\chi^2_{(df=4, N=480)} = 22.75,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	S.Urban	34(43.6%)	26(33.3%)	18(23.1%)	
	Rural	32(61.5%)	8(15.4%)	12(23.1%)	
Annual Income	1-2	90(43.7%)	57(27.7)	59(28.6%)	$\chi^2_{(df=8, N=480)} = 22.7,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	2-3	40(30.3%)	38(28.8%)	54(40.9%)	
	3-4	28(32.6%)	26(30.2%)	32(37.2%)	
	4-5	5(22.7%)	5(22.7%)	12(54.6%)	
	5-6	12(35.3%)	8(23.5%)	14(41.2%)	

** including Jain, Buddhist, Sikh, and others.

Inference

The test output indicates that gender is not statistically significant with respect to job satisfaction groups. The reason may be that there is no gender discrimination with respect to service conditions and other related areas. Backward community, most backward community and schedule caste and schedule tribe respondents compared to other communities, expresses lower satisfaction.

Minorities expressed higher dissatisfaction compared to other religious groups. MCA, BE and BBA respondents reported higher satisfaction than others. Urban respondents are more satisfied than the semi urban and rural respondents. Higher income has an increasing effect on job satisfaction.

Table 4.11 Chi-Square Tests for Job Satisfaction Dimensions with Social Variables

Dimensions of Job Satisfaction	Gender		Social Status		Religion		Place of origin	
	χ^2 -value	p-value						
Salary	2.93	.568	15.81	.466	23.72	.255	15.28	.054
Timing of work	10.49	.033*	31.54	.001*	60.75	.000*	20.15	.010*
Changes in Job	17.68	.001*	38.88	.000*	48.11	.000*	20.78	.008*
Night travel	2.98	.590	54.85	.000*	28.74	.275	18.46	.048*
Shift system	5.33	.255	18.17	.314	42.34	.002*	12.72	.122
Opportunities to learn	4.93	.294	29.82	.019*	44.34	.001*	22.91	.007*
Opportunities to go aboard	15.73	.008*	29.36	.081	52.52	.000*	16.23	.093
Benching	7.53	.184	58.43	.000*	4.04	.000*	29.80	.001*
Support of family	16.46	.006*	44.75	.000*	77.68	.000*	27.12	.001*
Opportunity to use knowledge	11.20	.024*	44.73	.000*	53.18	.000*	11.61	.170
Work environment	2.86	.582	61.60	.000*	42.91	.002*	26.56	.001*
Interpersonal relations with colleagues	.612	.962	45.13	.000*	37.99	.009*	15.79	.045*
Western culture at work place	7.74	.102	23.45	.107	41.82	.003*	35.65	.000*
Immediate supervisor's/Team leader's role in motivating you.	2.93	.570	22.82	.119	31.30	.051	5.27	.728

* indicate significant at .05 level.

Inference

The output indicate that timing of work, changes in job, opportunities to go abroad, support of family and opportunity to use knowledge are significant with respect to gender. The expressive cycle components such as support of family and opportunities to use knowledge are significant

across different social variables. Social status is significant across dimensions except western culture at work place and immediate supervisor's role in motivating.

4.3 Analysis of Role Scope

The basic human motivational needs are achievement, influence, control, extension, and affiliation. Though every person has all the needs, some may have some needs more than others may. In organizational setting, these needs are tried to be satisfied through organizational roles. In this sense, role scope is *“the opportunity given by the organizational role to satisfy the basic human needs such as achievement, influence, control, affiliation, and extension as perceived by an individual.”* The role scope is measured through an instrument using a five point scaling technique, with highest score anchored to five which means great deal of opportunity and lowest anchored to 1 which means absence of opportunity, concerning 25 items. Each of it represents a motivational dimension. The data is subjected to factor analysis with an objective of data reduction and for identification of latent variables. Correlation matrix of 25 items reveals that 268 correlations out of 325 correlations are significant at the .01 level indicating items suitability for factor analysis. Bartlett's Test for Sphericity, chi-square measure ($\chi^2_{(df=300, N=480)} = 4146.669, p=.000$) authenticated that there is sufficient common

variance in the factors. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of sampling adequacy indicated (value= 0.848 that is greater than .5 point out that the results of factor analysis will be effective. The scree plot also showed six factors could be considered for further analysis as no much value addition after sixth factor. Factor analysis is performed with Eigen values more than one with Varimax rotation. The communalities are greater than .50 for the variables pointing out that the data is suitable for further analysis. Six factors are obtained that explained 57.746% of total variation in the data. The overall reliability measure for the items in role scope is given by Cronbach Alpha= .8811. Factor loading greater than .4 is selected for each factor; each of the factors with corresponding factor loadings is selected for appropriate nomenclature. The selection of name for each of the factors is based on theoretical basis.

Figure 4.4 Scree Plot for Factor Analysis of Role Scope

The scree plot indicates that after the sixth factor there is no much value addition by including factors. Therefore, the process was stopped at sixth factor.

Table 4.12 Total Variance Explained for Different Components of Role Scope

Component	Initial Eigenvalues	Percentage of Variance	cumulative	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared loadings		
				Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.946	27.785	27.785	6.946	27.785	27.785	2.975	11.898	11.898
2	2.366	9.462	37.247	2.366	9.462	37.247	2.743	10.971	22.870
3	1.458	5.831	43.078	1.458	5.831	43.078	2.612	10.448	33.318
4	1.266	5.063	48.141	1.266	5.063	48.141	2.503	10.013	43.331
5	1.220	4.878	53.020	1.220	4.878	53.020	1.853	7.411	50.742
6	1.182	4.727	57.746	1.182	4.727	57.746	1.751	7.005	57.746

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis with Eigen values greater than one.

Table 4.13 Role Scope Dimensions Identified through Factor Analysis

Factor Loading	Factors	Motivational Dimension	Factor Name	Cronbach Alpha	Eigen Value	Percentage of variance
.701 .516 .706 .737 .740 .619	Factor 1 Develop close personal relations Develop your junior colleagues or subordinates Set standards of excellence Cooperate with others in a common task Interact with colleagues Work in teams	Affiliation Extension Achievement Extension Affiliation Extension	People orientation	.7847	6.946	27.785
.927 .546 .715 .609	Factor 2 Give ideas or suggestions to your superiors Make contributions to significant decisions Get regular reports from other sections or subordinates Interact with others on new task matters	Influence Influence Control Affiliation	Expansion of influence	.6849	2.366	9.462
.722 .676 .659	Factor 3 Work with friendly people Do something useful for others Stretch your abilities and skills	Affiliation Extension Achievement	Stretch	.6837	1.458	5.831
.700 .875 .635 .720	Factor 4 Admonish (punish) those who do not conform Direct and instruct people below you Control the people below you Admonish (punish) those who do not perform	Control Control Control Control	Strict conformity	.6884	1.266	5.063
.744 .682	Factor 5 Share feelings and emotions with others Help others	Affiliation Extension	Emotional coping	.6406	1.220	4.878
.761 .538	Factor 6 Do something challenging and worthwhile Influence or make an impact on others	Achievement Influence	Visibility	.4856	1.182	4.727

Extraction Method: Principle Component Analysis
Six factors extracted. Total variance explained = 57.75 %.

4.3.1 Nomenclature for Role Scope Dimensions

The explanations for each of the dimensions are based on theoretical considerations and task environment of BPO employees. The motivational dimensions- affiliation, extension, and control each represented by five items and achievement and influence has a score of three. The tasks are highly structured and the employee is expected to

perform interaction with customer with least deviation to achieve higher call numbers. The emphasis on timing of calls and adherence to norms is pointed in the dimension *strict conformity*.

In the process of interaction with customer, he or she is also expected to create a publicly facial or bodily or display in voice warmth and caring, even if the actual emotions are not in tune with that behaviour-giving rise to emotional exhaustion (Witt, Andrews and Carlson, 2004). Though the work process is centered on the employee with no interdependence of tasks, it is expected to cope with customer abuse, racial comments, and work intensity. In this situation ‘survival strategy,’ in the form of forming communities of coping is suggested. The *emotional coping* and stretch are the dimensions that address the issue of emotional exhaustion. *Expansion of influence* in the form of creative suggestions and ideas to others is expected. Though the tasks are highly structured, they do not exhaust all the possible answers to the customers. Sharing of ideas and thoughts is one of the ways used by employees to enhance their performance and they expect this must be recognized by management in the form of *visibility* dimension. The factor analysis helped to identify latent variables. However, there is a need to understand how employees differ in the intensity of having these dimensions. Therefore, there is a need to find any groups among employees and their characteristics.

Table 4.14 Descriptive Statistics of Role Scope Dimensions

Dimensions of Role Scope	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
People Orientation	2.92	.6847	-.133	-.804
Expansion of Influence	3.23	.8529	-.132	-.530
Stretch	3.62	.848	-.397	-.348
strict conformity	3.579	1.028	.113	-.256
Emotional Coping	1.6021	.5984	-.267	-.826
Visibility	3.1396	.9812	-.135	-.593

Figure 4.5 Scores of Role scope dimensions

4.3.2 Definitions of Dimensions of Role Scope

The following definitions are obtained reflecting the BPO employee's role scope.

1. **People orientation:** *Preference for and positive tendency towards colleagues by building team spirit and setting lofty standards of excellence.*

2. **Expansion of influence:** *Contribution to decision making by providing creative inputs and interacting with colleagues in task and non-task issues.*
3. **Stretch:** *Helping and being friendly with others often as far as possible by reaching beyond what is expected, by using abilities and skills.*
4. **Strict conformity:** *Correcting self as well as others to follow norms and usual standards that are expected by group or organization without any deviation.*
5. **Emotional coping:** *Dealing with and pain of workplace situations and way of getting through the day.*
6. **Visibility:** *Setting challenging goals and making an impact on others.*

4.3.3 Cluster analysis - Role Scope

With the purpose of understanding the role scope, further analysis is undertaken to identify existence of groups and factor analysis results are used. The factors identified (six in number) are represented by individual factor loadings. These factor loadings are additive and the variables scores are summated (Hair *et al.*, 2008). The output is considered for K-means clustering analysis.

Table 4.15 Descriptive Statistics of Role Scope Groups

Dimensions of Role Scope	Role scope groups		
	Low n=192 (40%)	Moderate n= 172 (35.8%)	High n=116 (24.2%)
People orientation	2.24	3.21	3.59
Expansion of Influence	2.65	3.31	4.04
Stretch	3.01	3.91	4.17
Strict conformity	3.25	3.1	4.82
Emotional coping	1.42	1.68	1.77
Visibility	2.74	3.1	3.85

Figure 4.6 Scores of Role Scope Groups

K-Means Clustering provided three groups with each factor and their scores. The mean values for each of the factors are in increasing order from first cluster to the third cluster. Therefore, the clusters may be labelled as low, medium, and high based on mean values. Most of the employees are having low role scope (40%), followed by medium role scope (35.8%), and prominent role scope (24.2%).

Literature survey also supports this view that the task performance in BPO industry provides fewer chances for role scope due to technological intensity and with less interdependence of tasks among the employees.

Table 4.16 Inter Correlation Coefficients ^a of Role Scope Dimensions

	Mean*	SD*	People orientation	Expansion of influence	Stretch	Strict conformity	Emotional coping	Visibility
People Orientation	2.92	.685	1					
Expansion of Influence	3.23	.853	.531**	1				
Stretch	3.62	.846	.556**	.349**	1			
Strict conformity	3.578	1.035	.370**	.311**	.185**	1		
Emotional Coping	1.602	.595	.234**	.209**	.163**	.175**	1	
Visibility	3.139	.98	.375**	.339**	.290**	.306**	.161**	1

* Average of summated scale from factor analysis. (Hair *et al.*, 2008)

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

^a Small effect ($.1 < r < .3$), medium effect ($.3 < r < .5$), large effect ($r > .5$) Cohen, 1988.

The correlations are significant at .01 level for all dimensions indicating good convergent validity. However, not high values of correlation coefficients indicate that the items are distinctive. People orientation has large effect correlation coefficients with expansion of influence and stretch and medium effect correlation coefficients with visibility and strict conformity. The results indicate the high extension orientation in role scope. Further analysis is needed to have better insights into this aspect.

Two Dimensional Scale

Figure 4.7 Two Dimensional Model of Role Scope

Young's S-stress formula 1 is used to obtain stress and squared correlation (RSQ) in distances for two-dimensional representation. RSQ values are the proportion of variance of the scaled data (disparities) in the partition (row, matrix, or entire data) which is accounted for by their corresponding distances. Kruskal's stress for matrix is given by $\text{Stress} = 0.01113$, $\text{RSQ} = 0.99937$ indicating low stress and high correlation values indicating better representation.

The important dimensions of role scope- people orientation occupy the parallel position to that of strict conformity. While strict conformity is task oriented behaviour, people orientation is directed towards human aspects of task performance.

Expansion of influence and stretch occupy the middle most position in between people orientation and strict conformity. This indicates the appropriate alignment of three dimensions. In other words, people orientation and strict conformity are balanced by expansion of influence and stretch in the process satisfying the motivational needs of control, influence, and extension. Emotional coping represents the other parallel from people orientation. Emotional coping is a necessary factor as discussed with respect to work of Korczynski (2003). The task environment is characterised by elevated level of emotional labour (Hochschild, 1983). It involves managing emotions, irrespective of the emotions that are shown by customers²³. If the emotions are not in tune with the internal emotions of the employee; then the employee feel stress. Thus, the axis is named as emotional and social orientation of role scope. The middle positions are occupied by stretch and visibility. The stretch dimension is to go beyond the work norms to help others. This is to satisfy the motivational need of extension. If an employee performs beyond expectations, he expects visibility of his achievements. The inference explains the theoretical basis of role scope. However, the paradox of total independent tasks performed by employee and the high emotional and people orientation of role scope is yet to be addressed.

²³ Ibid., p.9.

Due to novelty of business processes, operations pertaining to different country with different culture and isolation from social environment, the social space of the employee are restricted to that of the organization. The work geography ²⁴ that is difference between role at employment and home is changed. These circumstances of employment combined with anxiety of performance norms leads to the employee being motivated to be more people oriented. This proposition provides an explanation why the employees spend time after official times in lounges, cafeteria, and other places. This also makes the employee think that this is western culture as he or she is unaware of the western culture, other than the accent and few cultural aspects that are necessary for mimicking the client culture, by camouflaging their identity. The team spirit ²⁵ given in definition of people orientation is not the same as perceived in the general sense, but has specific meaning with respect to BPO work as discussed.

Furthermore, to test the dependence of role scope on different sociodemographic variables the following hypothesis is devised for testing.

H₀5: Role scope groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.

H₁5: Role scope groups are dependent of sociodemographic variables.

²⁴ Ibid., p. 81.

²⁵ Ibid., p.59.

Table 4.17 Cross Tabulation of Role Scope Groups with Sociodemographic Variables

Characteristic	Category	Role Scope Groups			Chi-Square Test *
		Low 192(40%)	Moderate 172(35.8%)	High 116(24.2%)	
Gender	Male	100(36%)	104(37.4%)	74(26.6%)	$\chi^2_{(df=2, N=480)} = 4.78,$ $p > .05,$ not significant
	Female	92(45.5%)	68(33.7%)	42(20.8%)	
Social Status	OC	46(34.9%)	44(33.3%)	42(31.8%)	$\chi^2_{(df=6, N=480)} =$ 11.68, $p > .05,$ not significant
	BC	104(43%)	86(35.5%)	52(21.5%)	
	MBC	32(43.2%)	28(37.8%)	14(19%)	
	SC/ST	10(31.2%)	14(43.8%)	8(25%)	
Religion	Hindu	132(39.7%)	116(35%)	84(25.3%)	$\chi^2_{(df=6, N=480)} = 14.96,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	Muslim	24(52.2%)	14(30.4%)	8(17.4%)	
	Christian	28(36.8%)	28(36.8%)	20(26.4%)	
	Others**	8(30.8%)	14(53.8%)	4(15.4%)	
Educational Qualification	BA	6(21.4%)	10(35.7%)	12(42.9%)	$\chi^2_{(df=16, N=480)} =$ 65.38, $p < .05,$ significant
	BCom	20(33.3%)	26(43.4%)	14(23.3%)	
	BBA/BBM	10(62.5%)	2(12.5%)	4(25%)	
	BSC	38(47.5%)	30(37.5%)	12(15%)	
	MSC	20(56%)	12(33%)	4(11%)	
	MCA	26(50%)	8(15.4%)	18(34.6%)	
	BE	34(27.9%)	60(49.1%)	28(23%)	
	ME/MBA	34(54.8%)	16(25.8%)	12(19.4%)	
Others	4(16.7%)	8(33.3%)	12(50%)		
Origin	Urban	138(39.4%)	122(34.9%)	90(25.7%)	$\chi^2_{(df=4, N=480)} =$ 11.38, $p < .05,$ significant
	S.Urban	24(30.8%)	34(43.6%)	20(25.6%)	
	Rural	30(57.7%)	16(30.8%)	6(11.5%)	
Annual Income	1-2	84(40.8%)	88(42.7%)	34(16.5%)	$\chi^2_{(df=8, N=480)} =$ 43.64, $p < .05,$ significant
	2-3	54(41%)	46(34.8%)	32(24.2%)	
	3-4	36(42%)	28(32.5%)	22(25.5%)	
	4-5	10(45.5%)	4(18.1%)	8(36.4%)	
	5-6	8(23.6%)	6(17.6%)	20(58.8%)	

** including Jain, Buddhist, Sikh, and others.

Inference

Gender and social status are not significant with respect to role scope. Religion, educational qualifications, origin, and annual income are significant. Origin's significance can be explained as they stay in hostels or house of relatives, giving rise to different social environment.

The employees are from villages and towns that have no awareness about modern business adding to different social pressure on them to be on par with their city peers. Similarly, education as arts and science graduates, technical graduates and post graduates likely to give rise to different social geography, interaction and outlook regarding career opportunities giving rise to differences in the role scope.

The income structure with different consumption pattern may give rise to differences in the role scope. These explanations need to be accepted with caution, as more qualitative research is required to assert these relationships.

4.4 Analysis of Value priorities

All human beings have universal set of values. However, they differ in their value priorities that are molded by culture, interaction with different institutions and environment. For the present study, forty-two statements are identified and itemized, scale is used with highest value 5 anchored to total agreement and total disagreement anchored to one. The forty-two items are tested for correlation and 644 have significant correlations (at .01 level) out of 924, pointing out suitability for factor analysis. Bartlett's Test for Sphericity indicated ($\chi^2_{(df=861, N=480)} = 5486.421, p=.000$), that the factor analysis can be used for analysis. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of

sampling adequacy indicates a Value of .738, pointing that factor analysis is an appropriate tool of analysis. All the variables exhibited communality more than .50. The Cronbach Alpha = .8234 indicating strong reliability of instrument. The factors explained 59.85% of total variation in the data. Factor loadings are set under a varimax rotation to get a better view of the factor loadings.

Figure 4.8 Scree Plot for factor analysis of value priorities

Table 4.18 Total Variance Explained for Different Components of Value Priorities

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.412	12.886	12.886	3.078	7.327	7.327
2	4.362	10.386	23.272	2.986	7.110	14.437
3	2.169	5.163	28.435	2.303	5.482	19.920
4	1.984	4.724	33.159	1.922	4.575	24.495
5	1.569	3.737	36.896	1.842	4.385	28.880
6	1.406	3.347	40.242	1.801	4.287	33.167
7	1.381	3.287	43.530	1.708	4.066	37.233
8	1.310	3.120	46.649	1.665	3.965	41.198
9	1.276	3.039	49.688	1.647	3.921	45.119
10	1.194	2.843	52.531	1.575	3.751	48.870
11	1.150	2.738	55.269	1.567	3.731	52.600
12	1.126	2.680	57.949	1.547	3.684	56.284
13	1.095	2.608	60.557	1.517	3.611	59.895

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

4.4.1 Nomenclature for Value Priorities Dimensions

The over all reliability of the instrument for value priorities is given by Cronbach Alpha = .8234 indicating higher reliability of the instrument. The scree plot indicate that there is less value addition from 11th to 13th item though their Eigen values are greater than one .

However, they do represent some of the values that need to be considered and has been included for analysis. Items 11 and 13 have no reliability value as they contain only one variable. Factor loading greater than .4 is selected for each factor. The nomenclature for each of the factors is subjective. However, care has been taken in such a way that the names reflect the meaning of each of the statements in the context of BPO industry.

Table 4.19 Value Priorities Dimensions Identified through Factor Analysis

Factor Loading	Factors	Primary Representation	Cronbach Alpha	Eigen Value	Percentage of Variance
.667 .749 .665 .609 .596	<u>Factor one</u> Family is not the most important concept in the global environment. Health considerations are not very important. Preventive health care is not workable in 365*twenty-four*7 work environment. There is no need for challenging work. Broadmindedness need not be an important quality of work.	Low Health care and low need for family, hard work and broadmindedness	.7435	5.412	12.886
.698 .579 .609 .654 .437 .428 .546	<u>Factor 2</u> Current working style leads to a comfortable life. Work style must act as stimulant to active life. Self-respect is upheld in workplace. BPO gives room for mutual help and welfare. We cannot be dishonest in BPO related work. Individual responsibility is the top most concern in BPO Self-reliance is more demanded.	Comfortable and active life with self-reliance and responsibility	.7441	4.362	10.386

.479 .673 .717 .682	<u>Factor 3</u> No time left for developing true friendship. Life is becoming more mechanical. Love and affection are slowly vanishing Obedience and politeness are replaced by self-respect and decency.	Routinized work environment devoid of true friendship, love, and affection.	.6408	2.169	5.163
.609 .691 .537	<u>Factor 4</u> Competition is the only attribute associated with development. Current working requires more individual contribution. Religious beliefs have no place in current work.	Competition for development with no personal beliefs	.4919	1.984	4.724
.449 .689 .519	<u>Factor 5</u> There is little room for personal jealousy in the workplace. Competency in subjects studied has no relevance. Team discussion and solution replace faultfinding and admonishing.	Teamwork with no jealousy	.4535	1.569	3.737
.525 .728	<u>Factor 6</u> There is no need to develop special capabilities for BPO. Elevated level of intelligence is not required in BPO.	Low intelligence and low capability requirement	.4794	1.406	3.347
.669 .667	<u>Factor 7</u> Work environment offers equal opportunity for all. Brotherhood has a major place in workplace.	Equal opportunity and brotherhood	.3702	1.381	3.287
.587 .783	<u>Factor 8</u> Work must lead to lasting contribution to society. Intellectual pursuits pave way for acquiring intelligence.	Lasting contribution to society with intellectual pursuits.	.4698	1.310	3.120
.462 .831	<u>Factor 9</u> Personal life in work does not guarantee freedom of choice. Constrained interpersonal relations lead to lower output.	Mutual dependence	.3795	1.276	3.039
.729 .544	<u>Factor 10</u> Excitement at work is not important. There is no meaning of enforcing morality in personal relations.	Excitement and no enforcement of morality	.4092	1.194	2.843
.752	<u>Factor 11</u> Leisure pursuits are directed towards pleasure rather than salvation.	Hedonistic		1.150	2.738
.800	<u>Factor 12</u> Beauty and aesthetic values have no role in global economy	Low aesthetic	.4133	1.126	2.680
.713	<u>Factor 13</u> Personal advancement with a focus on creativity and self-reliance.	Personal advancement with self-direction		1.095	2.608

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Thirteen factors extracted. Total variance explained = **59.89%**.

For better understanding of factor representation process, primary representation is given to summarize different variables in the factor loading. Some of the variables are designed in negative form based on the recommendation that having negative statements help in better response

or else there will be problem of “end-piling” (Munson, 1984). To have uniformity of analysis we need to convert them. For this purpose, the mean values are subtracted from the highest value possible, that is five. In the process, the primary representation changes with respect to these dimensions.

Table 4.20 Change in the Mean Values to Reflect the Value Dimensions

Primary Representation	Changed Representation	Mean	Changed Mean*
Low Health care and low need for family, hard work, and broadmindedness.	Health care and need for family, hard work, and broadmindedness.	2.742	2.258
Routinized work environment devoid of true friendship, love, and affection.	Stimulation	3.433	1.567
Low intelligence and low capability requirement	Intelligence and capability requirement	2.9771	2.0229
Excitement and no enforcement of morality	Excitement	2.7729	2.2271
Low Aesthetic	Aesthetic	3.2292	1.7708

* (5-Mean= changed mean)

At workplace, there is less emphasis on aesthetic values, stimulation, competence, excitement and health and family values.

Table 4.21 Identification of Value Types Relating to Factor Analysis Output

Primary Representation	Value Types
Health care and need for family, hard work and broadmindedness.	Health, family, and broadmindedness value
Comfortable and active life with self-reliance and responsibility.	Tradition and Conformity value
Work environment devoid of true friendship, love, and affection.	Stimulation value
Competition for development with no personal beliefs.	Achievement value
Teamwork with no jealousy.	Benevolence value
Low intelligence and low capability requirement.	Competence value
Equal opportunity and brotherhood.	Universalism value
Lasting contribution to society with intellectual pursuits.	Accomplishment value
Mutual dependence.	Helpful value
Excitement.	Excitement value
Hedonistic	Hedonism value
Aesthetic values	Aesthetic value
Personal advancement with self-direction	Competence value

4.4.2 Definitions of Dimensions of Value Types

These definitions are given in the context of BPO work environment.

Health, family, and broadmindedness value: *Fitness, fulfilling family life with broadmindedness by being tolerant of different ideas and beliefs with mature understanding of life.*

Tradition and Conformity value: *Preservation and enhancement of self and others; submission to life's circumstances with self-respect, self-reliance, honesty, and individual responsibility.*

Restraint of actions inclinations and impulses those are likely to harm others and violate social norms.

Stimulation value: *Excitement, novelty, challenge in life with risk taking.*

Achievement value: *Personal success through demonstrating competence according to social standards.*

Benevolence value: *Preservation and enhancement of the welfare of people with whom one is in frequent contact.*

Competence value: *Consistently developing skills that ensure success.*

Accomplishment value: *Striving for higher order goals by contributing to society in the process of acquiring intelligence.*

Universalism value: *Understanding, appreciation, tolerance, and protection for the welfare of all people and nature.*

Helpful value: *Willing to be cooperative, supportive, obliging and caring for others.*

Excitement value: *Enthusiasm and experience of exhilaration*

Hedonism value: *Pleasure and sensuous gratification for oneself indicating enjoyment of food, leisure and so on.*

Aesthetic value: *Appreciation of artistic and visual beauty.*

Self-Direction value: *Independent thought and action choosing, creating, and exploring.*

The value priorities, benevolence, accomplishment, and universalism represent higher mean values. Stimulation, aesthetic, competence, excitement and health, family and broadmindedness in that order represent the lowest values. Further analysis is undertaken to obtain better insights.

Table 4.22 Descriptive Statistics of Value Priorities Dimensions

Value Priorities Dimensions	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Health, family, and broadmindedness value	2.258	1.7666	.106	-.793
Tradition and Conformity value	3.3601	1.3524	-.516	.286
Stimulation value	1.567	1.3526	-.139	-.239
Achievement value	3.4028	1.3914	-.004	.158
Benevolence value	3.542	1.344	.006	-.457
Competence value	2.0229	1.5341	.110	-.477
Universalism value	3.4292	1.4549	.093	.237
Accomplishment value	3.4979	1.2155	.055	.994
Helpful value	3.1604	1.2049	-.112	.051
Excitement value	2.2271	1.5169	.064	-.757
Hedonistic value	3.325	1.230	-.383	.637
Aesthetic value	1.7718	1.3144	-.239	-.243
Self-direction value	3.1875	1.231	-.302	-.598

Figure 4.9 scores of Value Priorities Dimensions

Figure 4.10 Model of Value Priorities of BPO Employees

Inference

Different dimensions and their mean values are given in the four quadrants.

First Quadrant → Third Quadrant → Social Context of Outcome versus Individual Context of Outcome Paradigm

The first quadrant represents moderately higher values in universalism, benevolence and helpful values indicating that higher focus on social context of outcomes is balanced with the lower values on health, family, and broadmindedness. The lower value on health-family-broadmindedness group, which is individual context outcome, is also due to higher values on achievement. The higher individual oriented achievement with higher stress work environment has two impacts- less

of health, family, and broadmindedness and more of social context of outcomes.

The fourth quadrant-Focus on Opportunity –Focus on organization Paradigm

The work is routinized, with no time left for developing true friendship, love, and affection indicating low value for simulation. This leads to higher hedonistic practices at workplace combined with higher disposable income. This is balanced by moderately higher value on tradition and conformity.

While tradition and conformity value of the individual pulls the employee in one direction, hedonism sometimes thrust him or her pulls in other different direction. These inferences are on tune with the model explanations of Schwartz (1992, 1996) and strengthen the content validity of the instrument. However, further analysis is needed.

The factor analysis output is summated for thirteen dimensions and the following results obtained by using K-means cluster analysis.

Table 4.23 Descriptive Statistics of Value Priorities Groups

Dimensions of value Priorities	Group 1 (n=146)	Group 2 (n=236)	Group 3 (n=98)	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Health, Family& Broadmindedness	1.89	2.95	1.26	Medium	High	Low
Tradition Conformity	2.50	3.72	3.74	Low	Medium	High
Stimulation	1.83	1.56	1.21	High	Medium	Low
Achievement	2.95	3.44	3.93	Low	Medium	High
Benevolence	2.98	3.22	3.74	Low	Medium	High
Competence	1.87	2.47	1.20	Medium	High	Low
Universalism	3.11	3.38	4.01	Low	Medium	High
Accomplishment	3.16	3.60	3.75	Low	Medium	High
Helpful	2.69	3.11	3.66	Low	Medium	High
Excitement	2.75	2.55	3.32	Medium	Low	High
Hedonistic	3.12	3.55	3.77	Low	Medium	High
Aesthetic	3.09	3.09	3.75	Medium	Medium	High
Self direction	3.05	3.06	3.69	Low	Medium	High

Figure 4.11 Scores of Value Priorities Groups

Inference

The group 1 has low value priorities represented by 30.4% of respondents, group 2 has moderate value priorities represented by 49.1% of respondents, and group 3 has high value priorities represented by 20.4% of respondents. The resulting data from factor analysis is subjected

to multidimensional scaling to have a better understanding of typology of respondents based on value priorities.

4.4.3 Analysis of Value Typology

The value priorities are analyzed using three-dimensional scaling and value typologies given by sociologists Zetterberg and Zetterberg, 1997. The dimension of value space (Z-axis) depicted, moves from stability to modernity. It corresponds to a scale from traditionalism to innovation. In the innovation, phase less preference for traditional values with new ways of experimentation given importance as opposed to stability. The next dimension (X-axis) corresponds to scale from fidelity to pragmatism. For fidelity- one dramatizes his or her values – includes aspects relating to conscious loyalty towards family, solidarity with weak, compassion for suffering and saving planet for future generations. For pragmatism, one compromises his or her values and pragmatism is concerned with instrumentality. The third dimension (Y-axis) separates concern with material things (materialism) from concern with human beings (humanism) - representing the continuum of humanism to materialism. Based on different combinations of these dimensions eight different typologies are identified for persons from European countries. For the present study, the basic propositions offered (Zetterberg and Zetterberg, 1997) are accepted.

However, to identify typologies the measurements are obtained from the three-dimensional output (Euclidian distance model) and given in the Table 4.23.

Three dimensional Model for Value Priorities

Figure 4.12 Three-dimensional model of value priorities

Table 4.24 Analysis of Value Typology of Respondents

Value Priorities	X-AXIS						Y-AXIS						Z-AXIS						
	FIDELITY			PRAGMATISM			HUMANISM			MATERIALISM			STABILITY			MODERNITY			
	H	M	L	L	M	H	H	M	L	L	M	H	H	M	L	L	M	H	
Health ,Family & broadmindedness value			+1.25																
Tradition & Conformity value	4.75																		
Stimulation value			+1.75																+0.7
Achievement value			+0.1																
Benevolence value				0.0															
Competence value				-1.75															
Universalism value				-1.0															
Accomplishment value				-1.0															
Helpful value				-1.5															
Excitement value				-1.25															
Hedonistic value				-1.0															
Aesthetic value				-1.0															
Self direction value				-2.0															

Legend

X-Axis representing Fidelity-Pragmatism continuum
X-Scale [+5,-4]: Fidelity {High (5-3), Medium (-2), Low (2-1)}
Pragmatism {Low (0,-2), Medium (-2,-3), High (-3,-4)}
Y-Axis representing Humanism-Materialism continuum
Y-Scale [+1,-1.5]: Humanism {High (1, .5), Medium (.5, 0), Low (0,-.5)}
Materialism {Low (-1,-.5), Medium (-.5,-1) Low (-1,-1.5)}
Z-Axis representing Stability-Modernity continuum
Z-Scale [-.4, .8]: Stability {High (-.4,-.2), Medium (-.2, 0), Low (0, .2)}
Modernity {Low (.2, .4), Medium (.4, .6), Low (.6, .8)}

The fidelity-pragmatism continuum there is a shift towards pragmatism however with high value on tradition and conformity, health, family and broadmindedness, simulation, and achievement- nonetheless, the shift is not total. On the humanism-materialism continuum, there is a clear shift towards materialism. In the stability –modernity continuum they are in the lower stage of stability. The general typology of BPO employees may be stated as,

- 1) High fidelity- conscious and loyal towards traditions and conformity, to a lesser extent towards health, family, stimulation, and achievement.

- 2) Pragmatism- Pragmatic with achievement, accomplishment, interpersonal relations, helpful, hedonistic, and self-directed.
- 3) Materialism- There is high tendency towards material things than with human beings.
- 4) Stability- low on stability with respect to all values indicating that he or she traditional but is ready for new ways of experimentation.
- 5) Is there a shift from Gemeinschaft to Gesellschaft? There is a tendency towards the shift but the shift has not taken place.

In summary, he or she is loyal towards tradition and conformity, likes to take care of health and family but not in a position to work towards that goal. Instrumental with respect to interpersonal relations, achievement, hedonistic and self-directed. Highly materialistic in outlook and stable, ready for new ways of experimentation. He or she is experimenting with new type of performing tasks, tasting newfound liberty and choices combined with high income with imagination of western life. This is an explanation for their changing life styles (they are not changed- they are only experimenting). After some time they find that this new experiment may not be in tune with the tradition and conformity, they either leave job and go for higher education or change their industry. The values promoted by BPO organization of fun culture, odd incentives such as dating allowance only gives rise to experimentation with self to fast realize the fragility of fun to

change to old traditional way of life or start liking the present way of doing things and continue the same. Therefore, they may be called as EXPERIMENTERS, who try out new things or attempt a new course of action without being sure of outcome facing complexity.

Table 4.25 Inter Correlation Coefficients^a of Value Priorities

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Health, Family & Broadmindedness value	Tradition & Conformity value	Stimulation value	Achievement value	Benevolence value	Competence value	Universalism value	Accomplishment value	Helpful value	Excitement value	Hedonistic value	Aesthetic value	Self-direction Value
Health, family & broadmindedness value	2.258	1.7666	1.000												
Tradition & Conformity value	3.3601	1.3524	.187**	1.000											
Stimulation value	1.567	1.3526	.142**	.220**	1.000										
Achievement value	3.4028	1.3914	.115	.387**	.248**	1.000									
Benevolence value	3.342	1.344	.221**	.292**	.273**	.302**	1.000								
Competence value	2.0229	1.5341	.547**	.155**	.089	.132**	.232**	1.000							
Universalism value	3.4292	1.4549	.158**	.259**	.142**	.483**	.179**	.032	1.000						
Accomplishment value	3.4979	1.2155	-.057	.303**	.140**	.114**	.240**	-.162**	.214**	1.000					
Helpful value	3.1604	1.2049	.172**	.190**	.240**	.247**	.240**	.074	.170**	.096	1.000				
Excitement value	2.2271	1.5160	.329**	.075	.119**	.132**	.157**	.144**	.128**	.068	.108	1.000			
Hedonistic value	3.325	1.230	.001	.202**	.290**	.240**	.181**	.136**	.161**	.163**	.160**	.057	1.000		
Aesthetic value	1.7718	1.3144	.209**	.166**	.137**	.211**	.550**	.262**	.108	.255**	.151**	.188**	.075	1.000	
Self direction value	3.1875	1.231	.198**	.047	.082	.183**	.161**	.231**	.037	.091	.147**	.194**	.063	.206**	1.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

^a Small effect ($.1 < r < .3$), medium effect ($.3 < r < .5$), large effect ($r > .5$) Cohen, 1988.

Analysis of Inter correlation Coefficients of Value Priorities

For convergent validity, 83.33 % (65/78) of correlations indicate that there is good convergence. The degree of practical distinctiveness depends on the absolute magnitudes of the correlations and the nature of components under examination (Bagozzi and Edwards, 1998). The low values of correlations indicate that the components are distinct. Health, family, and broadmindedness have large effect positive correlation coefficient ($r > .5$) with competence and medium effect correlation coefficient ($.3 < r < .5$) with excitement, indicating higher importance for

health, family, and broadmindedness is likely to have better impact on the employees. Tradition and conformity has positive large effect correlation coefficient with achievement, accomplishment, and benevolence. This indicates that promotion of tradition and conformity values have a positive effect on these values. Stimulation has significant positive small effect correlation coefficients with hedonistic, excitement, helpful and achievement values, indicating higher challenges in work environment has positive impact on other values. Achievement has medium effect on universalism indicating emphasis on achievement improves understanding, appreciation, and tolerance in the organization. Benevolence has large effect correlation coefficient with aesthetic value, improving better understanding of environment by the employees. Furthermore, to test the dependence of value priorities on sociodemographic variables the following hypothesis is devised for testing.

H₀6: Value priorities groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.

H₁6: Value priorities groups are dependent of sociodemographic variables.

Table 4.26 Cross Tabulation of Value Priorities Groups with Sociodemographic Variables.

Characteristic	Category	Value Priorities Groups			Chi-Square Test *
		Group 1 146(30.4%)	Group 2 236(49.1%)	Group 3 98(20.5%)	
Gender	Male	90(32.4%)	136(48.9%)	52(18.7%)	$\chi^2_{(df=2, N=480)} = 1.79, p > .05, \text{ not significant}$
	Female	56(27.7%)	100(49.5%)	46(22.8%)	
Social Status	OC	42(31.8%)	68(51.5%)	22(16.7%)	$\chi^2_{(df=6, N=480)} = 16.76, p < .05, \text{ significant}$
	BC	74(30.6%)	116(47.9%)	52(21.5%)	
	MBC	24(32.4%)	38(51.4%)	12(16.2%)	
	SC/ST	6(18.7%)	14(43.8%)	12(37.5%)	
Religion	Hindu	92(27.7%)	172(51.8%)	68(20.5%)	$\chi^2_{(df=6, N=480)} = 25.3, p < .05, \text{ significant}$
	Muslim	24(52.2%)	16(34.8%)	6(13%)	
	Christian	18(23.7%)	34(44.7%)	24(31.6%)	
	Others**	12(46.2%)	14(53.8%)	-	
Educational Qualification	BA	8(28.6%)	12(42.8%)	8(28.6%)	$\chi^2_{(df=16, N=480)} = 42.84, p < .05, \text{ significant}$
	BCom	26(43.3%)	20(33.3%)	14(23.4%)	
	BBA/BBM	8(50%)	4(25%)	4(25%)	
	BSC	18(22.5%)	48(60%)	14(17.5%)	
	MSC	14(38.9%)	16(44.4%)	6(16.7%)	
	MCA	14(27%)	20(38.4%)	18(34.6%)	
	BE	36(29.5%)	72(59%)	14(11.5%)	
	ME/MBA	20(32.3%)	28(45.2%)	14(22.5%)	
Others	2(8.3%)	16(66.7%)	6(25%)		
Origin	Urban	112(32%)	166(47.4%)	72(20.6%)	$\chi^2_{(df=4, N=480)} = 16.23, p < .05, \text{ significant}$
	S. Urban	12(15.4%)	52(66.6%)	14(18%)	
	Rural	22(42.3%)	18(34.6%)	12(23.1%)	
Annual Income	1-2	72(35%)	96(46.6%)	38(18.4%)	$\chi^2_{(df=8, N=480)} = 12.47, p > .05, \text{ not significant}$
	2-3	30(23%)	70(53%)	32(24%)	
	3-4	30(35%)	36(41.8%)	20(23.2%)	
	4-5	6(27.3%)	12(54.5%)	4(18.2%)	
	5-6	8(23.5%)	22(54.7%)	4(11.8%)	

** including Jain, Buddhist, Sikh, and others.

Inference

Gender and annual income is not significant with respect to value priorities. The income not being significant is a crucial point to be noted. If we consider the age group of the sample they are representing the young persons and they are having similar value profile is understandable. Social status, religion, educational qualification has meaningful relationship with value priorities.

Value priorities having meaningful relationship with educational qualification may be caused by the difference in education between science and arts graduates and technical graduates among respondents and technical graduates having higher ambitions may have an influence on their value priorities.

4.5 Analysis of Individualization of work

Individualization of work is a new phenomenon characterised by networks, flat organizational structure, flexibilization of work, mobility, unstructured task environment, open work culture, and with individualization trait. Thirty-six statements relating to individualization of work are identified and responses are obtained on a 5-point scale, with highest value for total agreement at 5, and lowest value for total disagreement at 1. Correlation analysis was performed with respect to 36 items and 441 have significant correlations (at .01 level) out of 630 correlations, indicating that factor analysis can be used. Using SPSS, principal components were extracted for factors with Eigen values more than one. Bartlett's Test for Sphericity (χ^2 (df=630, N=480) = 4368.483, p=.000) indicates that the factor analysis can be used for analysis. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of sampling adequacy (value=0.675) indicated that factor analysis is an appropriate tool of analysis. The Cronbach Alpha = .7476 indicate good reliability of the instrument The scree plot also

showed twelve factors could be considered for further analysis. Communalities of variable are more than .50 indicating suitability of the data for factor analysis. The output explained 62.052% of total variation in the data. Factor loadings are configured under varimax rotation to obtain a better distribution of values.

Figure 4.13 Scree Plot for Factor Analysis of Individualization of work.

Table: 4.27 Total Variance Explained for Different Components of Individualization of Work

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.432	12.310	12.310	2.769	7.692	7.692
2	3.281	9.115	21.425	2.477	6.880	14.572
3	2.168	6.022	27.448	2.046	5.683	20.255
4	1.978	5.494	32.942	1.973	5.481	25.736
5	1.697	4.714	37.656	1.882	5.227	30.963
6	1.555	4.319	41.975	1.751	4.865	35.828
7	1.492	4.143	46.118	1.729	4.802	40.630
8	1.353	3.759	49.877	1.710	4.751	45.381
9	1.174	3.262	53.140	1.678	4.660	50.041
10	1.139	3.164	56.303	1.634	4.538	54.579
11	1.068	2.966	59.269	1.414	3.928	58.507
12	1.002	2.783	62.052	1.276	3.545	62.052

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

4.5.1 Nomenclature for Individualization of Work

Factor loading greater than .4 is selected for each factor. Each of the factors with corresponding factor loadings are selected for appropriate nomenclature. The labeling process of the factors is subjective. However, care has been taken in such a way that the nomenclature reflects the meaning of each of the statements in the context of BPO industry.

Table 4.28 Individualization of Work Dimensions Identified through Factor Analysis

Factor Loading	Factor	Factor Name	Cronbach Alpha	Eigen Value	Percentage of variance
.721 .850 .810 .727	<u>Factor 1</u> International exposure is provided in the work environment I prefer working for my company as consultant if it is helpful to my career Copy rights must be registered in my name though I work for organization I like working with virtual colleagues	Global View	.6680	4.432	12.310
.656 .617 .516 .725 .642	<u>Factor 2</u> Provident Fund and other social security measures are no more relevant for BPO industry I prefer government not to involve into the BPO industry In BPO industry it is not Indian or American culture, it is global culture Individual employment contracts are better than uniform contracts for jobs Since two jobs are not the same the salary also has to take this into account	Individual employment contracts	.6785	3.281	9.115
.548 .783 .512 -.573	<u>Factor 3</u> To perform well I must work like an entrepreneur taking decision and being responsible for the same Life time learning is one of the most important dimension of job I like multiple demands on me by job as it provides me better exposure Job security is not important	Life time learning with job security	.0410	2.168	6.022
.435 .693 .684 .463	<u>Factor 4</u> Flexibility of job will help me to grow I prefer visibility to achieve personal goals I rely on myself totally for any job related issues My personal identity is most important for me	Personal identity	.6012	1.978	5.494
.468 .483 .722	<u>Factor 5</u> When I reflect on my work I feel inner emptiness I prefer to do a task in my own way even if it takes longer period I prefer quitting organization if my productivity is not to the expectations	Job autonomy	.4593	1.697	4.714

.769 .663	<u>Factor 6</u> Changing jobs is good for my career When other does better than me I get tense and aroused	Positive Job hopping	.2079	1.555	4.319
.601 .473 .731	<u>Factor 7</u> If I am faced with work related issue, I prefer to deal it myself I take ownership for my work I often do work in my own way	Solitary worker	.5159	1.492	4.143
.410 .573 .728	<u>Factor 8</u> I prefer a flat organization with low hierarchy International culture ensures better performance I have developed my own values after joining my job	Global standards of performance	.4377	1.353	3.759
.412 .822 .577	<u>Factor 9</u> Unstructured jobs are preferred by me Since no two persons are same the work also must be designed to the competence of the employee I feel easy with myself if I am asked to have different values from what I have in the work place	Work for competence	.5221	1.174	3.262
.464 .516 .770 .486	<u>Factor 10</u> I am provided with required job training by my organization Flexibility of job will help me to grow Mobility in jobs to various locations is a learning experience Flexible timings in job is preferred by me	Mobility and flexibility	.6050	1.139	3.164
.677	<u>Factor 11</u> Unions are irrelevant for BPO industry	No collective action		1.068	2.966
.762	<u>Factor 12</u> Long hours of work is necessary to meet customer needs	Borderless work geography		1.002	2.783

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Twelve factors extracted. Variance explained = **62.05%**.

4.5.2 Definitions of Dimensions of Individualization of work

The dimensions of individualization of work and their definitions in the context of BPO work environment are as follows:

1. **Global View:** *Prefer to work in international environment with virtual colleagues with identity recognized at work.*
2. **Individual employment contracts:** *Non-state intervention in deciding employment conditions and prefers individual employment contract.*

3. **Lifetime learning with job security:** *Readiness for multiple tasks with job security.*
4. **Personal Identity:** *Visibility in the form of recognition and personal identity with self-reliance in job performance.*
5. **Job autonomy:** *Preference for self-designed tasks.*
6. **Positive job-hopping:** *Changing jobs for career growth.*
7. **Solitary worker:** *Preference to deal with work related issues single-handed.*
8. **Global standards of performance:** *Redefined values with international culture of performance.*
9. **Work for competence:** *Differentiated work assignment based on skill to do tasks successfully.*
10. **Mobility and Flexibility:** *Preference for job mobility and flexibility.*
11. **No collective action:** *Unions and other collective action tools are irrelevant for BPO industry.*
12. **Borderless work geography:** *Reduced relevance of work life and private life boundary.*

Table 4.29 Descriptive Statistics of individualization of work dimensions

Dimensions of Individualization of Work	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Global View	4.1073	1.8519	.236	.988
Individual employment contracts	3.5508	1.1037	1.436	4.495
Life time learning with job security	3.4854	0.733	.155	.182
Personal identity	3.8895	0.9148	1.235	2.356
Job autonomy	3.2958	1.0079	.477	.419
Positive Job hopping	3.2916	1.429	1.493	1.602
Solitary worker	3.85	0.9549	1.787	5.217
Global standards of performance	3.7458	0.8962	.085	.904
Work for competence	3.4402	1.1242	.626	2.178
Mobility and flexibility	3.7479	0.9046	.561	.425
No collective action	3.575	1.8123	1.445	3.744
Borderless work geography	3.6312	0.9716	.277	1.560

Figure 4.14 Scores of Individualization of work Dimensions

The resulting output is analyzed using K-means cluster analysis tool and the following results are obtained.

Table 4.30 Descriptive Statistics of Individualization of Work Groups

Dimensions of individualization of work	Group 1 N=300	Group 2 N=56	Group 3 n=124
Global View	3.33	4.4	4.04
Individual employment contracts	3.03	3.42	4.85
Life time learning with job security	3.42	2.95	3.88
Personal identity	3.75	3.26	4.49
Job autonomy	3.2	3.4	3.46
Positive Job hopping	3.09	3.37	3.73
Solitary worker	3.67	3.68	4.35
Global standards of performance	3.49	3.48	4.48
Work for competence	3.35	2.98	3.86
Mobility and flexibility	3.68	3.23	4.14
No collective action	3.44	3.64	3.871
Borderless work geography	3.64	2.96	3.9

Figure 4.15 Scores of Individualization of Work Groups.

Inference

The low values indicate that there is low individualization of work and this group may be labeled as “COMMONERS.” The next group has highest value for globalization of work and other values are moderate. Therefore, this group may be labeled as “HIGH VIEWS LOW PRACTITIONER.”

The next cluster have all high values except globalization of work and it may be labeled as Individualists or “STRAIGHT ‘I’ S.” The commoners are in high number with 62.5%, followed by, high views low practitioners with 11.7% and Straight I s 25.8%.

THREE DIMENSIONAL MODEL

INDIVIDUALIZATION OF WORK

S.I: SUBSTANTIVE INDIVIDUALIZATION ,F.I: FUNCTIONAL INDIVIDUALIZATION

P.I.: PROCEDURAL INDIVIDUALIZATION

Figure 4.16 Three-Dimensional Model of Individualization of Work

Multidimensional scaling results may be analysed with the help of empirical research performed by two British researchers with respect to attributes of individualization. Storey and Bacon (1993, 1996) have identified three areas in which individualism, collectivism in employment relations’ arrangements can be assessed, and these are **procedural individualization**, which refers to removal of collective bargaining

mechanisms from determining terms and conditions of employment (Brown *et al*, 1998). **Substantive Individualization**, which is the differentiation of individual employees' employment contracts like pay and non-pay terms and conditions of employment that is individualism in human resources aspects of management strategy like nature of pay system, terms, and conditions. **Functional individualization** corresponds to how much autonomy is given to perform the job, and type of supervision and accountability. In addition, there is a tendency to disembeddedness of work from traditional context of work to reembeddness into new and more variable context of global environment.

Table 4.31 Analysis of Three Dimensional Representation of Individualization of work Dimensions.

Dimensions of Individualization of work	Coordinates			Functional Individualization			Substantive Individualization			Procedural Individualization		
	X	Y	Z	High	Medium	Low	High	Medium	Low	High	Medium	Low
Global View	2	.25	-1	2			.25					-1
Individual employment contracts	2.2	.3	-1	2.2			.3					-1
Life time learning with job security	.8	0	.3		.8		0				.3	
Personal Identity	1.2	.3	.4	1.2			.3				.4	
Job autonomy	-.8	-.6	.01			-.8			-.6		.01	
Positive Job hopping	-.2	-.1	-.4			-.2		-.1				-.4
Solitary worker	0	-.4	.01		0			-.4			.01	
Global standards of performance	1	0	-.2	1			0					-.2
Work for competence	-.8	-.25	.25		-.8			-.25		.25		
Mobility and flexibility	1	.3	.5	1			.3			.5		
No collective action	-.3	-.25	.25			-.3		-.25		-.25		
Borderless work geography	-.25	-.25	.25		-.25			-.25		.25		

Legend:

X-Axis representing Functional Individualization

X- Scale: [3.0, -3.0] [High (3.0, 1.0), Medium (1.0,-1.0) Low (-1.0,-3.0)]

Y-Axis representing Substantive Individualization

Y-Scale: [1.0, -2.0] [High (1.0, 0.0), Medium (0.0,-1.0), Low (-1.5,-2.0)]

Z-Axis representing Procedural Individualization

Z-Scale: [+1.0, -1.0] [High (1.0, 0.5), Medium (+.25,-.25), Low (-.05,-1.0)]

A weighted average scores (high=3, medium=2, low=1) for functional individualization =4.3, substantive individualization =4.83 and procedural individualization = 4.

Inference

The weighted average scores indicate substantive individualization is most desired followed by functional individualization and procedural individualization. The employees seem to prefer individual pay system, terms, and conditions based on competence and ability to perform tasks. Similarly, there is expectation of job autonomy, lesser supervision, and more accountability. Jobs with mobility, flexibility, and borderless work geography are not constraints to the employees.

Table 4.32 Inter Correlation Coefficients ^a of individualization of work Dimensions

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Global view	individual employment contracts	Life time learning with job security	Personal identity	Job autonomy	Positive job hopping	Solitary worker	Global standards of performance	Work for competence	mobility and flexibility	No collective action	Borderless work Geography
Global View	4.1073	1.8519	1.000											
Individual employment contracts	3.5508	1.1037	.122**	1.000										
Life time learning with job security	3.4854	0.7330	-.158**	.182**	1.000									
Personal identity	3.8895	0.9148	.131**	.212**	.323**	1.000								
Job autonomy	3.2958	1.0079	.071	.034	.205**	.017	1.000							
Positive Job hopping	3.2916	1.429	-.148**	.110	.067	-.013	.175**	1.000						
Solitary worker	3.85	0.9549	.007	.279**	.338**	.347**	.127**	-.007	1.000					
Global standards of performance	3.7458	0.8962	-.049	.512**	.135**	.401**	.134**	-.084	.220**	1.000				
Work for competence	3.4402	1.242	.050	.094	.216**	.222**	.133**	-.058	.151**	.127**	1.000			
Mobility and flexibility	3.7479	0.9046	.121**	.175**	.303**	.452**	.074	-.065	.280**	.290**	.204**	1.000		
No collective action	3.5750	1.8123	.021	.159**	-.030	-.105	-.042	-.042	-.002	.042	.098	.015	1.000	
Borderless work geography	3.6312	0.9716	-.180**	.090	.179**	.441**	-.100	.188**	.298**	.200**	.140**	.190**	-.074	1.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

^a Small effect (.1 < r < .3), medium effect (.3 < r < .5), large effect (r > .5) Cohen, 1988.

Analysis of Inter Correlation Coefficients of Individualization of Work

For convergent validity 57.5 % (38/66) of correlations indicate that there is moderate convergence. The overall low values of correlations indicate that there is distinctiveness of the items. Individual employment contracts have large effect correlation coefficient with respect to global standards of performance and small effect correlation coefficient for

personal identity and solitary worker indicating substantive individualization regarding work norms. Lifetime learning with job security has medium effect correlation coefficients with personal identity, solitary worker, mobility, and flexibility. Personal identity has medium effect correlation coefficients with mobility and flexibility, borderless work geography, global standards of performance and low effect negative correlation with no collective action and positive job changes, confirming the theoretical basis of individualization. Solitary worker has small effect correlation coefficient with borderless work geography.

Table 4.33 Bivariate Correlation of Individualization of work and Value Priorities

	Health & Family	Tradition & Conformity	Stimulation	Achievement	Benevolence	Competence	Universalism	Accomplishment	Helpful	Excitement	Hedonistic	Aesthetic	Self direction
Global View	0.276**	-0.288**	-0.004	-0.01	0.052	0.222**	-0.063	-0.117	0.025	-0.032	0.031	0.071	0.044
Individual employment contracts	0.124**	0.088	0.027	0.215**	0.152**	0.336**	-0.016	-0.074	-0.036	0.071	0.134**	0.195**	0.183**
Life time learning with job security	0.04	0.428**	0.208**	0.353**	0.248**	0.057	0.265**	0.179**	0.063	0.138**	0.236**	0.193**	0.003
Personal identity	-0.068	0.318**	0.223**	0.268**	0.229**	0.05	0.116	0.159**	0.097	0.017	0.262**	0.187**	0.125
Job autonomy	0.278**	0.083	0.262**	0.107	0.194**	0.021	0.213**	0.197**	0.118**	0.245**	0.079	0.142**	0.184**
Positive Job changes	0.349**	-0.197**	0.099	0.047	0.064	0.253**	0.068	0.024	-0.052	0.324**	0.03	0.086	0.130**
Solitary worker	-0.051	0.342**	0.171**	0.379**	0.215**	0.006	0.150**	0.028	0.115	0.09	0.239**	0.062	0.136**
Global standards of performance	0.053	0.119**	0.11	0.141**	0.178**	0.146**	0.077	0.059	0.189**	-0.024	0.187**	0.183**	0.195**
Work for competence	0.203**	0.157**	0.135**	0.164**	0.202**	0.126**	0.173**	0.109	0.057	0.278**	0.122**	0.126**	0.013
Mobility and flexibility	-0.018	0.386**	0.027	0.288**	0.288**	-0.032	0.215**	0.143**	0.207**	0.042	0.239**	0.141**	0.165**
No collective action	0.051	0.087	-0.102	0.017	0.157**	0.018	-0.001	-0.007	0.042	0.088	-0.089	0.149**	0.027
Borderless work geography	-0.015	0.142**	0.230**	0.191**	-0.138**	0.096	0.051	0.009	0.038	0.068	0.250**	0.09	0.138**

** Correlation is significant at .01 level

² Small effect ($.1 < r < .3$), medium effect ($.3 < r < .5$), large effect ($r > .5$) Cohen, 1988.

Analysis of Bivariate Correlation Coefficients of Individualization of Work and Value Priorities.

Health, family, and broadmindedness have medium effect correlation on positive job-hopping and small effect with global view, job autonomy and work for competence. Tradition and conformity has medium effect correlation with lifetime learning, personal identity, solitary work and mobility and flexibility. Stimulation has small effect correlation with lifetime learning with job security, personal identity, and job autonomy Achievement has medium correlation effect on lifetime learning with job security and solitary worker. Benevolence has medium effect correlation with lifetime learning with job security. Competence has medium effect on individual employment contracts. Excitement has medium effect correlation with positive job-hopping. The results are in consonance with the definitions.

However, negative small effect correlations of global view with achievement, universalism, accomplishment, and excitement are not in tune with the definition. Furthermore, to test the relationship between individualization of work and sociodemographic variables the following hypothesis is devised for testing.

H₀7: Individualization of work groups are independent of sociodemographic variables.

H₀7: Individualization of work groups are dependent of sociodemographic variables.

Table 4.34 Cross Tabulation of Individualization of work Groups with Sociodemographic Variables.

Characteristic	Category	Individualization of work Groups			Chi-Square Test *
		Commoner 300(62.5%)	High views and Low practitioner 56(11.7%)	Straight I's 124(25.8%)	
Gender	Male	180(64.7%)	30(10.8%)	68(24.5%)	$\chi^2_{(df=2,N=480)} = 1.45,$ $p > .05,$ not significant
	Female	120(59.4%)	26(12.9%)	56(27.7%)	
Social Status	OC	76(57.6%)	26(19.7%)	30(22.7%)	$\chi^2_{(df=6,N=480)} = 34.0,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	BC	162(67%)	16(6.6%)	64(26.4%)	
	MBC	46(62.2%)	12(16.2%)	16(21.6%)	
	SC/ST	16(50%)	2(6.3%)	14(43.7%)	
Religion	Hindu	208(62.6%)	38(11.4%)	86(26%)	$\chi^2_{(df=6,N=480)} = 52.95,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	Muslim	34(74%)	6(13%)	6(13%)	
	Christian	50(65.7%)	6(8%)	20(26.3%)	
	Others**	8(30.8%)	6(23%)	12(46.2%)	
Education Qualification	BA	22(78.6%)	4(14.3%)	2(7.1%)	$\chi^2_{(df=16,N=480)} = 50.56,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	BCom	40(66.7%)	12(20%)	8(13.3%)	
	BBA/BBM	4(25%)	6(37.5%)	6(37.5%)	
	BSC	48(60%)	10(12.5%)	22(27.5%)	
	MSC	26(72.2%)	4(11.1%)	6(16.7%)	
	MCA	32(61.5%)	-	20(38.5%)	
	BE	76(62.3%)	12(9.8%)	34(27.9%)	
	ME/MBA	32(51.6%)	8(12.9%)	22(35.5%)	
Others	20(83.3%)	-	4(16.7%)		
Origin	Urban	222(63.4%)	36(10.3%)	92(26.3%)	$\chi^2_{(df=4,N=480)} = 7.14,$ $p > .05,$ not significant
	S.Urban	52(66.7%)	12(15.4%)	14(17.9%)	
	Rural	26(50%)	8(15.4%)	18(34.6%)	
Annual Income	1-2	144(69.9%)	18(8.7%)	44(21.4%)	$\chi^2_{(df=8,N=480)} = 20.24,$ $p < .05,$ significant
	2-3	74(56.1%)	16(12.1%)	42(31.8%)	
	3-4	46(53.5%)	12(14%)	28(32.5%)	
	4-5	10(45.4%)	6(27.3%)	6(27.3%)	
	5-6	26(76.4%)	4(11.8%)	4(11.8%)	

****including Jain, Buddhist, Sikh, and others.**

Inference

Gender is the only variable that is not significant. All other sociodemographic variables are significant with individualization. This is an especially important outcome of study, that individualization as a phenomenon is affected by different sociodemographic characteristics of workforce. The relationship of sociodemographic variables and study variables are summarized in the following table for appropriate analysis.

Table 4.35 Summary of Sociodemographic Variables relation with Study Variables

Study variables	Gender	Social Status	Religion	Educational Qualification	Place of origin	Annual Income
Job Satisfaction	<i>Not significant</i>	Significant	Significant	Significant	Significant	Significant
Role Scope	<i>Not significant</i>	<i>Not significant</i>	Significant	Significant	Significant	Significant
Value Priorities	<i>Not significant</i>	Significant	Significant	Significant	Significant	<i>Not significant</i>
Individualization of work	<i>Not significant</i>	Significant	Significant	Significant	<i>Not significant</i>	Significant

Inference

Gender as a variable is not significant with study variables. This is in contrast research in other countries as BPO is regarded as gendered workplace. Social status is not significant with role scope only. Religion and educational qualifications are significant with respect to all study variables, indicating their importance. Place of origin is not significant with individualization of work and annual income is not significant with value priorities. To summarize various relationships of sociodemographic variables with study variables, except gender other variables have good relationship; however, this must be proved through rigorous analysis.

4.6 Analysis - Relationships within Study Variables

The four study variables with respect to respondents studied are job satisfaction, role scope, value priorities, and individualization of work. These variables are classified as groups based on appropriate criteria using clustering procedure. These variables are cross tabulated to test for any relationships using chi-square test.

Job Satisfaction with Role Scope

Job satisfaction groups are cross tabulated with role scope group and the results are obtained to test the following hypotheses.

H₀8: Job satisfaction group and role scope group are independent.

H₁8: Job satisfaction group and role scope group are dependent.

Table 4.36 Cross Tabulation of Job Satisfaction Group with Role Scope Group

Groups		Role Scope Group			Total
		Low	Moderate	High	
Job satisfaction Group	Low satisfied	96	62	22	180
	Moderately satisfied	64	40	25	129
	Highly satisfied	32	70	69	171
Total		192	172	116	480

Table 4.37 Chi-Square Test for Cross Tabulation of Job Satisfaction Group with Role Scope Group

Tests	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	62.911	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	66.060	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	55.388	1	.000

Table 4.38 Directional Measures of Job Satisfaction Group with Role Scope Group

			Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal	Somers' d	Symmetric	.301	.037	8.189	.000
		Job satisfaction Dependent	+.302	.037	8.189	.000
		Role scope Dependent	+.299	.037	8.189	.000

Inference

The Pearson Chi-square (χ^2 (df =4, N=480) = 62.91, and p= .000) indicate that null hypothesis is rejected at .05 significance level and alternate hypothesis is accepted. The directional measures also indicate that the relationship is positive and moderate. Therefore, job satisfaction and role scope are dependent.

Job satisfaction with Value Priorities

Job satisfaction groups are cross tabulated with value priorities group and the results are obtained to test the following hypotheses.

H₀: Job satisfaction group and value priorities group are independent.

H₁: Job satisfaction group and value priorities group are dependent.

Table 4.39 Cross Tabulation of Job Satisfaction Group with Value Priorities Group

Job satisfaction Group		Value priorities group			Total
		Low	Moderate	High	
Job satisfaction Group	Low satisfied	88	70	22	180
	Moderately satisfied	44	57	28	129
	Highly satisfied	14	109	48	171
Total		146	236	98	480

Table 4.40 Chi-Square Test for Cross Tabulation of Job Satisfaction Group with Value Priorities Group

Tests	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	71.390	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	79.863	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	56.056	1	.000

Table 4.41 Directional Measures for Job Satisfaction Group with Value Priorities Group

			Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal	Somers' d	Symmetric	.311	.036	8.679	.000
		job satisfaction Dependent	+.320	.036	8.679	.000
		Value Priorities Dependent	+.303	.035	8.679	.000

Inference

The Pearson Chi-Square test (χ^2 (df =4, N=480) =71.39, p=.000) indicates that null hypothesis is rejected at .05 level of significance and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, job satisfaction group and value priorities group are dependent. The directional measures also indicate the relationship is positive and moderate.

Job satisfaction with Individualization of work

Job satisfaction groups are cross tabulated with individualization of work groups. The results are obtained to test the following hypotheses.

H₀10: Job satisfaction group and individualization of work group are independent.

H₁10: Job satisfaction group and individualization of work group are dependent.

Table 4.42 Cross tabulation of Job Satisfaction Group with Individualization of Work Group

		Individualization of work group			Total
		Commoners	High views low practitioner	Straight Is	
Job satisfaction group	Low	92	40	48	180
	Moderate	93	10	26	129
	High	115	6	50	171
Total		300	56	124	480

Table 4.43 Chi-Square Tests for Job Satisfaction Group with Individualization of Work Group

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	37.319	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	37.880	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.243	1	.134

Table 4.44 Directional Measures for Job Satisfaction Group and Individualization of Work Group

			Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal	Somers' d	Symmetric	-.090	.042	-2.140	.032
		Job satisfaction dependent	-.101	.047	-2.140	.032
		Individualization of work dependent	-.081	.038	-2.140	.032

Inference

The Pearson Chi-square test (χ^2 (df =4, N=480) =37.319, p=.000) indicate that null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Thus, job satisfaction group and individualization of work group are dependent. Directional measures indicate weak negative relationships.

Value priorities with Role Scope

The value priorities group and role scope group are cross-tabulated, and results are analyzed for testing following hypotheses.

H₀11: value priorities group and role scope group are independent.

H₁11: value priorities group and role scope group are dependent.

Table 4.45 Cross tabulation of Value Priorities Group with Role Scope Group

		Values priorities group			Total
		Low	Moderate	High	
Role scope group	Low	100	58	34	192
	Moderate	30	108	34	172
	High	16	70	30	116
Total		146	236	98	480

Table 4.46 Chi-Square Tests for Cross Tabulation of Value Priorities Group with Role Scope Group

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	75.578	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	76.217	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	35.466	1	.000

Table 4.47 Directional Measures of Value Priorities Group with Role Scope Group

			Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal	Somers' d	Symmetric	+.261	.041	6.354	.000
		Role scope dependent	+.267	.042	6.354	.000
Value priorities dependent		+.255	.040	6.354	.000	

Inference

Pearson Chi-Square test (χ^2 (df =4, N=480) = 75.578, p=.000) indicate that null hypothesis is rejected at .05 level of significance and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Thus, there is dependence between values and role scope. Directional measures also indicate that there is a positive moderate relationship.

Individualization of Work and Role Scope

Individualization of work group and role scope group are cross-tabulated, and results are used to test the following hypotheses.

H₀12: Individualization of work group and role scope group are independent.

H₁12: Individualization of work group and role scope group are dependent.

Table 4.48 Cross Tabulation of Individualization of Work Group with Role Scope

		Individualization of work group			Total
		Commoner	High views low Practitioner	Straight Is	
Role Scope Group	Low	110	34	48	192
	Moderate	108	16	48	172
	High	82	6	28	116
Total		300	56	124	480

Table 4.49 Chi-Square Test for Cross Tabulation of Individualization of Work Group with Role Scope

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.572	4	.009
Likelihood Ratio	13.885	4	.008
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.777	1	.183

Table 4.50 Directional Measures for Individualization of Work Group with Role Scope Group

			Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal	Somers' d	Symmetric	-.069	.041	-1.687	.002
		Role scope dependent	-.077	.046	-1.687	.002
		Individualization of work dependent	-.062	.037	-1.687	.002

Inference

Pearson Chi-Square test (χ^2 (df =4, N=480) =13.572, p=.009) indicates that null hypothesis is rejected at .05 level of significance. Individualization of work and role scope is related. Directional measures also indicate there is a negative weak relationship. The Straight Is with prominent role scope is only 22.6%, while low and moderate role scope is 38.7% each.

Value Priorities and Individualization of Work

Individualization of work group and value priorities group are cross-tabulated, and results are analyzed to test following hypotheses.

H₀13: Value priorities group and individualization of work group are independent.

H₁13: Value priorities group and individualization of work group are dependent.

Table 4.51 Cross Tabulation of Value Priorities Group with Individualization of Work Group

		Individualization of work			Total
		Commoners	High Views low practitioner	Straight Is	
Value priorities	Low	82	38	26	146
	Medium	168	12	56	236
	High	50	6	42	98
Total		300	56	124	480

Table 4.52 Chi-Square Test for Cross Tabulation of Value Priorities Group and Individualization of Work Group

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	58.045	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	52.877	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.148	1	.023

Table 4.53 Directional Measures for Value Priorities Group and Individualization of Work Group

			Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Ordinal by Ordinal	Somers' d	Symmetric	+.055	.043	1.281	.011
		Values priorities dependent	+.060	.047	1.281	.011
		Individualization of work dependent	+.051	.040	1.281	.001

Inference

Pearson Chi-Square test (χ^2 (df =4, N=480) =58.045, p=.000) indicates that null hypothesis is rejected at .05 level of significance.

Thus, value priorities and individualization of work are related. The directional measures also indicate that there is a weak positive relationship.

4.6.1 Summary -Relationships within Study Variable

The study variables and their interrelationships are given in the form of diagram and appropriate inferences are provided.

Figure 4.17 PROTOTYPICAL HUMAN RESOURCES MODEL FOR BPO ORGANIZATIONS

Inference

- 1) Value priorities have positive weak relationship with individualization of work group. This is in tune with literature survey. Persons with high individualization are likely to take decisions that have more self-enhancement content. This is indicated by higher mean value for individualization coinciding with higher value priorities.
- 2) Individualization of work and role scope have negative weak relationship indicating that higher individualization of

work trait is likely to lead to less of people orientation and expansion of influence. The low and negative correlations between individualization of work and role scope is in tune with the definition of the constructs. Does this result suggest more individualization of work means low people orientation? Further research is needed to answer the question.

- 3) Individualization of work has negative weak relationship with job satisfaction. The job in a BPO organization is team dependent and therefore a person with high individualization of work is likely to have less job satisfaction compared to his peers. In addition, the important job satisfaction dimensions are interpersonal needs oriented.
- 4) Value priorities have a positive moderate relationship with job satisfaction. As value priorities, increase there is increase in job satisfaction. Empirical research indicates that there is a relationship between value priorities and behavioural outcomes and this result supports the same.
- 5) Role Scope has positive moderate relationship with job satisfaction. Job satisfaction dimensions has four dimensions- support of family, work environment, interpersonal relations with colleagues, immediate supervisor's role/ team leader's role in motivating are considered important and interpersonal relation oriented. The higher emotional content of job satisfaction parameters explain the relation with role scope as role scope is based on motivation dimensions such as achievement, influence,

control, extension, and affiliation which are closely related to interpersonal relations.

- 6) Value priorities have positive moderate relationship with role scope group. Role scope dimensions are based on motivational factors. The motivational factors are outcomes of value priorities and the relationship is in tune with the empirical research.
- 7) Sociodemographic variables such as age, gender, social status, religion, educational qualification, place of origin and annual income are found to have effect on job satisfaction.

4.7 Goodness-of-fit Test for Job Satisfaction Model using Logistic Regression

The prototypical model (figure 4.17) needs to be subjected to rigorous testing to confirm the relationships. This is achieved with the help of logistic regression model.

4.7.1 Justification for Use of Logistic Regression

Job satisfaction is the outcome given in the model and it is influenced by sociodemographic variables, role scope, value priorities, and individualization of work according to the chi-square results. However, the relationships are to be confirmed by higher order statistical analysis. As it is observed from the table 4.9 regarding the classification of Z-cumulative values, they are classified as low, moderate, and high. However, observations of the totals of Z-values indicate that low

represents -5.361, moderate represent -2.057 and high +7.195. Thus, both low satisfaction and moderate satisfaction is combined as low satisfaction group due to their negative Z value summation scores and high satisfaction group is retained as a high satisfier without violating the inherent character. This gives rise to dichotomous outcome facilitating logistic regression. Alternatively, multinomial regression is available for three group data, in the opinion of different researchers, logistic regression provides better insights.

4.7.2 Coding of Data for Analysis

SPSS version 10 is used for the purpose of analysis. Job satisfaction is coded to as 0, 1- in such a way that zero represents the dissatisfaction of respondents and 1 represents the satisfaction of respondents, to facilitate SPSS to predict the satisfaction as it predicts the highest coded value.

The variate or value produced by logistic regression is a probability value between 0, 1. If the probability for the group membership is above a cut point (generally 0.50 is used as a cutoff point), the subject is predicted to be member of the modeled group, otherwise it is predicted as member of other group. In the present study, 0 is classified as dissatisfied and 1 as satisfied pointing to 0 will be below 0.50 and 1 will be above 0.50. For any given case, logistic regression computes the probability that

a case with a particular set of values for the independent variable is a member of the modeled category. Modeled category refers to satisfaction of the respondents.

4.7.3 Conditions for Logistic Regression

Logistic regression requires that the dependent variable to be dichotomous, and dissatisfaction and satisfaction are dichotomous in nature. The independent variable can be dichotomous or metric. If the independent variable is ordinal, it may be assumed as metric with caution. The independent variables are assumed metric without violating statistical conditionalities. Logistic regression does not require assumptions of normality, linearity, and homogeneity of variance for independent variables and in the present research, such assumption is not made. The preferred case to variable ratio is 10:1, and for hierarchical logistic regression, it is 20:1. For present research case to variable ratio is, 480:11(43.63:1) satisfying the condition of sample size.

Table 4.54 Initial Classification by Logistic Regression Analysis

			Predicted		
			Job satisfaction		Percentage Correct
Step 0	Observed		.00	1.00	
	Job satisfaction	.00	309	0	100.0
		1.00	171	0	.0
Overall Percentage					64.4

a .Constant is included in the model.

b. The cut value is .500

Inference

Analysis of the first table indicates that the satisfied employees are 171 and dissatisfied employees are 309.

The probability of satisfaction = $171/480 = 0.356$.

The probability of dissatisfaction = $309/480 = 0.644$.

In the case of logistic regression, the interest is in the odds ratio.

The odds of satisfaction = $171/309 = 0.553$.

Table 4.55 Variables in the Equation at Step Zero

		B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step 0	Constant	-.592	.095	38.533	1	.000	.553

The value of 0.553 in the step zero represents the Exp (B) Value and its antilog is

-.592 which is the B value given in the table 4.55.

The interpretation of the *odds* may be in the following order,

- (a) Employees are expected to be satisfied instead of dissatisfied in half of the trials.
- (b) Being satisfied is half-as becoming dissatisfied.

By inverting the *odds*,

- (c) Being dissatisfied is twice as likely as being satisfied.

The beginning block -2 Log Likelihood (-2LL) value is given by 625.181 which is a χ^2 value. As the independent variables enter the solution the -2LL value is likely to reduce; however, the quantum of

reduction must be significant. The change is to 599.616, with a quantum of 25.565, significant ($<.05$), which is given by table 4.56.

Goodness-of-Fit Measures

	Value
-2 Log likelihood (-2LL)	625.181

Independent Variables

The difference in the dissatisfaction and satisfaction may be caused by independent variables that comprise of sociodemographic variables and study variables. To establish the model fit there is a need to control for the effect of sociodemographic variables and then find the effect of study variables. Thus, all the independent variable's score statistic is obtained and their significance is examined.

As it can be observed educational qualification, religion, place of origin annual income, of sociodemographic variables are significant.

Table 4.56 Variables not in the Equation

Independent variables	Score statistic	Sig.
Sociodemographic Variables		
Age	.359	.549
Gender	.144	.704
Social Status	1.166	.280
Religion	7.167	.007
Educational qualification	4.055	.044
Place of origin	10.851	.001
Annual Income	5.987	.014
Study Variables		
Role scope group	60.471	.000
Value priorities group	47.584	.000
Individualization of work group	.065	.799
Role scope group and value priorities group and individualization of work group	35.111	.000
Individualization of work group and Value priorities group	10.853	.001
Role scope group and value priorities group	73.729	.000
Role scope group and Individualization of work group	24.177	.000
Overall Statistics	116.981	.000

After introduction of sociodemographic variables that are significant into logistic regression analysis solution, the -2 log likelihood value is reduced from 625.181 to 599.616 accounting for the difference of 25.565 χ^2 value. The omnibus test $\chi^2_{(df=6, N=480)} = 25.565$ is obtained and it is significant (less than .05).

Table 4.57 Overall Model Fit Goodness of Fit Measures

Change in -2 Log Likelihood					
	From Base Model			From Prior Step	
	Value	Change	Significance	Change	Significance
-2 LL	599.616	25.565	.000	25.565	.000
Cox and Snell R^2	.052				
Nagelkerke R^2	.071				
Pseudo R^2	.041				

$$\text{Pseudo } R^2 = \frac{-2LL_{\text{null}} - (-2LL_{\text{model}})}{-2LL_{\text{null}}}$$

	Value	Significance
Hosmer and Lemeshow χ^2	11.339	.183

The model summary of the indicators- Cox and Snell R^2 and Nagelkerke R^2 indicate a .052 and .071 values and Hosmer and Lemeshow test indicate $\chi^2_{(df=8, N=480)} = 11.339$, which is non significant ($>.05$) give rise to positive fit of the data.

. Table 4.58 Sociodemographic Variables in the Solution after Step 1

	Sociodemographic Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step 1	Education	.270	.177	2.315	.128	1.310
	Religion	-.341	.127	7.221	.007	.711
	Place of Origin	-.422	.144	8.608	.003	.655
	Annual Income	.139	.077	3.290	.070	1.149
	Constant	-.248	.427	.337	.561	.780

Inference

The standard error for all variables is less than 2.0 indicating that there is no multicollinearity. The null hypothesis that the B coefficient for the sociodemographic variables religion and place of origin is rejected as Wald statistic is significant at .01 level for both the variables ($< .05$). The value of Exp(B) is less than one and giving rise to negative B values indicating that respondents with higher scores in religion and place of origin (higher scores are for minorities in the case of religion and to rural persons in place of origin) are more likely to be less satisfied. The value of Exp (B) indicates one unit of rise in the odds of religion pointing to respondents being satisfied is reduced due to less than 1 value in the Exp (B). In the case of education and annual income, the Wald statistic is not significant. However, the annual income significance is .070 indicating that it may be considered for practical significance as the value is nearer to .050. If this argument is accepted then for Exp (B) value of 1.149 may be interpreted as for an increase of one unit in income the modeled variable that is satisfaction is likely to go up by 14.9%.

Table 4.59 Classification Table for Sociodemographic Variables Effect on Job Satisfaction ^a

			Predicted		
			Job satisfaction		Percentage Correct
Step 1	Observed		.00	1.00	
	Job satisfaction	.00	287	22	92.9
		1.00	155	16	9.4
Overall Percentage					63.1

a. The cut value is .500

4.7.4 Study Variables and their Interaction Variables in the Solution

The study variables consisting of role scope, value priorities and individualization of work and interaction variables in the form of role scope *value priorities- role scope * individualization of work – value priorities * individualization of work and role scope *value priorities * individualization of work are entered into the solution.

	Value
-2 Log likelihood (-2LL)	490.733

Table 4.60 Overall Model Fit Goodness of Fit Measures

Change in -2 Log Likelihood					
	From Base Model			From Prior Step	
	Value	Change	Significance	Change	Significance
-2 LL	490.733	134.448	.000	108.883	.000
Cox and Snell R^2	.244				
Nagelkerke R^2	.336				
Pseudo R^2	.215				

$$\text{Pseudo } R^2 = -2LL_{\text{null}} - (-2LL_{\text{model}}) / -2LL_{\text{null}}$$

	Value	Significance
Hosmer and Lemeshow χ^2	13.443	.097

The model summary of the indicators- Cox and Snell R^2 and Nagelkerke R^2 indicate a .244 and .336 values and Hosmer and Lemeshow test indicate $\chi^2_{(df=8, N=480)}=13.443$, which is non significant ($>.05$) give rise to positive fit of the data.

Table 4.61 Study Variables and Interaction Variables in the Equation in Step 2

Study Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Education	.306	.201	2.310	.129	1.358
Religion	-.331	.142	5.431	.020	.719
Place of origin	-.577	.154	14.014	.000	.561
Annual income	.058	.089	.415	.519	1.059
Role scope group	3.744	1.099	11.609	.001	42.282
Value priorities group	4.223	1.034	16.675	.000	68.246
Individualization of work group	1.916	1.146	2.796	.049	6.794
IN group * RS group *VA group	.518	.249	4.327	.038	1.679
Individualization of work group* value priorities group	-1.177	.508	5.360	.021	.308
Role scope group * Value priorities group	-1.601	.499	10.275	.001	.202
Role scope group * Individualization of work group	-.821	.574	2.045	.153	.440
Constant	-9.338	2.332	16.039	.000	.000

Inference

The standard error for all variables is less than 2.0 indicating that there is no multicollinearity. However, the standard error for constant is not considered. The null hypothesis that the B coefficient for the study variables role scope group, value priorities group, individualization of work group, interaction groups of Ingroup*RS group*VA group, individualization of work * value priorities group and role scope * value

priorities are rejected as Wald statistic is significant for all the variables ($< .05$) at .01 level of significance. The greater than 1 Exp (B) value indicates that role scope group, value priorities group, individualization of work group and the inter action group IN group*RS group*VA group have a positive impact on the odds of satisfaction. These observations indicate that for a unit change in these variables, there is significant positive change in the odds of satisfaction. However, individualization of work group * value priorities group has negative impact. These negative values suggest there may be mediated or moderated effects for some of the variables.

The study variables are classified according to the three different states of clusters indicating that higher states are likely to have higher levels of odds of satisfaction. This is in tune with the theoretical model suggested. However, Individualization of work is propositioned to have negative impact on the satisfaction has no evidence in the present test. In the case of Individualization of work group* value priorities group and Role scope group * Value priorities group, The value of Exp(B) is less than one and gives rise to negative B values indicating that their effect is negative on the odds of satisfaction.

Table 4.62 Classification Table with Study Variables and Interaction Variables in the final solution ^a

		Predicted		
		Job satisfaction		Percentage Correct
Observed		.00	1.00	
Job satisfaction	.00	256	53	82.8
	1.00	82	89	52.0
Overall Percentage				71.9

a. The cut value is .500

4.7.5 Predictive Accuracy

The bench mark that is used to characterize logistic regression model as useful is 25% improvement over the rate of accuracy achieved by chance alone.

The chance prediction is given by $= .356^2 + .644^2 = .54147$, which is 54.15%.

An increase of 25% is given by $54.15 * 1.25 = 67.68\%$. Thus, the predictive accuracy should be equal to or greater than threshold value of 67.68%. For the present study, the predictive accuracy is 71.9% indicating that there is good prediction accuracy.

4.7.6 Validation Analysis

The samples are randomly split into 80% -20%, while 80% represent the training sample and 20% representing the holdout sample. The baseline logistic regression is rerun-using method for including variables identified in the research.

The different measures adhered to the significance levels and Hosmer and Lemeshow Test is not significant. The following final classification matrix is obtained.

Table 4.63 Classification Matrix of Randomly Selected Cases and Holdout Sample Cases ^c for Validation

		Predicted Group Membership					
		Randomly Selected Cases Analysis ^a			Holdout Sample ^b		
		Job satisfaction		Percentage Correct	Job satisfaction		Percentage Correct
Observed		.00	1.00		.00	1.00	
Job satisfaction	.00	211	40	84.1	51	7	87.9
	1.00	55	80	59.3	19	17	47.2
Overall Percentage				75.4			72.3

a. Randomly 386 selected cases for training sample.

b. Holdout 94 sample cases.

c. The cut value is .500

Inference

The criteria to support the classification accuracy of the model is an accuracy rate for the holdout sample that is no more than 10% lower than the accuracy rate for the training sample. The accuracy rate for the random training sample is 75.4%, making the minimum threshold requirement for the holdout sample equal to 67.86% (0.90 x 75.4%). The accuracy rate for the holdout sample is 72.3%, which satisfied the minimum requirement. The classification accuracy for the analysis of the full data set is supported.

4.7.7 Outliers and Influential Cases

Logistic regression models the relationship between a set of independent variables and the probability that a case is a member of one of the categories of the dependent variable. If the probability is greater than 0.5, the case is classified in the modeled category. If the probability is less than 0.50, the case is classified in the other category. The actual probability of the modeled event for any case is either 1.0 or 0.0, i.e., a case is in the modeled category, or it is not. The residual is the difference between the actual probability and the predicted probability for a case. If the predicted probability for a case that belonged to the modeled category were 0.80, the residual would be $1.00 - 0.80 = 0.20$. The residual can be standardized by dividing it by an estimate of its standard deviation. Since the dependent variable is dichotomous or binary, the standard deviation for proportions is used. If a case has a standardized residual larger than 2.0 or smaller than -2.0, it is considered an outlier, and a candidate for exclusion from the analysis. In the present research, the outliers that are more than 2 standardized residual are requested from SPSS and it indicated that there are five cases. Since the numbers of outliers are 1.04% of the total cases, it may be ignored.

Table 4.64 Case-wise List of Outliers

	Selected Status	Observed	Predicted	Predicted Group	Temporary Variable	
Case		Job satisfaction			Residual	Z-Residual
29	S	1**	.037	0	.963	5.106
150	S	1**	.121	0	.879	2.695
283	S	1**	.126	0	.874	2.628
307	S	1**	.126	0	.874	2.628
450	S	1**	.127	0	.873	2.624

a. S = Selected, U = Unselected cases, and ** = Misclassified cases.

b. Cases with studentized residuals greater than 2.000 are listed.

4.8 Summary of findings and human resources model for BPO organizations

The study was undertaken with primary purpose of finding job satisfaction among BPO employees to address the issue of job attrition. For this purpose, social forecasting is used as a methodology. The workforce of BPO industry is youthful, at a mean age of 25.87 years and median age of 25 years, single (65.8%), with 42.1% of female members. The engineering and postgraduates occupy largest segment with 56.6% spread among nine major areas with 26 sub areas. The skill set required for different work areas are different and employees are required to learn new skills and some leverage is provided for interaction with customers. Gender, social class, and religion are dependent on work area; however, there is no stereotypical employment pattern of female members of crowding in voice and consumer services; lower social class and minorities occupy lower end of services.

There are four study variables; job satisfaction an outcome or dependent variable, role scope, value priorities and individualization are independent variables. Gender was not a discriminating feature with all study variables, indicating that in the work place is not gendered as observed in different research studies (Steinberg and Figart, 1999, Leidner, 1999, Salzinger, 2003, Mirchandani, 2004). Religion and place of origin are the important social variables found to have a role in job satisfaction albeit with minorities and rural persons experiencing lower satisfaction. Job satisfaction was quantitatively partitioned into three progressively increasing sets and found to have relationship with other study variables. The qualitative partitioning is work logistics, expressive cycle, and instrumental cycle nature of job satisfaction provided different facet for analysis. Value priorities latent constructs are identified and subjected to further analysis to find general typology of employee as experimenters. Similarly for individualization of work it has been found that the employees aspiring to have substantive, functional and procedural individualization in that order. A prototypical model was proposed for preliminary investigation. It has been observed that in this model individualization has negative weak relationship. However, empirical finding could not substantiate this contention. Based on the logistic

regression analysis the prototypical model is modified and following model is suggested.

HUMAN RESOURCES MODEL FOR BPO ORGANIZATIONS

Figure 4.18 Human Resources Model for BPO organizations

Role scope, value priorities and individualization of work has positive relationship with job satisfaction. As the role scope increases job satisfaction also increases. Similarly, an increase in value profile and individualization of work of employees increases job satisfaction.

Chapter 5: Recommendation s and suggestions

Chapter Overview

This chapter presents major findings in the context of economic, technological, political issues. The managerial implication of suggestions are delineated. Finally, topics for future research are suggested.

5.1 Recommendation

The present study is on job attrition of BPO employees and solutions to increase job satisfaction and increase retention. Social forecasting is used as a methodology to address the issue. The industry operates in environment that is a function of economic, demographic, political, and technological aspects. The context of BPO industry in these dimensions must be discerned before providing any solution.

5.1.1 Global Competitiveness, Economic, Political, and Technological Issues (2009-2014)

The BPO industry growth and expansion depends on the economic growth of United States of America, UK, and Europe. Three crucial factors need to be taken into account; the competitiveness issues, economic scenario, and political scenario. As it has been observed the cost competitiveness for India is highest with employees cost only to the extent of 38% while global employee cost is 65%. The individual wage

is also 2,667 \$ per annum²⁶, which is lowest compared to recently developed economies. Regarding service competitiveness reports (D'Cruz and Noronha, 2007) indicated that workforce has measured up to global standards. However, such low level of wages-combined with expectation of high service level may not be sustainable in long run.

Even if they reach at least the index of recently developed economies of paying approximately three times present salary- 8,958\$ still Indian industry will be able to retain its long-term competitiveness. Present research also indicated that higher salary is likely to increase the instrumental cycle²⁷ of employees and compensate for the emotional labour in the process increasing retention rates. Similarly, annual salary was found to be an effective discriminator for job satisfaction.

The next issue is economic issues- first relating to the downturn in the United States of America, United Kingdom, and European countries. The economic forecast indicated that it is likely to be reversed from the year 2010. The second relating to continued sustainability of outsourcing of work from these countries to India. Accepting that there is going to be reversal of economic downturn, the demographic indicators in these countries indicate that large workforce may not be available and may have to rely on countries

²⁶ Ibid., p.18.

²⁷ Ibid., p.87,130.

such as India and China. However, China to reach competitiveness of English speaking capability with India in short run (comprising of next five years) may not be possible. The work force requirements with respect to outsourcing, United States Department of Labour, and Forrester Research Inc.²⁸ data indicate that there is going to be good opportunity for next five years. With demographic advantage and competitiveness, the BPO industry can look forward for sustained growth rates and expansion. The globalization process which is driving the prices down keep the competitive pressure on organizations to cut costs and may not respond to any political backlash in the form of not exporting jobs. The prime reason is that the nature of economy has changed to that of net work economy and such political steps may not percolate to business realities. However, one relevant factor is that jobs are taken away from poorer sections of the society in advanced countries with good social security net and transferred to low wage country with no social security and other benefits to employees gives rise to issue of free trade versus fair trade. The transfer of low-tech jobs will be meaningful only if they are played in level playing field and in the case of BPO industry, it is not level playing field for economies with social commitment. Technological forecasting, accepting the Kondratieff long

²⁸ Ibid., p.40.

wave phenomena²⁹, indicate that the long wave started in the year 1970 and we are in the consolidation phase where the technological innovations are utilized rather than innovated at least for the period of forecast from 2009-2014. The consolidation phase of technology is most appropriate technological phase for BPO industry. Therefore, economic, political, or technological challenges for BPO industry may be limited. With this framework, the researcher suggests increase in salary not only to retain talent but also to attract talent. The salary increase with simultaneous investment in infrastructure³⁰ by BPO organizations in states like Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, and Bihar where there is no significant presence of BPO industry is recommended. The typology of BPO organization is also unstable³¹ in long run. The potency of involvement and priority of commitment of employee required is high at the cost of social life of the employee. There is a need to address these two issues as the employees are found to be high on tradition and conformity³² with respect to value priorities. As the employee progresses in age the social commitments and social obligations increase and there should be provision for the same in human resource policy of BPO organization.

²⁹ Ibid ., p.46.

³⁰ Ibid., p.49.

³¹ Ibid., p.89.

³² Ibid., p. 148.

5.1.2 Human Resources Model for BPO Organization

In this section, the model suggested and its implications are discussed. The model suggested for BPO organization indicates the role of sociodemographic variables. Religion and place of origin³³ are found to have effect on the job satisfaction. The minorities especially Muslims and persons from rural areas are less represented compared to their numerical strength. Industry may consider this as a social obligation and should ensure that the disparities are reduced, by way of offering training to these sections of society. Graduates from arts and science background may be trained in their last year of graduation so that they will be industry ready from date of graduation. Such academic-industry interaction will help to spread the knowledge about the industry.

5.1.3 Role Scope

The job design, which is embedded in the technological process, gives rise to lower role scope. Present research indicates that the employees have internalized the aspect of strict conformity³⁴. Emotional coping is addressed by way of creating fun³⁵ atmosphere by way of partying, late night picnics. This has been termed by sociologists as fragility of fun as it is not going to unwind a person from the tough work atmosphere. It will work towards

³³ Ibid., p.179.

³⁴ Ibid., p.139.

³⁵ Ibid., p . 61.

lesser support from family. Family support is one of the important dimensions of job satisfaction and female employees consider it as one of the important dimensions of job satisfaction. At the same time, the night work give rise to poor health and partying may not help the health and family dimension of values. The circular effect of such short-term quick fix solutions may lead to long time dissatisfaction and job attrition. Emotional coping may be addressed with the help of forming small groups to discuss work related issues, provide solutions, and share information. In this regard, research indicates that opportunities to use knowledge³⁶ are considered as one of the important dimensions of job satisfaction.

5.1.4 Individualization of work

The relationship between individualization of work, value priorities, and role scope is one of the ambivalence when analyzing the BPO industry. The human resources mission is to integrate individuals by facilitating them to share a collective interest. Similarly, when knowledge is shared throughout the organization then it can achieve the status of learning organization (Nonaka, Takeuchi, and Umemoto, 1996; Prahalad and Hammel, 1990). Suggestion of inclusion of individualization of work into human resources domain appears to be paradoxical.

³⁶ Ibid., p .126.

Keen examination of individualization of work dimensions indicate;(a) moving away from collective mechanism for wages; (b) lifetime learning and job autonomy;(c) global performance norms;(d) personal identity;(e) preference for borderless work geography; and(f) positive job hopping. Do these findings signify that he or she is prepared for intensification of work, acceptance of risk, responsibility by asking for more autonomy and responsible for their own development? The answer to this question is affirmation. In the case of BPO organizations, employees experience multiple sources of loyalty (identity to BPO or to the client serviced?) and commitment as well as feeling of insecurity and destabilization (Marchington *et al.*, 2005) giving rise to issue of commitment and trust. Will individualization of work address these issues? The dimensions of individualization of work provide answer only to a certain extent.

The managerial implication of introducing this dimension into human resources practices is to have a departure from existing pattern of working with respect to substantive individualization and functional individualization. An observation of different contracts and wage increases indicate there is no place for collective bargaining and procedural individualization to a certain extent has taken place. For functional and

substantive individualization performance appraisal and management control aspects need to be considered. The job strain in the form of high demands, low job latitude and less social support³⁷ must be addressed with creating an atmosphere of high trust environment. For building an organization with high trust environment it is suggested to combine these initiatives with that of value inculcation initiatives.

5.1.5 Value Priorities

The values have two facets; rationality, by which a person determine why they should adopt certain values; and virtuality, by which persons develop their ability to live by these values. The values imply the development of the ability to correctly evaluate reality, consider its outcomes, experience the satisfaction, and retain the learning on self and effect of it on others. The value typology of employees indicates they are experimenters with focus on tradition and conformity. They are experimenting with unique way of looking at work and life in a non-traditional way, which is different from what their parents have experienced. In the BPO setting, the fun culture to ameliorate the anxiety and tension will only lead to dysfunctional outcomes, in the form of less focus on health and family. This in turn have an impact on job satisfaction.

³⁷ Ibid., p.181.

The expectation of employees is to obtain and use knowledge to experience satisfaction- the focus of organization is stick to talk time and simpler tasks and not to ask for more. Similarly, the stimulation value at work place is low devoid of any challenges. Value inculcation that promotes health awareness, increasing aesthetic values by providing environment appreciation focus, being flexible with social obligations of employees to have better work-life balance, promotion of thrift, increasing business awareness are some of the ways to increase the value priorities. An increase in value priorities³⁸ empirically established in the present research increases the job satisfaction more than any other variable. Ethical working norms and low tolerance for unethical practices will provide employees enhanced self-concept. Values will be a good stance for the management to increase job satisfaction and stop job attrition.

5.2 Conclusion

The research is concluded with the note that enhancing value priorities, incorporation of individualization of work in to human resource practices and enhancing role scope will improve job satisfaction and reduce job attrition in BPO organizations.

³⁸ Ibid., p.181.

As the social forecasting output indicates, the industry is likely to be stable and growing and persons can aspire for a career.

5.3 Suggestion for Future Research

Based on the study the following suggestions are provided.

- 1) Personality variables and their effect on value priorities and job satisfaction.
- 2) Study of work place disorders in consultation with occupational physicians.
- 3) Organizational culture and its relationship with value priorities and job satisfaction.
- 4) Network economy and its effect on BPO employees value priorities and job satisfaction.
- 5) Emotional labour and its effect on value priorities.
- 6) Comparative study of value priorities between BPO employees and Information technology employees.
- 7) Social forecasting- a cross impact analysis for BPO industry.
- 8) Role of gender in managing stress in BPO industry.
- 9) Attitude towards work of BPO employees.

APPENDIX 1

Questionnaire

Respected Sir/Madam,

I am carrying out a study on Social Forecasting: Evolving a model for Business Process Outsourcing Industry, as a part of my doctoral dissertation for Aligarh Muslim University. I would appreciate if you will please convey your views on the different questions referred to in this schedule. Information provided by you is only for academic purpose and all information provided by you will be kept confidential. Thank you very much for sparing your valuable time and co-operation.

K.Prabhakar

Demographic Details

Name:

Organization:

Age:

Gender: M/F

Social status: OC/BC/OBC/SC/ST

Religion: Hindu/Muslim/Jain/Sikhism/ Buddhist/Christian/others (please specify)

Educational Qualifications:

UG/PG PROGRAMME	TICK APPROPRIATE CELL
BA (Humanities, languages)	
Bcom	
BBA	
BBM	
BSc	
MSc	
MCA	
BE	
ME	
MBA	
Others (Please specify)	

Martial Status: **Married/Not married/separated**

Place of origin:

Urban/semi urban/rural

Present salary per annum-Please tick in the appropriate column

Less than 2 Lakhs		4Lakhs-5 lakhs	
2lakhs-3lakhs		5lakhs-6lakhs	
3lakhs-4lakhs		More than 6 lakhs	

Please indicate by ticking

Education and occupation of father	Education and occupation of mother
Primary education/+2/undergraduate /post graduate/professional/doctorate	Primary education/+2/undergraduate /post graduate/professional/doctorate
Government/private sector/public sector/doctor/lawyer/professor/farmer Unemployed	Government/private sector/public sector/doctor/lawyer/professor/stay-at-home spouse

Please indicate the area you are working*

Finance and Accounting	
Sales and Marketing	
Human Resources	
Knowledge Services	
Consumer Services	
Technical Support	
Survey	
Research and Development	
Engineering and Design	
Others	

* If you have worked in multiple areas indicate area you worked for longest period

1) Please indicate your satisfaction level with the following factors of employment

- (1) Highly dissatisfied
- (2) Dissatisfied to a considerable extent
- (3) Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- (4) Satisfied to a considerable extent
- (5) Totally satisfied

DIMENSIONS OF JOB SATISFACTION	1	2	3	4	5
1. Salary					
2. Timing of work					
3. Changes in job					
4. Night travel					
5. Shift system					
6. Opportunities to learn					
7. Opportunities to go abroad					
8. Benching					
9. Support of family					
10. Opportunity to use knowledge					
11. Work environment					
12. Interpersonal relations with colleagues					
13. Western culture at work place					
14. Immediate supervisors/team leaders role in motivating you					

Segments of Work Area	
Finance and accounting	
Logistics and supply chain management	
Sales and Marketing	
Human resources	
Knowledge services	
Customer care and help desk	
Customer service	
Technical support	
.Product support	
Pay role processing	
Voice out-bound sales campaigns	
Telemarketing	
Surveys	
Schedule changes	
Equity financial insurance research data search integration and management	

Research and information services in human resources	
Market research and competitive intelligence	
Engineering and design	
Animation and simulation services	
Para legal content and services	
Medical content and services	
Biotech and pharmaceuticals	
Research and development	

Role Satisfaction

2) Your role may provide you with opportunities for varied factors in different degrees. Read each statement carefully. Then indicate under how much opportunity your role in your organization provides for that dimension. Please use the following numbers to indicate your reply:

1. Means about no opportunity,
2. Means extraordinarily little opportunity
3. Means some opportunity
4. Means quite a good deal of opportunity
5. Means great deal of opportunity

DIMENSIONS OF JOB	1	2	3	4	5
1. Do something challenging and worthwhile.					
2. Influence or make an impact on others.					
3. Admonish (punish) those who do not conform.					
4. Work with friendly people.					
5. Do something useful for others.					
6. Get immediate feedback on your performance.					
7. Have autonomy and work independently.					
8. Direct and instruct people below you.					
9. Develop close personal relations.					
10. Develop your junior colleagues or subordinates.					
11. Set standards of excellence.					
12. Give ideas or suggestions to your superiors.					
13. Control the people below you.					
14. Share feelings and emotions with others.					
15. Help others.					
16. Show that efficiency can be rewarded.					
17. Make contributions to significant decisions.					

18. Admonish (punish) those who do not perform.					
19. Interact with colleagues.					
20. Cooperate with others in a common task.					
21. Stretch your abilities and skills.					
22. Get recognition for work done.					
23. Get regular reports from other sections or subordinates.					
24. Interact with others on non-task matters.					
25. Work in teams.					

Values

3. Instructions: Please read each of the statements given. Please give your answer with the following scale

- (1) Totally disagree
- (2) Disagree to a considerable extent
- (3) Neither agree nor disagree
- (4) Agree to a considerable extent
- (5) Totally agree

Statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. Current working style leads to a comfortable life					
2. Excitement in work is least important					
3. Work style must act as stimulant to active life					
4. Work is to satisfy fulfilling life					
5. Work must lead to lasting contribution to the society					
6. A world of peace is possible in the global environment					
7. Beauty and aesthetic values have no role in global economy					
8. Competition is the only attribute associated with development					
9. Work environment offers equal opportunity for all					
10. Brotherhood has a major place in workplace					
11. The current working conditions lead to less care of loved ones					
12. Family is not the most important concept in the global environment					
13. Personal advancement comes above all other conditions					
14. Personal life in work does not guarantee freedom of choice					
15. Current working requires for more individual contribution					
16. Health considerations are not especially important					
17. Preventive health care is not workable in 365*24*7 work Environment					
18. There is little room for personal jealousy in the work place					
19. There is no meaning in talking about morality in personal relations					

20. Constrained interpersonal relations lead to lower output					
21. National security is more important in dealing with work					
22. Leisurely pursuits are directed towards pleasure rather than salvation					
23. Self respect is upheld in workplace					
24. No time left for developing true friendship					
25. Wisdom is not the important word associated with work and development					
26. Aspirations and work has no relation					
27. There is no need for challenging work					
28. There is no need to develop special capabilities for BPO					
29. Broadmindedness need not be an important quality in work					
30. Competency in subjects studied has no relevance					
31. Personal beliefs have no place in current work					
32. Team discussion and solution replace fault finding and admonishing					
33. BPO gives room for mutual help and welfare					
34. We cannot be dishonest in BPO related work					
35. Individual responsibility is the top most concern in BPO workers					
36. Self reliance is more demanded					
37. Intellectual pursuits pave way for acquiring intelligence					
38. Elevated level of intelligence is not required in BPO					
39. Life becomes more mechanical					
40. Love and affection are slowly vanishing					
41. Obedience and politeness are replaced by self respect and decency					
42. Self discipline is the most desired quality					

Individualization

Please indicate your agreement and disagreement with respect to each statement in the following scale: (Indicate by way of tick)

- (1) Agree totally
- (2) Agree to a certain extent
- (3) Neither agree nor disagree
- (4) Disagree to a certain extent
- (5) Totally disagree

S.NO	STATEMENTS	1	2	3	4	5
1.	To perform well I must work like an entrepreneur taking decision and being responsible for the same.					
2.	I am provided with required job training by my organization.					
3.	Flexibility of job will help me to grow.					
4.	Mobility in jobs to different locations is a learning experience.					
5.	Unstructured jobs are preferred by me.					
6.	Flexible timings in job are preferred by me.					
7.	Unions are irrelevant for BPO industry.					
8.	Life time learning is one of the most important dimensions of job.					
9.	I like multiple demands on me by job as it provides me better exposure.					
10.	When I reflect on my work, I feel inner emptiness.					
11.	I prefer a flat organization with low hierarchy.					
12.	I prefer to do a task in my own way even if it takes longer period.					
13.	International culture ensures better performance.					
14.	Changing jobs is good for my career.					
15.	International exposure is provided in the work environment.					
16.	If I am faced with work related issue, I prefer to deal it myself.					

17.	Since no two persons are same, the work also must be designed to the competence of the employee.					
18.	Long hours of work are necessary to meet customer needs.					
19.	I take ownership for my work.					
20.	I feel easy with myself if I am asked to have different values from what I have in the work place.					
21.	I often do work in my own way.					
22.	I prefer visibility to achieve personal goals.					
23.	I rely on myself totally for any job related issues.					
24.	My personal identity is most important for me.					
25.	When other does better than me I get tense and aroused.					
26.	I prefer working for my company as consultant if it is helpful to my career.					
27.	Copyrights must be registered in my name though I work for organization.					
28.	I prefer quitting organization if my productivity is not to the expectations.					
29.	Provident Fund and other social security measures are no more relevant for BPO industry.					
30.	I prefer government not to involve into the BPO industry.					
31.	In BPO industry it is not Indian or American culture, it is global culture.					
32.	I have developed my own values after joining my job.					
33.	Job security is not important.					
34.	I like working with virtual colleagues.					
35.	Individual employment contracts are better than uniform contracts for jobs.					
36.	Since two jobs are not the same, the salary also must take this into account.					

Appendix 2

Value Carriers

Uprights	Being traditional	Fidelity	Materialism
	Old-fashioned people who mean it when they say "You must!" and "You must not!". The Upright are patriotic and often suspicious of strangers and immigrants. They hate inflation and love law and order. As consumers they are cautious and apprehensive about experimenting. They like tried and true products.		
Folks	Being traditional	Fidelity	Humanism
	The Folks are more concerned with family and relatives than with the material base of existence; old-fashioned religion thrives here. As with the Uprights, love of the home community and the preservation of its traditions and surrounding nature are important concerns. Service to the next of kin is self-evident. When buying they often follow the advice of their long-time local retailer.		
Matter-of-Fact	Being traditional	Instrumentality	Materialism
	In this segment one seeks practical and technical rather than traditional solutions. Do-it-yourself is common. Your car and residence, not only your family, signal who you are. As consumers The-matter-of-fact are more ambitious than the Uprights and the Folks. They are not trendy; often they go for big brands and standard products.		
Belongers	Being traditional	Instrumentality	Humanism
	These sociable but old-fashioned people believe that friends and clubs, not only family and possessions, signal your identity. In joint efforts they have learned to influence their conditions. As consumers they may like to bargain pleasantly in looking for value for money.		
Advocates	Becoming modern	Fidelity	Materialism
	Here are the people who like the comfort of modern living but do not use material goods as status symbols. They are convinced of the merits of their values and want to change society to correspond to their values, not to adjust themselves to		

	society. They are pro-environment and anti-commercialism. They are big consumers but they are usually suspicious of advertising.		
Zealous	Becoming Modern	Fidelity	Humanism
	Emotion and intuition and empathy are meaningful for the Zealous. Like the Advocates they question tradition, hierarchy, and authority. They embrace not only environmental and Third-world causes as the Advocates but are also stronger on issues such as peace, feminism, multi-culturalism, gay rights, and/or animal rights. They are overly critical consumers who tend to look for personal experiences rather than material things in the market place.		
Daredevils	Becoming Modern	Instrumentality	Materialism
	Unafraid of the complexity of life they look for and enjoy challenge, e.g., entrepreneurship, risky lifestyles in sports and/or in financial markets. Their bonds to products, causes, and people may, however, be short-lived. They continually ask, "What works for me?" and are ready to discard anything that is no longer flashy, profitable, or useful. They are very interested in the technical features of the hardware they buy, but volatile in their pursuit of fashion in clothing, of cars, and of interior design.		
Minglers	Becoming Modern	Instrumentality	Humanism
	Trendy networkers thriving on cosmopolitan contacts and markets. Eating an ethnic dish a day is a matter of course. Interest in new expressions of personal life is intense. In their way of living they often like to combine familiar fragments in unexpected ways as in a music video. The Minglers are sophisticated consumers, more interested in software than hardware.		
Centerites			
	They have mean scores of all value dimensions. Methodologically they are uncertain to classify. They represent the minority who has average values on all dimensions.		

References

- Agarwal, R., & Hoetker, G. (2007). A Faustian bargain? The growth of management and its relationship with related disciplines. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(6), 1304-1322.
- Alferoff, C., & Knights, D. (2001). We are all partying here: target and games, or target as games in call centre management. Paper presented at the Second Critical Management Studies Conference.
- Allport, F.H. (1962). A structural conception of behaviour: Individual and collective. Structural theory and the expert problem of social psychology. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 64, 3-30.
- Allport, G.W., Vernon, P.E., & Lindzey, G. (1961). Study of values. Manual and test booklet (3rd Edition.). Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Almeida, A. J. (2007). Employability, work contexts and labour market in Portugal, *Educational Sciences Journal*, 3, 51-58.
- Altemeyer, B. (1988). Enemies of freedom: Understanding right-wing authoritarianism. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Altvater, E., & Mahnkopf, B. (1997). Grenzen der Globalisierung. Ökonomie, Ökologie und Politik in der Weltgesellschaft. Münster.
- Alvarez, I., and Kilbourn, B. (2002). Mapping the information society literature: topics, perspectives, and root metaphors. (www.firstmonday.org)
- Ang, S., Van Dyne, L., & Begley, T.M. (2003). The employment relationships of foreign workers versus local employees: A field study of organizational justice, job satisfaction, performance, and OCB. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 24, 561-583.
- Argandoña, A. (2001). Algunas tesis para un debate sobre los valores, *Revista Empresa y Humanismo*, 1.

- Argandoña, A. (2002). *Fostering Values in Organizations*, Barcelona: IESE Business School-University de Navarra, RP No. 483. (Accessed from www.ssrn.com June 2007)
- Arnopoulos, P. (1979). Toward a model procedure for social forecasting, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 13, 31-42.
- Aronson, E. (1992). The return of the repressed: Dissonance theory makes a comeback. *Psychological Inquiry*, 3, 303-311
- Arunachalam, S. (1999). Information and knowledge in the age of electronic communication: A developing country perspective. *Journal of Information Science*, 25, 465.
- Asher, G.M., & Nandy, A. (2007). Demographic Complementarities and Outsourcing: Implications for India, *IIMB Management Review*, June 2007.
- Babakus, E., Cravens, D. W., Johnston, M., & Moncrief, W. C. 1999. The role of emotional exhaustion in sales force attitude and behavior relationships. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 27, 58–70.
- Baccili, P. A. (2003). ‘Company and Manager Psychological Contract Violations: What Difference does it make who violates the Contract?’ *Proceedings of the Academy of Management Annual Meeting*, Denver, CO.
- Bagozzi, P. R., & Edwards, R. J. (1998). A general approach for representing constructs in organizational research, *Organizational Research Methods*, 1, 45-87.
- Bagozzi, P. R., & Edwards, R. J. (1998). A general approach for representing constructs in organizational research, *Organizational Research Methods*, 1, 45-87.
- Bain, P., & Taylor, P. (2000). Entrapped by the ‘electronic panopticon’? Worker resistance in the call centre. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 15, 2–18.

- Bain, P., & Taylor, P. (2002a). Ringing the changes? Union recognition and organization in call centres in the UK finance sector. *Industrial Relations Journal*, 33, 246–261.
- Bain, P., & Taylor, P. (2002b). Consolidation, ‘cowboys’ and the developing employment relationship in British, Dutch, and US call centres. In Holtgrewe, U., Kerst, C. and Shire, K. (Eds.), *Re-Organizing Service Work: Call Centres in Germany and Britain*. Aldershot, UK: Ashgate.
- Bain, P., Watson, A., Mulvey, G., Taylor, P. & Gall, G. (2002). Taylorism, targets and the pursuit of quantity and quality by call centre management. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 17, 170–185.
- Bakker, A.B., Demerouti, E., & Schaufeli, W.B. (2003). Dual processes at work in a call centre: An application of the demands-resources model. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 12(4), 393-417.
- Baldamus, W. (1961). *Efficiency and Effort*. London: Tavistock.
- Baldry, C., Bain, P. & Taylor, P. (1998). ‘Bright satanic offices’: intensification, control, and Team Taylorism. In Thompson, P. & Warhurst, C. (Eds), *Workplaces of the Future*. Basingstoke: Palgrave.
- Bardi, A., & Schwartz S.H. (2002) Values and Behaviour: Strength and Structure of Relations, *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, Vol. 29, p. 1209.
- Bargh, J.A., Chaiken, S., Govender, R., & Pratto, F. (1992). The generality of the automatic attitude evaluation effect. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 62, 893-912.
- Barth, James R. (2008). The US housing and financial meltdown: what happened and what has been the response, India Programme, Office of International Information Programme, US Department of State, November 28 to December 19, 2008.
- Batt, R. & Moynihan, L. (2002). The viability of alternative call centre production models, *Human Resource Management Journal*, 12, 4, 14-34.

- Batt, R. (1999) .Work Organization, Technology, and Performance in Customer Service and Sales. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review* 52(4), 539–64.
- Batt, R., & Moynihan, L. (2002). The viability of alternative call centre production models. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 12, 14–34.
- Batt, R., (2002).Managing Customer Services: Human resource practices, quit rates and sales growth, *Academy of Management Journal*, 45(3), 587-597.
- Batt, R., Doellgast, V., & Kwon, H. (2006). Service management and employment systems in U.S. and Indian call centres. In Collins, S. and Brainard, L. (Eds.), *Offshoring White-Collar Work*. Washington, D.C.: Brookings Press.
- Beck, R. C. (1990). *Motivation theories and principles*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Beck, U., (1992). *Risk Society. Towards a New Modernity*. London, Newbury Park, New Delhi: Sage.
- Beck, U., Elizabeth, B., & Gernsheim. (2001). *Individualization: Institutionalized Individualism and its Social and Political Consequences*. (Sage, London).
- Beck, U., Giddens, A., & Lash, S. (1996). *Reflexive Modernisierung. Eine Kontroverse*. Frankfurt a.M.: Suhrkamp.
- Beck, Ulrich & Bonß, Wolfgang (2001). *Die Modernisierung der Moderne*. Frankfurt a.M.: Suhrkamp. Beck, Ulrich & Sopp, Peter (Eds.) (1997). *Individualisierung und Integration. Neue Konfliktlinien und neuer Integrationsmodus?* Opladen: Leske + Budrich.
- Beck, Ulrich (1986). *Risikogesellschaft. Auf dem Weg in eine andere Moderne*. Frankfurt a. M.: Suhrkamp.
- Beck, Ulrich (1994). *Jenseits von Stand und Klasse?* In Ulrich Beck & Elisabeth Beck-Gernsheim (Eds.), *Risikante Freiheiten. Individualisierung in modernen Gesellschaften* (pp.43-60). Frankfurt a. M.: Suhrkamp.

- Beck, Ulrich and Beck-Gernsheim, Elisabeth (1993). Nicht Autonomie, sondern Bastelbiographie. Anmerkungen zur Individualisierungsdiskussion am Beispiel des Ansatzes von Günter Burkart. *Zeitschrift für Soziologie*, 22, 178-187.
- Beck, Ulrich and Beck-Gernsheim, Elisabeth (1994). Individualisierung in modernen Gesellschaften: Perspektiven und Kontroversen einer subjektorientierten Soziologie. In Ulrich Beck & Elisabeth Beck-Gernsheim (Eds.), *Risikante Freiheiten. Individualisierung in modernen Gesellschaften* (pp.10-39). Frankfurt a. M.: Suhrkamp.
- Becker, A .H. (2001). Social Impact Assessment, *European Journal of Operational Research*, 128(2), 311-321.
- Beck-Gernsheim, Elisabeth & Ostner, Ilona (1978). Frauen verändern – Berufe nicht? Ein theoretischer Ansatz zur Problematik von Frau und Beruf. *Soziale Welt*, 29, 257-287.
- Beffa, J.L., Boyer, R., & J.P. Touffut. (1999). Les relations salariales en France: Etat, entreprises, marchés financiers, *Notes de la Fondation Saint-Simon*, 107.
- Bell, D. (1973). 'The coming of Post- Industrial Society,' New York, Basic Books pp 507.
- Bell, D. (1973). 'The coming of Post- Industrial Society,' New York, Basic Books pp 507.
- Bergeron, S. (2001).Political economy discourses of globalization and feminist politics. *Signs*, 26(4), 983-1006.
- Berings, D., De Fruyt.F., and Bouwen, R. (2004). Work values and personality traits as predictors of enterprising, social, and vocational interests. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 36, 153-180.
- Berry, B.J.L. (1991). *Long Wave Rhythms in Economic Development and Political Behaviour*, Johns Hopkins University Press, Baltimore.

- Berry, B.J.L. (2000) A pacemaker for the long wave, *Technology Forecasting and Social Change*, 63, 1-23.
- Bhatnagar, J. (2007). Talent management strategy of employee engagement in Indian ITES employees: key to retention. *Employee Relations*, 29, 640–663.
- Biddle, B. J. (1979) .Role Theory: Expectations, Identities, and Behaviors. Academic Press, New York.
- Bilsky & Koch. M. On the content and Structure of Values: Universal or Methodological artifacts? Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Münster, Germany.
- Blau, G. (1999). Testing the longitudinal impact of work variables and performance appraisal satisfaction on subsequent overall job satisfaction. *Human Relations*, 52, 1099-1113.
- Bloom, D. E., & Canning, (2006). “Booms, Busts, and Echoes: How the Biggest Demographic Upheaval in history is Affecting Global development,” *Finance and Development*, 43, 3, 8-13.
- Borg, I. & Groenen, P. (1997). *Modern Multidimensional Scaling*. Berlin: Springer.
- Borg, I. & Shye, S. (1995). *Facet theory: Form and content*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Boulding, K. (1958). Where does business history go from here? *Business History Review*, 36, 11-20.
- Braithwaite, V.A., & Law, H.G. (1985). Structure of human values: Testing the adequacy of the Rokeach Value Survey. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 49, 250-263.
- Brisson. C., Larocque. B., Moisan. J. (2000). Psychosocial factors at work, smoking, sedentary behavior, and body mass index: a prevalence study among 6995 white-collar workers. *Journal of Occupational Environment Medicine*, 42, 40–46.

- Brown, W., S. Deakin., M. Hudson., Pratten, C., & Ryan, P. (1998). The individualization of employment contracts in Britain. *Volume 4*, of Employment Relationships Research Series, London: United Kingdom Department of Trade and Industry.
- Budhwar, P., & Malhotra, N. (2008). Patterns of work processes and emerging problems in Indian call centres. In Thite, M. and Russell, B. (Eds.) *The Next Available Operator: Managing Human Resources in Indian Call Centres/BPO Providers*. Sage: Delhi.
- Budhwar, P., Luthar, H., & Bhatnagar, J. (2006a). The dynamics of HRM systems in Indian BPO firms. *Journal of Labor Research*, 27, 339–360.
- Budhwar, P., Varma, A., Singh, V., & Dhar, R. (2006b). HRM systems of Indian call centres: An exploratory study. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17, 881–897.
- Calantone, Roger J., C.Schewe, & C.T.Allen (1980). Targeting specific advertising messages at tourist segments. In *Tourism Marketing and Management*, Donald E.Hawkins, Elwood L.Shafer and James M. Rovelstad(Eds) . Washington DC: George Washington University, 133-147.
- Campbell, D.T., & Stanley, J.C., (1963). *Experimental and Quasi-experimental Design for Research*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Press.
- Canter, D. (Ed.). (1985). *Facet theory*. New York: Springer.
- Carayon, P. (1993). Effects of electronic performance monitoring on job design and worker stress: Review of the literature and conceptual model. *Human Factors*, 35, 385-395.
- Carlile, P.R., & Christensen, C.M. (2004). The Cycles of Theory Building in Management Research, *Harvard Business School Working Paper*.
- Carlile, P.R., & Christensen, C.M. (2004). The Cycles of Theory Building in Management Research, *Harvard Business School Working Paper*. Version 5.0.no. 05-057.

- Carroll, J.D., & Chang, J.C. (1970). Analysis of individual differences in multidimensional scaling via an N-way generalization of Eckhart Young decomposition. *Psychometrika*, 35, 283-319.
- Carroll, Newgren E, Kenneth & B.Archie, (1979) Social Forecasting in U.S. Corporations-A Survey, *Long Range Planning*, 12 Mitton, R. and Willmott, M. (2005). A Social Forecast Revisited. *Futures*, 37, 39-50.
- Carty, V. (1997). Ideology and forms of domination in the organization of the global production and consumption of goods in the emerging postmodern era: A case study of Nike Corporation and the implications for gender. *Gender, Work and Organization*, 4(4), 189-201.
- Castells, M (1996). 'The Rise of Network society,' New York: Blackwell.
- Castells, M (2000b). Materials for an exploratory theory of the network society. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 51, 5-24.
- Castells, M. (1996) The Information Age Vol 1: The Rise of the Network Society. Oxford: Blackwell
- Castells, M. (1997a).The Power of Identity, Oxford: Blackwell
- Castells, M. (1997b). An Introduction to the Information Age. *City. Seven*, 6-16.
- Castells, M. (1999). The Social Implications of Information and Communication Technologies. UNESCO's World Social Science Report.
- Castells, M. (2000a). End of Millennium, Oxford, Blackwell.
- Castells, M. (2000c).Towards a sociology of the network society. *Contemporary Sociology*, 29, 693-699.
- Castells, M. (2004). Informationalism, Networks, and Network Society: A Theoretical Blue printing, The network society: A Cross-Cultural Perspective, Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar.

- Chalykoff, J., & Kochan, T. (1989). Computer-aided monitoring its influence on employee job satisfaction and turnover. *Personal Psychology*, 42, 807-834.
- Chew, I., and Putti, J. (1995). Relationship on work-related values of Singaporean and Japanese managers in Singapore. *Human Relations*, 48, 1149-1170.
- Chithelen, I. (2004). Outsourcing to India: causes, reaction, and prospects. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 39 (10), 1022-24.
- Choffat. P., Desbazelle. A., Eugène, G. (1999). Etude de postes de travail utilisant le couple téléphone-écran dans les services de relation clientèle. *Arch Mal Prof*, 60, 755–759.
- Christine, C., Gillian, B., & Garavan, N.T. (2008). The Psychological Contract in Call Centres: An Employee Perspective. *Journal of Industrial Relations*, 50, 229-142.
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioural Sciences*. (2nd edition). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Earlbaum Associates.
- Cohen, L., & El-Sawad (2007). Lived Experiences of Offshoring: An Examination of UK and Indian Financial Service Employee's Accounts of Themselves and One Another, *Human Relations*, 60, 1235.
- Cronbach, L.J. & Meehl, P.E. (1955). Construct validity in psychological tests. *Psychological Bulletin*, 52, 281-302.
- D'Cruz, P., & Noronha, E. (2007). Technical call centres: beyond 'electronic sweatshops' and 'assembly lines in the head.' *Global Business Review*, 8, 53–67.
- Dancer, L.S. (Ed.) (1990). Facet Theory (Special issue). *Applied Psychology*, 39 (4).
- Das, Diya., Dharwadkar, Ravi., & Brandes, Pamela. (2008). The Importance of being 'Indian': Identity Centrality and Work Outcomes in an Off-shored Call Center in India, *Human Relations*, 61, 1499.

- Dataquest –IDC Employee Satisfaction Survey. (2007). (Available at http://dqindia.ciol.com/content/top_stories/2007/107111617.asp and accessed in June 2007)
- Davis, G.F., McAdam, D., Scott, W.R., & Zald, M.N. (2004). *Social movements and organization theory*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- de Jouvenel, Bertrand. 1967. *The art of conjecture*. New York: Basic Books.
- de Man, A. P. (2004) *The Network Economy: Strategy, Structure and Management*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar.
- Deery, S., Iverson, R., Walsk, J. (2002). Work relationships in telephone call centres: understanding emotional exhaustion and employee withdrawal, *Journal of Management Studies*, 39,471–496.
- Demaris, A. (1995). A tutorial in logistic regression. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 57, 956-68.
- Devezas T.C, Linstone H.A, and Santos H.J.S. (2005). The Growth Dynamics of the Internet and Long Wave Theory, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 72, 913-915.
- Devezas T.C., & Corredine J. (2001). The biological determinants of long wave behaviour in socioeconomic growth and development, *Technology Forecasting and Social Change*, 68, 1-57.
- Dillman, D.A. (1978): *Mail and Telephone Surveys: The Total Design Method*, New York: Wiley.
- DiMaggio, P. (2001) 'Introduction', in P. DiMaggio (Ed.) *The Twenty-First Century Firm*, pp. 3–30. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Dormann, C., & Zijlstra, F. (2003). 'Call Centres: High on Technology, High on Emotions,' *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 12(4), 305-10.

- Dossani, R., & Kenney, M. (2003). Went for cost, stayed for quality? Moving the back office to India. Asia Pacific research Centre Working Paper, Stanford, CA, USA. (Accessed from <http://APARC.stanford.edu>).
- Dunnette, P. (1970). *Psychology and Industry*. London: The Callier-McMillan Company.
- Elizur, D., Borg, I., Hunt, R., & Beck I.M. (1991). The structure of work values: A cross-cultural comparison. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 12, 21-38.
- Ellis, V., & Taylor, P. (2006). 'You don't know what you've got till it's gone': re-contextualizing the origins, development, and impact of the call centre. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 21, 107-122.
- Erlang, A.K. (1948). On the rational determination of the number of circuits. In *The Life and Works of A.K. Erlang*, E. Brockmeyer, H.L. Halstrom and A. Jensen (Eds.). Copenhagen: The Copenhagen Telephone Company, 1948.
- Everitt, B.S. (1993). *Cluster Analysis*. New York: Halsted Press.
- Eysenck, J.H. *The Psychology of Politics* (London, Routledge, and Kegan Paul).
- Farh, J.L., Hackett, R.D., & Liang, J. (2007). Individual-level cultural values as moderators of perceived organizational support-employees outcomes relationships in China: Comparing the effects of power distance and traditionality. *Academy of management Journal*, 50, 715-729.
- Farh, J.L., Hackett, R.D., & Liang, J. (2007). Individual-level cultural values as moderators of perceived organizational support-employee outcomes relationships in China: Comparing the effects of power distance and traditionality. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50, 715-729.
- Feather, N.T. (1975). *Values in education and society*. New York Free Press.
- Feather, N.T. (1982). Human values and prediction of action: An expectancy-valance analysis. In N.T. Feather (Ed.), *Expectations and Actions: Expectancy-*

value models in psychology(263-289).Hillsdale,Nj: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.

Feather, N.T.(1971). Organization and discrepancy in cognitive structures. *Psychology Review*, 78, 355-379.

Feldman, S. A., & Hurn, C, (1966). "The Experience of Modernization," *Sociometry*, 29, 378-395.

Felling, A., & Peters, J. (1984). Conservatisme in Nederland nadir bekeken. *Mens en Maatschappij*, 59, 339-362.

Felstead, A., & Jewson, N. (1999) Global Trends in Flexible Labour. London: Macmillan.

Fernie, S. & Metcalf, D. (1998). (Not) hanging on the telephone: payment systems in the new sweatshops. *Centrepiece*, 3, 7-11.

Fernie, S. (2004). Call centre HRM and performance outcomes: does workplace governance matter? In Deery, S. and Kinnie, N. (Eds.), Call Centres and Human Resource Management: A Cross-National Perspective. Basingstoke: Palgrave.

Fernie, S., & Metcalf, D. (1998). (Not) Hanging on the Telephone: Payment Systems in the New Sweatshops. London: *Centre for Economic Performance*, London School of Economics and Political Science.

Fischer, R., & Smith, P.B. (2006). Who cares about justice: The moderating effect of values on the link between organizational justice and work behaviour. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 55, 541-562.

Fleming, P., & Spicer, André. (2004). 'You Can Checkout Anytime, but You Can Never Leave' Spatial Boundaries in a High Commitment Organization. *Human Relations*, 57, 75-94.

Foucault, M. (1977). Discipline and Punish The Birth of the Prison. London: Allen Lane.

- Fowles, J. (1977). "The problem of values in futures research." *Futures*, 1977, 9 (4), 303-314.
- Francesco, A.N., & Chen, Z.X. (2004). Collectivism in action: It's moderating effects on the relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance in China. *Group & Organization Management*, 29, 425-441.
- Frenkel, S., Korczynski, M., Shire, K., & Tam, M. (1999). *On the Front Line: Organization of Work in the Information Economy*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Frenkel, S., Tam, M., Korczynski, M., & Shire, K. (1998). Beyond bureaucracy? Work organization in call centres. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 9, 957-979.
- Frenkel, S.J., Tam., M, Korczynski, M., & Shire, K. (1998). Beyond Bureaucracy? Work Organization in Call Centres. *The international Journal of Human Resource Management*, 9 (6), 957-979.
- Friedman, T. (2005). *The world is flat. The globalized world in 21st century*. New York: Penguin Books.
- Fu, P.P., Kennedy, J., Tata, J., Yukl, G., Bond, M.H., Peng, T.K., Srinivas, E.S., Howell, J.P., Prieto, L., Koopman, P., Boonstra, J.J., Para, S., Lacassagne, M.F., Higashide, H. & Cheosakul, A. (2004). .The Impact of Societal Cultural Values and Individual Social Beliefs on the perceived Effectiveness of Managerial Influence Strategies: A Meso Approach. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 35, p. 284 – 305.
- Furnham, A.N., Petrides, K.V., Tsaosis, I., Pappas, K., & Garrod, D. (2005). A cross-cultural investigation into the relationship between personality traits and work values. *The Journal of Psychology*, 139, 5-32.
- Gallie, D., White, M., Cheng, Y. & Tomlinson, M. (1998). *Restructuring the Employment Relationship*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.

- Garson, B. (1988). *The electronic sweatshop: How computers are transforming the office of the future into the factory of the past*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Gartner Report. (2006). Gartner's top predictions for IT organizations and users-2007 and beyond. ID No. G00144544.
- Gigerenzer, G., and Goldstein, D.G. (1996). Reasoning the fast and frugal way: Models of bounded rationality. *Psychological Review*, 103, 650-669.
- Gilmer V. H., (1971). *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, Mc Graw-Hill Book Comp., New York.
- Glaser, B., & Strauss, A. (1967). "The Discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies of Qualitative Research." London: Wiedenfeld and Nicholson.
- Glucksmann, M. (2004) 'Call Configurations', *Work, Employment and Society* 18 (4) 795–811.
- Goldthorpe, J., Lockwood, D., Bechofer, F. and Platt, J. (1968). *The affluent worker: Industrial attitudes and behaviour*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Goodrich, J. (1980). Benefit segmentation of US International travelers : An empirical study with American Express. In *Tourism Marketing and Management*, Donald E.Hawkins, Elwood L.Shafer and James M. Rovelstad(Eds). Washington DC: George Washington University, 133-147.
- Graen G. and Scandura, T. A. (1987) Toward a psychology of dyadic organizing. In Cummings, L. L. and Staw, B. M. (eds), *Research in Organizational Behavior*. JAI Press, Greenwich, CT, 9, pp. 175–208.
- Greaver, Maurice. (1999). 'Strategic Outsourcing: A structure Approach to Outsourcing Decisions and Initiatives,' American Management Association, New York.

- Grosjean, V., Ribert-Van de Weerd, C. (2003). Les modes de management dans un call center et leurs conséquences sur le bien-être des opérateurs. *scientifique et technique*, (INRS), NS234, 40.
- Grugulis, I., Warhurst, C., & Keep, E. (2004) 'What's Happening to "Skill"', In C. Warhurst, I. Grugulis, & E. Keep (Eds.) *The Skills that Matter*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Gutek, B. (1995). *The Dynamics of service: reflections on the changing nature of customer /provider interaction*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Guttman, R. & Greenbaum, C.W. (1998). Facet theory: Its development and current status. *European Psychologist*, 3, 13-36.
- Hair, J.F., Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., Anderson, R.E., & Tatham, R.C. (2008). *Multivariate Data Analysis*, (6th ed). Pearson Education, India.
- Haley, Russel I. (1968). Benefit segmentation: A decision oriented research tool. *Journal of Marketing*, 32(30), 35.
- Halman, L. (1991). *Waarden in de westerse Wereld*. Tilburg: Tilburg University Press
- Harman, W.W. (1978). Understanding social change, some comments on "Prediction and social change," *Futures*, 143-147.
- Hartman, S. C., & Yrle, A. C. (1996). Can the hobo phenomenon help explain voluntary turnover? *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 8(4), 11-16.
- Heller, T.C., & Wellbery, D.E. (1986). Introduction. In: T.C.Heller, M.Sosna, and D.E.Wellbery (Eds.), *Reconstructing individualism*, Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Herzberg, F. (1968) *Work and the Nature of Man*. St Albans: Staples Press.
- Heskett, J. L., Sasser, W.E. Jr., & Schlesinger, L. A. (1997). *The Service Profit Chain*. New York: Free Press.

- Hochschild, Arlie, R. (1983). *The Managed Heart*. Berkeley, University of California Press.
- Hofstede, G. (1980). *Cultures consequences*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- Hofstede, G. (1980a). *Culture's Consequences: International Differences in Work Related Values*. Beverley Hills: Sage.
- Hofstede, G. (1980b). Motivation, leadership, and organization: Do American theories apply abroad? *Organizational Dynamics*, 9, 42-63.
- Hofstede, G. (1984). *Culture's Consequences: International Differences in Work Related Values*, Beverley Hills, CA: Sage.
- Hofstede, G. (2002), "The Pitfalls of Cross-National Survey Research: A Reply to the Article by Spector et al. on the Psychometric Properties of the Hofstede Values Survey Module 1984", *Applied Psychology*, 51(1) p. 170 – 178.
- Holman, D. (2002). Employee wellbeing in call centres. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 12, 35–50.
- Holman, D., and Fernie, S. (2000). Can I help you? call centres and job satisfaction, *Centrepiece*, 5(1), accessed from www.centrepiece-magazine.com.
- Holman, D., Batt, R., & Holtgrewe, U. (2007). *The Global Call Centre Report International Perspectives on Management and Employment*. (Available at www.ilr.cornell.edu/globalcallcentre : accessed on 15, July 2009).
- Holman, D., Chissick, C., & Totterdell. (2002). The effects of performance monitoring on emotional labour and well-being in call centres. *Motivation and Emotion*, 26(1), 57-81.
- Hosmer D.W., & Lemeshow, S. (2000). *Applied Logistic Regression*, (2nd edition), New York, Wiley.
- Houlihan, M. (2000). Eyes wide shut? Querying the depth of call centre learning. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 24, 228–240.

- Houlihan, M. (2001) 'Control and Commitment in the Call Centre? More Evidence from the Field,' paper presented to conference on 'Call Centres and Beyond: The Human Resource Implications,' Kings College, London.
- Houlihan, M. (2002) 'Tensions and Variations in Call Centre Management Strategies', *Human Resource Management Journal*, 12(4), 67–85.
- Houlihan, M. (2002). Tensions and variations in call centre management strategies. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 12, 67–85.
- HSE (Health, Safety Executive). (2003). Psychological risk factors in call centres: an evaluation of work design and well-being. Research Report No. 169, 92 p. <http://www.hse.gov.uk/research/rrpdf/rr169.pdf>
- Huff, A. (1999). Presidential address: Changes in organizational knowledge production. *Academy of Management Review*, 25, 288-293.
- Huselid, M. (1995). The impact of human resources management practices on turnover, productivity, and corporate financial performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 38(3), 635-672.
- Hyman, J., Baldry, C., Scholarios, D. & Bunzel, D. (2003) .Work-Life Imbalance in Call Centres and Software Development. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 41(2), 15–39.
- Hyman, J., Baldry, C., Scholarios, D., and Bunzel, D. (2003). Work-Life imbalance in call centres and software development, *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 41(2), 15–39.
- Ilgén, D.R., & Klein, H.J. (1989). Organizational behaviour. *Annual Review of Psychology*. 40, 327-351.
- IMF (2008a). Global Financial Stability Report, International Monetary Fund, Washington D.C. (Dated October 7, 2008).
- IMF (2008b) World Economic Outlook Update, International Monetary Fund, Washington D.C. (Dated November 6, 2008).

- IMF (2009) Global Financial Stability Report: Market Update, International Monetary Fund, Washington D.C. (Dated January 28, 2009).
- India Social Development Report (2006). Council for Social Development, New Delhi.
- Inkeles, Alex. (1960). "Industrial Man: the Relation of Status to Experience, perception, and Value." *American Journal of Sociology*, 66, 1-31.
- Inkeles, Alex. (1969). "Making Men Modern: the causes and consequences of individual change in six developing countries." *American Journal of Sociology*, 75, 208-225.
- Jain, C.S., & Singhvi, S.S. (1977). Environmental Forecasting Non-Profit Professional Organizations, *Long Range Planning*, 10.
- James, B.G. (1978). Social Impact: The Pharmaceutical Industry, *Long Range Planning*, 11.
- Jones, L. E., & Young, F.W. (1972). Structure of a social environment: longitudinal individual differences scaling of an intact group. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*. 24, 1, 108-121.
- Junge, M. (1996). Individualisierungsprozesse und der Wandel von Institutionen. *Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 48, 728-747.
- Katz, D., & Kahn, L.R., (1970). *The Social Psychology of Organizations*, Wiley Eastern, India.
- Khurana, D.N. (2005). "Leveraging India's Demographic Position," *Asian Management Review*, October-December, p 40-43.
- Kinnie, N., Hutchinson, S., & Purcell, J. (2000a). 'Fun and surveillance: the paradox of high commitment management in call centres. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 11,967-985.

- Kinnie, N., Purcell, J., & Hutchinson, S. (2000b). Managing the employment relationship in telephone call centres. In Purcell, K. (Ed.), *Changing Boundaries in Employment*, Bristol: Bristol Academic Press.
- Kluckhohn, C.K.M. (1951). Values and value orientations in the theory of action. In T. Parsons & E. Sils (Eds.). *Toward a general theory of action* (pp. 388-433). Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Kluckhohn, F., & Strodtbeck, F. (1961) *Variations in Value Orientations*. Evanston, Illinois, Row-Peterson.
- Konrad, A.M. & Linnehan, F. (1995). "Formalized HRM Structures: Coordinating Equal Employment Opportunity or Concealing Organizational Practices?" *Academy of Management Journal*. 38(3), p. 787 – 811.
- Korczynski, M. (2001) 'The Contradictions of Service Work: Call Centre as Customer-Orientated Bureaucracy', pp. 79–101 in A. Sturdy, I. Grugulis and H. Willmott (Eds) *Customer Service: Empowerment and Entrapment*. London: Palgrave.
- Korczynski, M. (2003). *Communities of Coping: Collective Emotional Labour in Service Work*, *Organization*, 10, 55-79.
- Korczynski, M., Shire, K., Frenkel, S., & Tam, M. (2000). Service work in consumer capitalism: customers, control, and contradictions. *Work, Employment and Society*, 14, 669–687.
- Kuhn, T. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago : University of Chicago Press.
- Kumar, Rajiv et al. (2009). *Indian Economic Outlook 2008-09 and 2009-10*, Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations. New Delhi.
- Kunda, G. (1992) *Engineering Culture: Control and Commitment in a High Technology Corporation*, Philadelphia, PA: Temple University Press.

- Kunda, G. (1992). *Engineering Culture: Control and Commitment in a High-Tech Corporation*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press.
- Lam, S.K.S., Schaubroeck, J., and Aryees, S. (2002). Relationship between organizational justice and employee work outcomes: A cross-national study. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 23, 1-18.
- Lara Rodriguez, A.L. (2003). El telemarketing en España: Materiales para una cartografía del mundo del trabajo contemporáneo. *Sociología del Trabajo*, 49, 27-59.
- Lawrence, P., & Lorch, J. (1967). Differentiation and Integration in complex organizations. *Administrative Science Quarterly*. 12, 1-30.
- Lebell, D., and Krasner, O.J. (1977). Selecting Environmental Forecasting Techniques Form Business Requirements. *The Academy of Management Review*, 2, (3), 373-383.
- Leidner, Robin. (1999). Emotional labour in service work. *Annals of the American Academy of Political Science*, 56 (1), 81-95.
- Leisering, L. (1997). Individualisierung und "sekundäre Institutionen": der Sozialstaat als Voraussetzung des modernen Individuums in Ulrich Beck & Peter Sopp (Eds.), *Individualisierung und Integration. Neue Konfliktlinien und neuer Integrationsmodus?* (pp.143-159). Opladen: Leske Budrich.
- Levy, S. (1990). Values and deeds. *Applied Psychology*. 39, 379-400.
- Lewin, K. (1952). Constructs in field theory. In D.Cartwright (Ed.), *Field theory in social science: Selected theoretical papers by Kurt Lewin* (p. 30-42). London: Tavistock.
- Linton, R. (1936). *The Study of Man*. New York: Appleton-Century.
- Locke, E. A. (1976). The nature and causes of job satisfaction. In M. D. Dunnette (Ed.), *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology* (p. 1297-1349). Chicago: Rand McNally.

- Locke, E. A. (1976). The nature and causes of job satisfaction. In M. D. Dunnette (Ed.), *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology*. Chicago: Rand McNally.
- Mandelbaum, A. (2004). Call Centers Research Bibliography with Abstracts. Technion Technical Report, 2001. (Downloaded from: <http://ie.technion.ac.il/serveng> on 28 September 2007.)
- Mandelbaum, A., Sakov, A., Zeltyn, s. (2001). "Empirical Analysis of a Call Center,"
- March, J.G., and Simon, H.A. (1958). *Organizations*: New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Marchetti, C. (1980). Society as a learning system: discovery, invention, and innovation cycles revisited, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 18, 267-282.
- Marchetti, C. (1988) Infrastructure for movement: past and future, chapter 7, In J.H.Ausubel, R.Herman (Eds), *Cities and the Vital Systems: Infrastructure Past, Present and Future*, National Academy of Engineering.
- Marchington, M., Rubery, J., Grimshaw, D., & Willmott, H. (2005). *Fragmenting work*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Meadows, D. H. et al. (1972a). *The Limits to Growth* (Universe Books, New York).
- Meadows, D. L. & Meadows, D. H. (eds.) (1972b) *Toward Global Equilibrium- Collected Papers* (Wright-Allen Press, Boston, Massachusetts.)
- Meadows, D.L. (1972c). Toward a Science of Social Forecasting, *Proceedings of National Academy of Science, United States of America*, 69, 12, 3828-3831, (www.pnas.org).
- Meddin, I. (1975). Attitudes, values, and related concepts: a system of classification. *Social Science Quarterly*, 55 (4), 889-900.
- Metron, R.K. (1957). *Social theory and Social Structure*. New York: Free Press.

- Metz, R. (2005). Empirical Evidence and Causation of Kondratieff Cycles, presented at the NATO Advanced Research Workshop on Kondratieff Waves, Warfare and World Security, February, 14-18 , 2005, Covilhã, Portugal, to be published in the proceedings.
- Middendrop, C.P. (1978). Progressiveness and conservatism. The Hague: Mouton.
- Miller, E.J. & Rice.A.K. (1967). Systems of Organization: The Control of Task and Sentient Boundaries. London: Tavistock.
- Mirchandani, K. (2004). Practices of global capital: gaps, cracks, and ironies in transnational call centres in India. *Global Networks*, 4, 355–373.
- Mishra, P. (2006). Temptations of the west. How to be modern in India, Pakistan and beyond. London, Picador.
- Mitchell, T.R. & Larson, J. (1987). People in Organizational Behavior. New York, McGraw Hill Company.
- Mitton, R. and Willmott, M. (2005). A Social Forecast Revisited. *Futures*, 37, 39-50.
- Mokhtarian, L.P., Ory, T.D., & Cao, X. (2007). Shopping-related attitudes: A factor and cluster analysis of Northern California shoppers. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*. 36, 204-228.
- Morris, C. (1956). Varieties of human value. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Morris, G.K. (1975). Forecasting the Impact of Social Change, *Long Range Planning*.
- Morris, G.K. (1975). Forecasting the Impact of Social Change, *Long Range Planning*.
- Mount, M., Ilies, R., & Johnson, E. (2006). Relationship of personality traits and counterproductive work behaviors: The mediating effects of job satisfaction. *Personnel Psychology*, 59, 591-622
- Mowday, R.T. (1991). Equity theory predictions of behaviour in organizations. In R.M. Steers & L.W. Porter (Eds). Motivation and work behaviour: 89-110. New York: Mc Graw-Hill.

- Mowday, R.T. (1997). 1996 presidential address: Reaffirming our scholarly values. *Academy of Management Review*, 22, 335-345.
- Mueller, F. (1994). Teams between Hierarchy and Commitment: Change Strategies and the “Internal Environment.” *Journal of Management Studies*, 31(3), 383–403.
- Mumford, E. (1972) Job Satisfaction. London: Longman.
- Mumford, E. (1991). Job Satisfaction: A Method of Analysis, *Personnel Review*, 20(3), 2–16.
- Neck, C.P., Neck, H.M., Manz, C.C. and Godwin, J. (1999). I think I can, I think I can: A Self-Leadership Perspective towards Enhancing Entrepreneur Thought Patterns, Self-Efficacy, and Performance. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 14 (6), 477–501.
- Newcomb, T.M. (1950). Social Psychology. New York: Dryden. Organ, D. W., & Ryan, K. (1995). A meta-analytic review of attitudinal and dispositional predictors of organizational citizenship behavior. *Personnel Psychology*, 48, 775-802.
- Newgren E, Kenneth. (1976). Social forecasting: An assessment of existing practices within business organizations, Ph.D. dissertation, University of Georgia.
- Newgren E, Kenneth. (1977) Forecasting the social-political environment: an assessment of current business practices. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 290-294.
- Niedhammer. I., Chastang J-F., Gendrey. L., David. S., Degioanni.S. (2006). Psychometric properties of the French version of karasek’s “Job Content Questionnaire” and its scales measuring psychological pressures, decisional latitude, and social support: the results of the summer. *Santé Publique*, 18, 413–427.

- Niehoff, P.B., & Moorman, H.R. (1993). Justice as a mediator of the relationship between methods of monitoring and organizational citizenship behaviour, *Academy of Management Journal*, 36, 527-556.
- Nonaka, I., Takeuchi, H., & Umemoto, K. (1996). A theory of organizational knowledge creation. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 11(7-8), 820-833.
- Noon, M., & Blyton, P. (1997). *The Realities of work*. Basingstoke: Macmillan.
- Norling, P., (2001). Call Centre companies and New Patterns of Organization, *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, 22, 155-168.
- Ong, A. (1991). The gender of labour politics of post modernity. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 20, 279-309.
- Organ, D. W., & Ryan, K. (1995). A meta-analytic review of attitudinal and dispositional predictors of organizational citizenship behavior. *Personnel Psychology*, 48, 775-802.
- Page, C. (2003). Call center job satisfaction: Intrinsic and extrinsic factors and the role of organizational culture, paper prepared for British Academy of Management Annual Conference, 15–17 September, Leeds Business School, Leeds Metropolitan University.
- Pampel, F.C. (2000). *Logistic Regression: A Primer*, Sage University Papers Series on Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences, no-07-096. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Parè, G., & Tremblay, M. (2007). The influence of High Involvement Human Resources Practices, Procedural Justice, Organizational commitment and Citizenship Behaviors on Information Technology Professional's Turnover Intentions, *Group & Organization Management*, 32, 326-357.
- Parker, S.K. and P.R. Jackson (1993) 'The Implementation of High Performance Work Teams', pp. 42–56 in D. Gowler, K. Legge, and C. Clegg (eds) *Case*

Studies in Organizational Behaviour and Human Resource Management,
London: Chapman.

Parsons, T. (1951). *The Social System*. New York, Free Press.

Prabhakar, K. (2007). 'Social Forecasting-Relevance in Strategic Planning for corporate Sector,' Presentation at 10th International Strategic Management Forum Convention at Indian Institute of Technology, Mumbai.

Prabhakar, K. (2007). 'Social Forecasting-Relevance in Strategic Planning for corporate Sector,' Presentation at 10th International Strategic Management Forum Convention at Indian Institute of Technology, Mumbai.

Prahalad, C.K., & Hamel, G. (1990). The core competence of the corporation. *Harvard Business Review*, 68(3), 79-91.

Rafaeli, A (1989), "When Cashiers Meet Customers: An Analysis of the Role of Supermarket Cashiers," *Academy of Journal of Management*, 30, 245-73.

Rainnie, A., Barrett, R. Burgess, J. & Connell, J. (2008). Introduction Call Centres, the Networked Economy and the Value Chain, *Journal of Industrial Relations*, 50, 195-208.

Rainnie, A., Barrett, R., Burgess, G., & Connell, J. (2008). Introduction Call Centres, the Networked Economy and the Value Chain, *Journal of Industrial Relations*, 50, 196-208.

Ramachandran, J. & Mukherji, S. (2007). Outsourcing: practice in search of a theory. *IIMB Management Review*, 3,103-110.

Ravlin, E.C. (1995). Values, IN N.Nicholson (Ed.,) *The Blackwell Encyclopedic Dictionary of Organizational Behaviour*.(Blackwell Publishers, Oxford).

Remesh, B.P. (2004). 'Cyber coolies,' in BPO: insecurities and vulnerabilities of Non-standard work. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 39, 492-97.

- Richardson, R. & Marshall, J.N. (1999). Teleservices, call centres and urban and regional development, *The Service Industries Journal*, 19(1), 96-116. (Available at : [http:// proquest.umi.com/pqdweb](http://proquest.umi.com/pqdweb) , retrieved on 15th January 2008)
- Robbins S. P., 1996. *Organizational Behavior*, Prentice Hall, Inc, Seventh Edition, New Jersey.
- Roe, R.A., and Ester, P. (1999). Values and work: Empirical findings and theoretical perspective. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 48, 1-21.
- Roethlisberger, F.G., & Dickson .W.J. (1964). *Management and the Worker*. New York: John Wiley.
- Rohan, M.J. (2000). A Rose by Any Name? The Values Construct, *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 4, 255-277.
- Rokeach, M. & Parker, S. (1970a) Values as social indicators of poverty and race relations in America. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 388, 97-111.
- Rokeach, M. (1968). *Beliefs, attitudes, and values*. San Francisco: Josey-Bass.
- Rokeach, M. (1969). The role of values in public opinion research. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 1969, 32, 547-549.
- Rokeach, M. (1970b) *Beliefs, attitudes, and values: A theory of organization and change*. San Francisco: Jossey Bass.
- Rokeach, M. (1971) Long-range experimental modification of values, attitudes, and behavior. *American Psychologist*, 26, 453-459.
- Rokeach, M. (1973). *The nature of human values*. New York: The Free Press.
- Rokeach, M. (1973). *The nature of human values*. New York: The Free Press.

- Rokeach, M. (1979). From individual to institutional values: With special reference to the values of science. In M. Rokeach (Ed.), *Understanding human values: Individual and societal* (pp. 47-70). New York: Free Press.
- Rose, E., & Wright, G. (2005). Satisfaction and dimensions of control among call centre customer service representatives, *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 16(1), 136 – 160.
- Rose, M. (1994). Job satisfaction, job skills and personal skills. In Penn, R., Rose, M. and
- Rubery, J. (Eds) *Skill and Occupational Change*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Russell, B. (2006). Skill and info-service work in Australian call centres. In Burgess, J. and Connell, J. (Eds), *Developments in the Call Centre Industry: Analysis, Changes and Challenges*. London: Routledge.
- Russell, B. (2008). Call Centres A decade of Research. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 10 (3), 195-219.
- Saari, L. M., & Judge, T. A. (2004). Employee attitudes and job satisfaction. *Human Resource Management*, 43, 395-407.
- Salzinger, L. (2003). *Genders in production: Making workers in Mexico's global factories*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Sarkar, Santanu. (2007). Individualism-Collectivism as Predictors of Employee Attitudes towards Union Membership: An Empirical Study of Employees of BPO sector in India, Department of Personnel Management and Industrial Relations, Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai, India.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2002): *Research Methods for Business Students*, London: Financial Times, Prentice Hall.
- Schienstock, G. (2002). 'The Network as a New Paradigm of Business Restructuring,' paper presented at the Workshop for the Labour, Organization, and Competence in National Innovation Systems Project, Paris, April 2002.

- Schlesinger, L. A., & Zornitsky, J. (1991). Job satisfaction, service capability, and customer satisfaction: An examination of linkages and management implications. *Human Resource Planning, 14*, 141-149
- Schneider, B. (1987). The people make the place. *Personnel Psychology, 40*, 437-453.
- Schneider, Benjamin, and David E. B. (1985). Employee and customer perceptions of service in banks: Replication and Extension, *Journal of Applied Psychology, 70*, 423-33.
- Schwartz, A. M. (1967). Trends in White Attitudes toward Black people (Chicago, National Opinion Research Centre, United States).
- Schwartz, A. Mildred. (1967). Trends in White Attitudes toward Black people (Chicago, National Opinion Research Centre, United States).
- Schwartz, S. (1994). Are there universal aspects in the structure and contents of human values? *Journal of Social Issues, 50*, 19-45.
- Schwartz, S. (1996). Value priorities and behavior: Applying a theory of integrated value systems. In C. Selgman, J.M. Olson, & M.P. Zanna (Eds.), *The Ontario symposium: The psychology of values* (8, 1-24). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Schwartz, S. (1999). A theory of cultural values and some implications for work. *Applied Psychology: An International Review, 48*, 23-47.
- Schwartz, S. H., & Bilsky, W. (1990). Toward a psychological structure of human values, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 58*, 878-891.
- Schwartz, S. H., & Bilsky, W. (1990). Toward a psychological structure of human values, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 58*, 878-891.
- Schwartz, S.H. & Bilsky, W. (1987). Toward a universal psychological structure of human values. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 58*, 550-562.

- Schwartz, S.H. (1992). Universals in the content and structure of values: Theoretical advances and empirical tests in 20 countries. In M.P. Zanna (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology*, 24, 1-65. San Diego: Academic.
- Schwartz, S.H. (1992). Universals in the content and structure of values: Theoretical advances and empirical tests in twenty countries. In M.P.Zanna (Ed.) *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 24, p-1-65. San Diego: Academic.
- Schwartz, S.H. (1994), "Beyond Individualism / Collectivism: New Cultural Dimensions of Values" in U. Kim, H.C. Triandis, C. Kagitcibasi, S.C. Choi and C. Yoon (eds.), *Individualism and Collectivism: Theory, Method and Applications*, Thousand Oaks,CA: Sage.
- Schwartz, S.H., & Bilsky, W. (1987). Toward a psychological structure of human values. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 53, 550-562.
- Schwartz, S.H., & Bilsky, W. (1987). Toward a psychological structure of human values, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 53, 550-562.
- Scott, W. R. (2001). *Institutions and organizations* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Sewell, G. (1998). The discipline of teams: the control of team-based industrial work through electronic and peer surveillance. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 43, 397-428.
- Sewell, G., & Wilkinson, B. (1992). 'Someone to watch over me': surveillance, discipline and the just in time labour process. *Sociology*, 26.
- Shye, S. (1994). Smallest Space Analysis. In: *The International Encyclopedia of Education*(pp. 5497-5504). Oxford: Pergamon Press.
- Smith, M.J., Carayon, P., Sanders, K.J., Lim, S.Y., &LeGrande, D. (1992). Employee stress and health complaints in jobs with and without monitoring. *Applied Ergonomics*, 23, 17-27.

- Somers, M.J., & Birnbaum, D. (1998). Work-Related commitment and job performance: It is also the nature of the performance that counts. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 19,621-634.
- Standing, G. (1999) Global Labour Flexibility. London: Macmillan.
- Stanton, J.M. (2000). Reactions to employee performance monitoring: Framework, review, and research directions. *Human Performance*, 13, 85-113.
- Stanton, J.M., & BarnesFarrel, J.L.(1996). Effects of electronic performance monitoring on personal control, satisfaction, and performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81,738-745.
- Steinberg, R.J., and Figart, D.M. (1999). Emotional labour Since the Managed Heart. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 56(1), 8-26.
- Storey, J. and Bacon, N. (1993). Individualism and Collectivism: Into the 1990's, *International Journal of Human Resources Management*. 4(3), 665-84.
- Taylor, G.R. (1977). "Prediction and social change." *Futures*, 9 (5), 404-414.
- Taylor, P. & Bain, P. (1999). An assembly line in the head: work and employee relations in the call centre. *Industrial Relations Journal*, 30, 101-117.
- Taylor, P. and Bain, P. (2007). Reflections on the Call Centre – A Reply to Blucksmann. *Work, Employment and Society*, 21(2), 349–62.
- Taylor, P., & Bain, P. (1999). 'An assembly line in the head': work and employee relations in the call centre. *Industrial Relations Journal*, 30, 101–117.
- Taylor, P., & Bain.P. (2005).India calling to far way towns: The call centre labour process and globalization. *Work, Employment and Society*, 19(2), 261-282.
- Taylor, P., &Bain, P. (2007) 'Reflections on the Call Centre', *Work, Employment and Society* 21(2), 349–62.

- Taylor, P., and Bain, P. (2003). Subterranean Work sick Blues : Humour as Subversion in Two Call Centres,' *Organization Studies* 24(9), 1487–509.
- Taylor, P., Baldry, C., Bain, P., & Ellis, V. (2003). 'A unique working environment': health, sickness, and absence management in UK call centres. *Work, Employment and Society*, 17, 435–458.
- Testa, M. R. (2001). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and effort in the service environment. *Journal of Psychology*, 135, 222-236.
- Thite, M. & Russell, B. (2007). India and Business Process Outsourcing. In Burgess, J. & Connell, J. (Eds.), *Globalization and Work in Asia*. Oxford: Chandos.
- Thompson, P., & McHugh, D. (2002). *Work Organizations*. London: Palgrave.
- Thompson, P., & Warhurst, C. (1998) *Workplaces of the Future*. Basingstoke: Macmillan.
- Tomkins, S.S. (1962). *Affect imagery consciousness* (Vol. 1). New York: Springer.
- Trochim, William M. *The Research Methods Knowledge Base*, second Edition. (The book is available in website and accessed from website)
- Turner, R. H. (1956) Role-taking, role standpoint, and reference group behavior. *American Journal of Sociology*, 61, 316–328.
- Valverde, M., Ryan, G., & Gorjup, T. (2007). An examination of the quality of jobs in call centre industry, *International Advanced Economic Research*, 13, 146-156.
- Van den Broek, A., & Heunks, F. (1994). Political culture. Pattern of political orientations and behaviour. In P.Ester, L.Halman and R. de Moor (Eds), *the individualizing society*. Tilburg: Tilburg University Press, 159-228.
- Van den Broek, D. (2002). Monitoring and surveillance in call centres: some responses from Australian employees. *Labour and Industry*, 12, 43–58.

- Van den Broek, D., Callaghan, G. & Thompson, P. (2004). Teams without teamwork? Explaining the call centre paradox. *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, 25, 197–218.
- Van den Ven, A.H. (2007). Engaged scholarship: A guide for organizational and social research. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Varoom, V. 1954. Work and motivation. New York: Wiley.
- Vendramin, P.(2004). Le travail au singulier: Le lien social a Yepreuve de Vindividualisation (Bruylant-Academia, L'Harmattan, Louvain-la-Neuve).
- Wagner, J.A. (1995), “Studies of Individualism-Collectivism: Effects of Cooperation in Groups.” *Academy of Management Journal*, 38(1), pp. 152–172
- Wallace, M.C. Eagleson, G., & Waldersee, R. (2000). The Sacrificial HR Strategy in Call Centers, *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 11(2), 174-185.
- Walsh, J., & Derry, S. (2005). Refashioning organizational boundaries: Outsourcing customer service work. *Journal of Management Studies*, 43(4), 557-582.
- Watson, T. (2004) *Sociology, Work, and Industry*. London: Routledge.
- Wegge, J., Schmidt, K., Parkes, C., & van Dick, K. (2007). ‘Taking a sickie’: Job satisfaction and job involvement as interactive predictors of absenteeism in a public organization. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 80, 77-89
- Weiss, H. M. (2002). Deconstructing job satisfaction: separating evaluations, beliefs, and affective experiences. *Human Resource Management Review*, 12, 173-194.
- Weiss, H. M. (2002). Deconstructing job satisfaction: separating evaluations, beliefs, and affective experiences. *Human Resource Management Review*, 12, 173-194

- Whetten, D. A., Felin, T., & King, B. G. (2009). The practice of theory borrowing in organizational studies: Current issues and future directions, *Journal of Management*. 35(3), 537-563.
- Whyte, W.F. (1946). When Employees and Customers Meet, In W.F.Whyte (Ed.) *Industry and Society*, pp.123-47. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Witt, A.L., Andrews, M., and Carlson S. (2004). When Conscientiousness is not enough: Emotional exhaustion and performance among call centre customer service representatives, *Journal of Management*, 30 (1), 149-160.
- Witt, L.A., Andrews, C.M., & Carlson, S.D. (2004).When conscientiousness is not enough: emotional exhaustion and performance among call center customer service representatives. *Journal of Management*, 30(1), 149-160.
- Wohlrab-Sahr,M.(1997).Individualisierung:Differenzierungsprozess und Zurechnungsmodus. In Ulrich Beck & Peter Sopp (Eds.), *Individualisierung und Integration: Neue Konfliktlinien und neuer Integrationsmodus?* (pp.23-36).
- Wood, M.R., & Zürcher jr., L.A. (1988). *The development of personal documents*, New York: Greenwood Press.
- Wrightsman, L.S. (1991). Interpersonal trust and attitude toward human nature. In J.P. Robnson, P.R. Shaver, & L.S. Wrightsman (Eds.), *Measures of personality and social psychological attitudes* (pp. 373-412). New York Academic.
- Yankelovich, D. et al. (1985). *The world at work*, New York: Octogon Books.
- Yin, R. (1984). *Case Study Research*. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications.
- Zald, M. (1993). Organization studies as a scientific and humanistic enterprise. *Organization Science*. 513-530.
- Zapf, D., Isic, A., Bechtoldt, M. & Blau, P. (2003) ‘What is Typical for Call Centre Jobs? : Job Characteristics and Service Interactions in Different Call

Centres,' *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*,
12(4), 311–40.

Zenger, T.R., and Hesterly, W.S. (1997). The disaggregation of corporations:
Selective intervention, high-powered incentives, and molecular units.
Organization Science. 8, 209-222.

Zetterberg, H. L. (1992). "The Sociology of Values: the Swedish Value Space", paper
presented at the 87th Annual Meeting, of the American Sociological
Association, August 20-24, in Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, reprinted in
revised form in Richard Swedberg & Emil Uddhammar (eds) *Sociological
Endeavor* , City University Press, Stockholm 1997, pp. 191-219.

Zetterberg, H. L. (1992). "The Sociology of Values: the Swedish Value Space", paper
presented at the 87th Annual Meeting, of the American Sociological
Association, August 20-24, in Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, reprinted in
revised form in Richard Swedberg & Emil Uddhammar (eds) *Sociological
Endeavor* , City University Press, Stockholm 1997, pp. 191-219.

Zetterberg, K.B, and Zetterberg, H.L (1997). Values (available at
www.valuescope.com and accessed on August 2006).

Zetterberg, K.B, and Zetterberg, H.L (1997). www.vlauescope.com (Extensive
compilation has been provided by both the authors in the website).

Zijderveld, A.C. (1983). De Culturele factor. 's-Gravenhage: Vuga.

Websites

<http://www-2.cs.cmu.edu/~awm/tutorials/kmeans.html>

<http://www.cs.ualberta.ca/~zaiane/courses/cmput690/slides/Chapter8/index.html>

<http://www.analytictech.com/networks/hiclus.htm>

<http://www.cse.iitb.ac.in/dbms/Data/Courses/CS632/1999/clustering/dbms.html>

<http://www.socialresearchmethods.net/kb/>